

An exploration of internationalisation in the context of UK higher education with specific focus on universities: challenges and strategies

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DECLARATION

I declare that the work contained in this thesis has not been submitted for any other award and that it is all my own work. I also confirm that this work fully acknowledges opinions, ideas, and contributions from the work of others. Any ethical clearance for the research presented in this thesis has been approved. Approval has been sought and granted by the UWS Ethics Committee in November 2019

Pranita R Gosavi

DEDICATION

This journey is dedicated with love and respect to my mother, Rajashree Gosavi, sister, Prajakta Gosavi and Raj Asre who has always been with me in all ups and downs throughout this journey.

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This thesis would not have been possible without the love, support, and guidance of many people throughout my Doctorate journey in the United Kingdom. Many people contributed in various ways to the completion of this thesis, and I am grateful to each and every one of them. As a result, I feel obliged to express my profound gratitude to everyone who assisted and encouraged me to complete my studies.

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“This ongoing journey requires faith in the power of a single lamp to hold the darkness at bay. It demands confidence in the power of humble actions to act as an inspiration, or a magnet, and draw in greater energies. There is also a need for certain agility and strategic planning that puts these positive energies a few steps ahead of the negative trends. And, above all, we need a constant awareness that the 'other' is not really different from the 'self'”. --Rajni Bakshi

Abstract

Universities' 'internationalisation' has recently become a buzzword in many countries. With the advancement of globalisation, the mobility of students and academic staff at universities has increased dramatically over the last few decades. As a result, more universities are attempting to internationalise their institutions. While some universities focus on internationalising their curricula to meet the needs of a globalised society, others emphasise the formation of new collaboration agreements with foreign universities in order to raise their profiles even further. These changes have elevated universities to the forefront of global knowledge competition, necessitating the development of solid international strategies in order to thrive.

In this regard, the United Kingdom has most likely been one of the most proactive countries. This research will look into the underlying concepts of internationalisation in UK universities. The research aims to comprehend internationalisation of higher education as a phenomenon and to create a body of knowledge in this field, particularly in the context of the United Kingdom. It is also critical to define and assess activities, implementation scope, intent, effectiveness, and institutional support. This research will also attempt to explain why higher education institutions in the United Kingdom are pursuing internationalisation what are the strategies, issues and challenges faced by the

universities to advance internationalisation. Various internationalisation concepts, theories, and models were examined, and Kinght's cyclical model served as an analytical lens to comprehend various aspects and the process of internationalisation for this study.

The study is based on subject-specific questions that have previously received insufficient attention and is designed from the start to be exploratory, inductive, and action-oriented. As a result, it was necessary to scope the field of study and engage with and understand, at a granular level, the perceptions and experiences of internationalisation strategies in UK universities from the perspective of staff.

Based on universities in the UK, the study used an interpretive paradigm that included concept analysis and a qualitative approach. The data for the study was gathered via semi-structured face-to-face in-depth interviews conducted by telephone participants representing 13 higher education institutions.

The study's outcome was determined through using a thematic analysis approach, which enabled the identification of emergent and dominant themes as a focal point for the study's interpretation. The thesis went into great length into the internationalisation setting in the United Kingdom.

The analysis found a wide range of definitions and approaches, demonstrating not only the concept's versatility but also the degree of disagreement among authors. Internationalisation as a strategy, according to the study, is the sum of global actions carried out to manage higher education. Internationalisation is recognised

by universities as a viable source of capacity building and revenue generation coupled with boosting rankings on the league table.

As a result, when budgetary commitment is low, there is a stronger reliance on the economic rationale for internationalisation as a source of financial-distress relief, according to subsequent investigation. This study investigated the internal impediments that exist to stifle or halt the process of internationalisation.

The internationalisation agenda has a number of internal obstacles that have been highlighted. Resources, management support, staff engagement, supporting strategies, quality assurance, curricular content, bureaucratic procedures, staff and student mobility, and communication are all examples of these.

These challenges will have varying degrees of impact on various institutions, and ideas for dealing with and coping with them have been proposed. This study has not only made a direct contribution to higher education, but it has also contributed to knowledge by utilising sequential primary research process and closing the obvious knowledge gap associated with the identification of limitations to internationalisation of higher education in the United Kingdom. Finally, this thesis provides a deeper understanding of how internationalisation operations are carried out, as well as the challenges encountered, and solutions devised to overcome them.

The importance of this study is critical for the larger picture of higher education, where capitalistic influences can reshape how universities recruit and implement their goals and strategies. If higher education becomes another capital-profit-driven industry, the development of skilled workers, cultural understanding, and societal development may suffer. The study concluded that a successful education system is the foundation of a great nation because it is where they can develop cultural understanding and national citizenship.

This research is relevant to a broad community: it is anticipated that it will have a significant impact on various internal and external stakeholders: It will also help to identify gaps and missing elements in the internationalisation process, as well as related methods and approaches implemented by UK higher education.

Furthermore, it will help to develop more effective and informed internationalisation strategies and processes at the HE institutional level, as well as allow HIE to gain a better understanding of internationalisation approaches. As a result, it should help to achieve higher levels of internationalisation at both the institutional and national levels.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CSR- Corporate Social Responsibility

ERASMUS- European Community Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students.

GATS - General Agreement on Trade and Services

HE -Higher Education

HEI- Higher Education Institution

IHE -Institution of Higher Education

IAU - International Association of Universities

IMPDET - (International Multidisciplinary PhD Studies in Educational Technology

IAU -International Universities Association

MOU- Memorandum of Understanding

OECD - Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development

PMI -The Prime Ministers Initiative for International Education

TNE- Transnational Education

UKIERI - UK India Education Research Initiative

WTO - World Trade Organization

WWII - World War

Chapter 1- Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This thesis investigates the issue of internationalisation in UK universities. In the last 20 years, one of the most researched topics has been the internationalisation of higher education (Yang,2002; Bartell,2003; Teichler, 2004; Stensaker, 2008). Education internationalisation is one of many ways that a country can respond to globalisation's challenges.

Higher education has long been emphasised by international organisations as critical to global development. The need of internationalising higher education was emphasised during the UNESCO World Conference on Higher Education (WCHE) in Paris (1998) to address and minimise inequities between developed and developing countries. This was primarily accomplished through the exchange of technical and theoretical knowledge, which necessitates the formation of consortiums and networks to encourage and allow partners to collaborate and expand interculturally. As a result, education is a tool for a country's social and economic development (WCHE,1998).

This research will shed light on the issues in the internationalisation of the higher education sector in the UK based on information provided by relevant personnel from the international departments of UK universities, whose perceptions and experiences are likely to have a positive and long-term impact in addressing the issues of internationalisation of higher education.

This chapter establishes the remit for the study by presenting the context, rationale, goals, objectives, and methodology used, as well as the thesis structure.

1.2 Background- research context, gap, and rationale

In the last 20 years, and as mentioned above, one of the most researched topics has been the internationalisation of higher education (Yang,2002; Bartell,2003; Teichler,2004; Stensaker,2008). Internationalisation in Higher Education is defined as a set of policies and programmes put in place by universities and governments in response to globalisation (Altbach,2012;2009).

Internationalisation is a critical component in the higher education sector, which is experiencing the most powerful and concrete progressive development in the history of the UK's higher education sector (Harman, 2002; Kehm, 2007).

Despite the fact that higher education internationalisation appears to be a recent phenomenon, it has been recognised as a trend among developed-country universities since the 1980s (Bennell,2003). The ways in which universities internationalise differ, which can be ascribed in part to the various meanings and perspectives of internationalisation (Fielden,2008). Jane Knight's definition of internationalisation, on the other hand, is the most widely used.

“the process of integrating an international/intercultural dimension into the teaching, research and services functions of the institution, to strengthen international education” (Knight J. , Internationalization: management strategies and issues, 1993).

Internationalisation is usually considered to involve raising the number of international students (Trahar, 2005), but as the definitions above illustrate, it is a significantly more complex topic that encompasses many facets of a university's operations. In chapter 2 of this thesis, these are discussed in greater depth.

The government, on the other hand, is convinced that internationalisation is crucial, and Bill Rammell MP, the then-Higher Education Minister, indicated in a speech in May 2008 that internationalisation was a "big success" for UK universities (Gill,2008). This significance has been reaffirmed by a series of initiatives put in place to aid in the process. Rt. Hon. Tony Blair, the first Prime Minister's initiative, launched in 1999 under the title "Drive to attract overseas students to the UK," focused heavily on student numbers and income.

However, there has been a significant deviation from a focus on earnings and statistics. According to recent opinion, internationalisation affects almost every individual section or department within a university, further than the International Office and student enrolment (UK, 2008a). In March 2019, a second Prime Minister's initiative, titled International Education Strategy: Global Potential, Global Growth, stated a much wider perspective and strategy for internationalisation. This strategy outlined two key objectives to be met by 2030:

- to double annual education exports to £35 billion; and
- to double the number of international students studying in the UK to 600,000 per year.

The strategic document addresses collaborations, collective projects/courses, joint degrees, staff/student exchanges, and changes to visa and immigration rules. Clearly demonstrating a much broader understanding of internationalisation This strategy also addresses other initiatives such as:

- The International Education Champion: This effort will focus on growing education exports, diversifying the international student recruitment base, and overcoming market access restrictions such as mutual recognition of online and blended (offline and online) education supply.
- Free Trade: Following the UK's exit from the EU, the government will be able to set its own trading agenda with its important international partners. In creating international collaborations, the International Education Strategy emphasises the necessity of global mobility and exchange. Around the world, cultural exchange serves to develop crucial business, political, and diplomatic connections.

The main issue is that global demand for higher education is expected to outstrip UK demand, raising concerns about the UK's ability to compete (Universities, UK,2020).

The United Kingdom has a competitive edge due to a number of factors, including:

- A global reputation for education and research, as well as the profile of its elite global higher education brands

- Historical commercial and political ties
- The popularity of English language study and culture; and Post-study employment opportunities

(Universities UK, 2020)

As the number of international students declines, some UK universities face significant financial risk. Any decrease in international student recruitment could have a significant financial impact at a time when income from domestic fee-paying students is uncertain due to the removal of the fee cap and the Brexit vote (Curtis,2019). According to the British Council's most recent estimates for international student recruitment through 2020, the rate of growth has slowed dramatically, with the annual rate falling to 1.4 percent on average each year (British Council, 2014, p. 5). This is a significant decrease from the past average annual growth rate of 5% for the previous 20 years, beginning in 1990. British Council (2014, p. 5) Internationalisation is now "mainstreamed and entrenched in institutional strategic objectives," rather than an afterthought to HEI activities (Egron-Polak, 2011).

Higher education internationalisation is defined as a range of programs and policies implemented by academic institutions and governments in response to globalisation, which vary according to context (Altbach, 2009). According to Zeleza (2012), perceptions on internationalisation differ greatly in terms of the factors driving it, the activities that comprise it, the capabilities it promotes, the

values it creates, the processes that sustain it, the respective roles of relevant stakeholders within and outside universities, and its impacts on the core components of the higher-education organisation.

Moreover, Knight (2015), noted that the purpose of internationalisation is not to become well-known, but to use the integration of multinational, cross- cultural, or global dimensions into educational goals, functions, and delivery as a part of enhancing or achieving the institution's academic objectives. As a result, as Rosenblit (2015), points out, internationalising higher education necessitates a fundamental shift in how higher-education systems and individual higher-education institutions operate.

The common thread, however, is that internationalisation is broadly defined and applied; it is not limited to a single set of international activities, nor is it motivated by a single rationale (Wit,2002; Sehoole,2009; Knight,2008; Zeleza, 2012). As a result, the inclusion of the international perspective in higher education practices accurately reflects the fact and nature of internationalisation. Furthermore, because of the tremendous diversity in functions, quality, and financial support, among other things, higher education operates in a variety of environments, making generalisation difficult. Enders (2004), also claims that higher education, as an organisation, has values, culture, and belief systems; thus, institutions draw attention to what happens when the many variables are

integrated of internationalisation collide with the multidimensional nature of higher education sector.

This research aims at the organisational understanding, contextualisation, barriers, and impact of higher education internationalisation in the context of UK universities.

Table : 1.1 Research Gap in UK higher Education

Identifying the research gap		Are there any motivation mentioned in the model	Are there detailed motivation mentioned for cross border higher education	Are there general steps of internationalisation	Are there any details regard strategic models regard cross border higher education	Are there any general guideline regard decision making on cross border HE	Are there any details regard decision making on choosing entry strategies (i.e. types of cross-border HE	Are there any general guidelines regard implementation	Are there any detailed analysis indicated regarding implantation for each type of cross border HE	Are there any models / frameworks / suggestions provided regarding motivation, decision making and implementation based upon the type of university
✓ - Yes, it is included Gap in the topic										
Internationalisation (general guidelines)	Internationalisation Cycle	✓	Focused Research Gap	✓		✓		✓		Focused Research Gap
	NUFFIC Model	✓		✓		✓		✓		
	Internationalisation Cube	✓		✓			✓			
	The Fractal Process mode	✓		✓		✓				
	Davies' model			✓		✓		✓		
	Neave's Model	✓				✓		✓		
	Good Practice Model					✓	✓		✓	
Cross border/ HE (general model)	Contractual model					✓		✓		
	Detailed models & suggestions on cross border								✓ Focused Research Gap ✓ Focused Research Gap	
	3 models regard branch campus									
	Overseas campus analysis (by Altbach)	✓								

Higher education internationalisation is a globally recognised and significant phenomenon because it has improved the successful achievement of higher education objectives (de Wit, 2002). Deardorff and Van Gaalen (2012), on the other hand, argue that the success of internationalisation should be measured by its contribution to the achievement of an institution's mission and core goals. Even though universities are international in nature (Altbach & Teichler, 2001), and no

university can avoid internationalisation of higher education (Rumbley, Altbach, & Reisberg, 2012), this may give a false impression of commitment to internationalisation and understanding of the status and nature of internationalisation activities.

Definitions, activities, and strategies are constantly being updated and adopted differently among and within institutions (Cross, Mhlanga & Ojo, 2011; de Wit, 2011; Rumbley, Altbach & Reisberg, 2012). Scholars do not agree on the definition of internationalisation, according to Zeleza (2012), because of the diversity and complexity of its rationales, activities, stakeholders, and providers at the national, sectoral, and institutional levels. Furthermore, according to Warwick (2014), there is a problem of a lack of shared understanding of the true meaning of internationalisation, as well as a challenge in implementing internationalisation in complex professional organisations; as well as a lack of managerial skills, knowledge, and experience in international business. As a result, differences in definitions and understanding of internationalisation reflect disagreement on the meaning of internationalisation rather than scholarly carping.

This misunderstanding reflects a situation in which internationalisation is interpreted and used in a variety of ways and contexts (Knight, 2008; Rumbley, Altbach, & Reisberg, 2012; Zeleza, 2012); this presents a challenge in terms of developing a common understanding and conceptual understanding that can provide clarity on meaning, while also providing some principles to guide policy

and practice. As a result, leaders in higher education must be prepared to track and understand the broadest global trends in higher education, as well as the internationalisation of higher education; at the same time, leaders in higher education must be prepared to attend effectively to the unique needs and aspirations of their particular institution. The key to university internationalisation, according to Chan and Dimmock (2008) and Curtis (2013), is that there is no "one-size-fits-all" method for putting an internationalisation strategy into action. Nor should there be. This demonstrates the complexity of internationalisation and the potential need for certain competencies, knowledge, attitudes, skills, and understanding of international higher education and international education at the global level.

To comprehend the research gap in higher education internationalisation outlined above, it is necessary to recognise that internationalisation's success should be measured by its impact on an institution's mission and core goals.

As a result, Hudzik and Stohl (2009) argue that internationalisation activities should be carried out in accordance with institutions' overall missions and goals. According to Cross, Mhlanga, and Ojo (2011), there is growing agreement in many countries about the need for universities to internationalise; however, there is little agreement about what internationalisation entails and which strategies are most effective for implementing it in various contexts. As a result, while the concept of internationalisation is widely accepted, the current fundamental issue

for leaders, researchers, and practitioners is how to deal with the wide range of terms and definitions associated with internationalisation in higher education de Wit (2002) and Knight (2008).

Despite the fact that universities are international in nature, no university can avoid internationalising higher education (Altbach,2012). As a result, Stohl (2009), argues that internationalisation activities should be carried out in accordance with institutions' overall missions and goals. The gap must be filled!

According to Cross (2009), many countries are increasingly agreeing on the importance of internationalisation for universities; however, there is limited consensus on what internationalisation entails and which tactics are most effective for implementing it in various circumstances. As a result, while the concept of internationalisation is popular, the present fundamental difficulty for leaders, academics, and practitioners in higher education is how to deal with the range of terminologies and definitions associated with internationalisation (Wit, 2002; Knight, 2008).

Furthermore, a review of the literature revealed that there is little research in internationalisation from a UK perspective. The majority of the studies are comparative, and this research looks at universities from all four countries in the United Kingdom. Moreover, most internationalisation studies are conducted from a student perspective or are related to student recruitment or curriculum internationalisation and take a quantitative approach. This study examines

internationalisation from the perspective of staff and employs a qualitative approach to comprehend internationalisation issues and challenges.

Another gap is a lack of shared understanding, which shows that, despite becoming a mainstream phenomenon in higher education, internationalisation is still misinterpreted or inadequately defined and described among and by experts.

According to Knight (2008), the term means different things to different people and is thus used in a variety of contexts. According to Wit (2002), as globalisation gains traction, there is a tendency to employing it in the most appropriate context.

Authors define internationalisation based on their personal experiences; there are as many definitions of internationalisation as there are scholars in study.

However, despite efforts by various authors to define and describe internationalisation of higher education (Altbach,2009;Wit,2002;

Deardorff,2012;Jiang,2008;Knight,2004;2015;Söderqvist,2002;Yang,2002),

most definitions are only deeply embedded in an expertly worded demonstration, and thus internationalisation remains a misunderstood concept. These definitions are expanded on in chapter 2.

1.3 Geographical and global context of the study

The research is based in the United Kingdom and focuses on higher education institutions in England, Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Wales. All these regions were represented in the interviews that were conducted, as will be addressed in chapter 4. The literature review, on the other hand, has a broader, more global

perspective in terms of the sources of material employed, but these are explicitly indicated within the thesis and have been adapted to the UK context where appropriate.

OECD data for 2020/21 shows that the UK was the third most popular destination in the world for international students. It is notable that OECD data for the preceding year showed the United States of America in third position. This is a direct illustration of the impact of the pandemic which caused the United States to suspend international student recruitment and curtail their existing arrangements.

Table :1.2 International student mobility indicator

Source: OECD (2021)

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International faculty and students contribute significantly to the academic community in the United Kingdom, and global collaborations in research and education expand our influence and impact. The UK government has acknowledged the importance of internationalisation in its International Education Strategy and International Research and Innovation Strategy, which is a positive sign, especially given the challenges posed by BREXIT. It is now more important than ever for the sector to do what it does best: be open to the rest of the world and distinct in terms of internationalisation.

During the 2017–18 academic year, 139 UK universities provided Transnational Education (TNE) to 693,695 students from 225 countries and territories around the world. The United Kingdom is a global leader in this industry, with 1.5 times as many international students studying for a UK degree as there are overseas students studying in the UK. Collaborative delivery was the most common type of TNE. (HESA,2019).

In terms of research, the United Kingdom punches above its weight; despite accounting for only 0.9 percent of the global total, it produced 15.2 percent of the world's most highly cited articles in 2018. The global partnerships and collaborations of UK higher education institutions are critical to the quality and impact of their theoretical foundation. In 2018, the proportion of international co-authored publications in the UK reached 55.2 percent, and the proportion of UK research funding from overseas sources continued to rise. In 2017–18,

international and/or EU sources accounted for 23% of total UK research funding (UKVI,2018).

Table:1.3 Data on UK research funding

HIGHLIGHTS

Source: UKVI, (2018)

1.4 Impact of Covid -19 on Higher Education

The Corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic, which began in Wuhan, China and quickly spread to the rest of the world, claimed many lives. The global Covid-

19 pandemic impacted higher education institutions, as it did all aspects of life. Because of the pandemic, most countries' higher education institutions were temporarily closed. More than 90 percent of the global student population was affected by nationwide school closures (UNESCO, 2020). The pandemic had a greater impact on lower-middle and low-income countries. Only a few countries claimed that the pandemic had had no effect. As a result, the impact on global higher education was unprecedented since World War II (Bassett, 2020).

Table :1.4 Impact on teaching and learning by region

	Not affected	Classroom teaching replaced by distance teaching and learning	Teaching suspended but the institutions is developing solutions	Teaching cancelled
Africa	3 %	29 %	43 %	24 %
Americas	3 %	72 %	22 %	3 %
Asia & Pacific	1 %	60 %	36 %	3 %
Europe	Almost zero	85 %	12 %	3 %

Source :(IAU – COVID-19 Global Impact Survey, 202)

Many researchers are currently interested in the effects of Covid-19 on higher education (Altbach & de Wit, 2020a,b; Amemado, 2020; Amoah & Mok, 2020; Basset, 2020; Blanco & de Wit, 2020; Brandenburg, 2020). Furthermore, internationalisation in higher education has always been a concern for universities. Internationalisation is still a top priority in many countries' higher education institutions. The unexpected closure of higher education institutions around the world, as well as the adoption of distance education, caught nations

off guard. While some countries attempted to solve the problem through distance education, others were unable to manage the crisis due to socioeconomic and technological infrastructure issues. Thus, as the pandemic's economic impact was felt in both developed and developing countries, it also resulted in an increase in existing inequalities in a variety of fields.

The most important point to emerge from the Covid-19 outbreak is the long-term viability of internationalisation in higher education. In this context, the invisible section of the internationalisation iceberg is growing larger. Some experts in international higher education believe that inequality will worsen in the post-pandemic era. This is why it is critical to understand the implications of internationalising higher education in this process (Amoah & Mok, 2020).

The pandemic has also occurred during a period of strained global relations. Taking United Kingdom as an example, recent diplomatic relations between China and some countries have exacerbated the pandemic's impact. International students have long been a major source of income for British universities; more than half of the student population is international, with Chinese and Indian students accounting for a sizable proportion (Marginson, 2020; Welch, 2020). The sudden drop in international students as a result of border control has impacted the finances and governance of these universities (Mok, 2021), which will have a long-term impact on the development of higher education in the

region. Similar developments are taking place in USA, Asia and other European countries.

With the inclusion of remote and open education models, the higher education industry has become more competitive (Cunha et al., 2020). Prior to the current COVID-19 pandemic, many universities were anticipating income reductions due to factors such as Brexit, a changing demography with fewer students of university age, and higher competitiveness for students due to an increase in the number of university places available. Any unexpected drop in international student numbers would put many universities' finances in jeopardy (Marginson, 2017). In light of the pandemic, student recruitment and retention have become even more important in ensuring the traditional university model's long-term sustainability, and it is critical that student satisfaction rates remain high in order for a university to compete. The lessons learned by institutions and student experiences with remote delivery during the pandemic will shape students' future expectations of learning, teaching, and assessments, highlighting the importance of universities focusing on their unique selling points in a competitive market.

The pandemic has posed significant challenges in educational activities on a daily basis. The immediate impact has been lockdowns and the forced closure of schools, colleges, and universities over the last year (Watermeyer , 2020). However, this has not resulted in a halt to learning, teaching, and assessment; rather, online contingency plans have been developed to continue teaching and

assessment via a digital interface so that students can continue with their studies (Rapanta et al., 2020). Emergency Remote Education (ERE) refers to educational institutions' emergency response during crises (pandemics or conflict) to shift teaching and assessments online (Shin and Hickey, 2020). ERE can entail adapting content that was previously taught face-to-face as blended learning or fully distanced learning (Shin and Hickey, 2020).

Many universities had already implemented practices to make their education delivery more flexible and accessible in order to meet the needs of their students. While blended learning incorporates some aspects of online course delivery, other approaches include the hybrid model, which combines online course delivery with face-to-face sessions; however, all students must attend both modalities (Meydanlioglu and Arikan, 2014). Face-to-face and online learning are also combined in the Hyflex model. However, each session and learning activity is available in person, synchronously online, and asynchronously online, allowing students to choose how they want to participate (Beatty 2019, p.22). Although the Hyflex model provides more student choice, it may lead to greater disparities in student experiences and disrupt the experience of feeling part of a cohort, for example, if one student wants to work remotely while the rest of the class chooses to work on campus.

According to the literature reviewed in Farnell et al. (2021), COVID-19 has unavoidably introduced new risks and challenges that affect student access, study

process, and retention, particularly for students from underrepresented, vulnerable, and disadvantaged groups. Even for students who continue to study abroad, recent research on student learning experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic has identified the following challenges:

- Problems with researching conditions (i.e., access to a quiet place to study, equipment, reliable internet connection and course study materials, and confidence in using online platforms)
- Challenges with funding (for example, loss of employment/income, difficulty meeting living expenses, and difficulties receiving scholarships)
- Well-being issues (such as a lack of supportive social networks and prominent feelings of frustration, anxiety, and boredom with academic activities) (Farnell, et al., 2021, see also Doolan et al., 2021; Aristovnik et al., 2020; Amoah and Mok, 2020).

The preceding literature also confirms that students who face such challenges will consistently face difficulties in gaining access to higher education. National-level surveys, such as those conducted in the United Kingdom, show that students who are lonely or dissatisfied with their learning environment are more likely to drop out (Marinoni and Jensen, 2020). Similarly, Amoah and Mok reported in their study of the well-being of international students in 26 countries/regions that the majority of their respondents felt lonely and anxious while studying abroad. Many of these students also received insufficient support from their host

institutions in high-risk and uncertain environments, potentially prompting them to return home (Amoah and Mok, 2020; Doolan et al., 2020). In the context of a highly divided world, there is a strong call to address the growing concerns about increased inequalities in access and participation in international education in order to improve learning experiences for all.

Furthermore, the shift to online learning is likely to exacerbate inequalities between countries with varying levels of educational technology advancement. Virtual student mobility is increasingly being used to support communication during the pandemic, thanks to advances in information and communication technology. For example, 33 universities worldwide signed a joint statement to support student mobility during the pandemic, and more than 60% of HEIs worldwide increased their virtual mobility during the pandemic (UNESCO and HESA, 2021). When compared to in-person events and fairs, virtual student mobility can lower the transportation cost of international travel, making it more affordable for students with lower socioeconomic status. Students who are unable to travel internationally for various reasons, such as physical disability, can use virtual student mobility. However, equity concerns about access to such events persist because they continue to necessitate certain infrastructure support. Virtual student mobility is hampered by the following factors:

- Infrastructure constraints
- Concerns about the program's quality and, if applicable, the certificate

- Administrative measures differ between home and host institutions.
- Language differences
- Information availability

The digital divide between developed and developing countries may influence access to such programmes, worsening the educational divide between rich and poor. Some students and employers regard virtual student mobility as inferior to physical mobility, calling into question the viability of such programmes after the crisis. Given the foregoing, governments around the world must address the issues of higher education access and implement appropriate policies/measures to promote diversity in higher education, especially when regimes are eager to embrace innovation and technology.

Governments and institutions, in collaboration with various stakeholders in business and society, should group together to co-produce better learning opportunities in order to realise the UN Education for All agenda.

Moving forward, we must ensure that higher education is well-equipped to adapt to changing circumstances and future restrictions on student access to university campuses. It is critical to understand any barriers students encountered during this time period so that HEI can be more inclusive and meet student needs. In response to the pandemic, most institutions moved all teaching online; thus, implementing the most appropriate teaching model (all on campus, hybrid, or hyflex, all distance learning) is critical not only to inform future teaching practise but also

to ensure universities retain student numbers and remain financially sustainable in a competitive market.

Figure :1.1 COVID-19 affected teaching and learning

Source : (IAU – COVID-19 Global Impact Survey, 2022)

1.5 Research aims, questions and objectives

The aim of the study is to investigate the issue of internationalisation in UK higher education universities.

The study's purpose is thus to comprehend internationalisation of higher education as a phenomenon and to develop a body of knowledge in this area of higher education, particularly in the context of the United Kingdom. It is also critical to define and assess the activities, scope of implementation, intent, effectiveness, and institutional support.

This study investigates the motivation, strategies, and challenges associated with internationalisation in higher education. Financial, quality, and competition are the prominent perceptions that drive the concept of internationalisation. The most important achievement has been financial success, as profits can be used to open international doors and expand further. A recruitment strategy can be used to boost university rankings, promote competitiveness, and improve educational and academic quality. The findings of this study will ultimately assist institutions in better understanding their documented or unrecorded internationalisation methods, thereby improving the quality of teaching, learning, and student and university support services.

The general background mentioned above, combined with the research motivation and personal interest, identified the internationalisation subject area as one worthy of investigation. As a result of this focus, the three research questions listed below were developed:

- What is understood by the term ‘internationalisation’ in the context of higher education?
- What strategies have institutions implemented to advance the internationalisation agenda?
- What challenges have universities encountered in their drive to advance the internationalisation agenda?

There are three connected research objectives to ensure a broad exploration and investigation into the subject, allowing these research questions to be as fully answered as possible. The three objectives are as follows:

- To critically explore the concept of internationalisation in higher education.
- To critically assess the strategies used by the UK universities to advance internationalisation.
- To critically appraise the challenges faced by the universities in implementing strategies in internationalisation.

1.6 Research methodology

As mentioned earlier, the research is being carried out in the United Kingdom, with a focus on universities in England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland.

In-depth interviews with relevant persons (international department/teaching staff) from UK universities will be used to develop a qualitative approach. This research intends to investigate significant issues in higher education internationalisation by examining the perspectives of relevant individuals who are directly involved in the process of internationalisation. As these are the key people in charge of developing the strategies, this will provide a valuable data set.

A caveat about the sample size is in order here. A variety of factors hampered data collection in part. These included restrictions on access to participants due to Covid-19 and a relatively low number of universities (thirteen), despite sending

out seventy invitations to potential university participants with subsequent follow-ups via a variety of communications. Furthermore, the geographical scope of the study across the four nations of the United Kingdom has resulted in a balanced consideration that considers the various cultures and demographics that exist in those locations. In summary, the study has resulted in a local focus on the international agenda.

Nevertheless, despite the small sample size, this study has identified a new understanding of the challenges and thus contributes to larger-scale studies with a larger sample size. As a result, the study collects qualitative data; more information about this thesis' methodology is provided in chapter three.

In contrast, the literature review will provide a more global perspective in terms of the sources of material used, but they will be clearly noted where they are used in the thesis and have been applied to the UK context where appropriate. 1.7.

1.7 Organisation of the study

The following structure is used to present the information of internationalisation of higher education in the United Kingdom.

Chapter One is the study's introduction, addressing the advancements that urged this study and elaborating on current challenges to help readers understand the study's justification and motivation. All of the research objectives, questions, and goals are explained. The chapter's final section suggests with an overview of the study structure.

Chapter Two is a review of the literature, in which the current debates and assertions about internationalisation of higher education are presented. This chapter describes the origins of international higher education in relation to internationalisation, both globally and in the context of the United Kingdom. Clarity of internationalisation is discussed to comprehend various authors' and sources' definitions of internationalisation. The rationales, approaches, and strategies for internationalising higher education are further discussed in relation to development and evolution experience.

The third chapter discusses research design and methodological considerations related to research processes, methodology suitability, and study worthiness. In part, it introduces concept analysis as a methodology. This is covered in greater detail in Chapter Four. The chapter concludes with a thorough explanation and justification of all research design and methodology decisions.

Chapter Four presents the empirical findings from the interviews conducted subsequently broken down into various themes for interpretation of data.

Chapter Five represents the analysis of the findings followed by extended discussion using the theoretical lenses presented in chapter two.

Chapter Six summarises the findings of Chapter Five and then makes recommendations for further internationalisation improvement. Furthermore, it captures the originality of the research, the limitations of the study, and the possibilities for future research.

1.8 Conclusion

During the literature review process, it became obvious that there is a lack of study on the internationalisation of higher education institutions in the United Kingdom. This research is being carried out based on its predicted contribution to the topic of higher education internationalisation, as well as academic knowledge and research. Not only will this widen the existing literature and analytical tools, but it will also recommend additional research to push the boundaries of understanding even further.

Based on the phenomenon's popularity and significance, the findings and observations are expected to be useful for higher education research, policymakers, and practitioners, even though the study was conducted with a small sample in a large university community, because they are based not only on empirical and theoretical reflections and findings, but also on findings from previous studies.

The majority of prior research on higher education internationalisation have used quantitative or mixed approaches. This study, on the other hand, employs a qualitative method, which is discussed in further depth in chapter 3 of this thesis.

As a result, it has the potential to provide useful insights into the higher education sector, universities, by detailing how internationalisation could be perceived, defined, and deployed to augment higher education objectives. The revealed characteristics of internationalisation could be used to develop definitions of

higher education internationalisation. The research will also shed light on the rationale, barriers, and leadership positioning in relation to the success of internationalisation. As a result, higher education institutions will comprehend internationalisation and in consequence the strategies and policies that promote its implementation in the context of UK universities.

As a result, the first chapter functions as a preamble to the thesis. Its goal was to emphasise and rationalise the study's significance. This chapter argues for the inclusion of an international dimension in institutional higher-education operations while also describing the reality and essence of internationalisation.

Chapter 2 – Literature review

2.1 Introduction

The current literature on internationalisation in higher education is discussed in this chapter. The analysis focuses on the global and domestic development of higher education internationalisation, as well as exploring, delineating, and examining some conceptual structures related to internationalisation rationales and strategies. Finally, the gaps in the related literature are identified, as the foundation for this study.

2.2 Concept of internationalisation in higher education

In the field of education, internationalisation is not a new term or concept. It is frequently discussed in terms of how it was introduced and developed in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries (Healey, 2008). Internationalisation is becoming increasingly important as a strategy for higher education institutions. The effects of globalisation are being felt all over the world. Internationalisation has become an agenda of increasing strategic relevance for institutions of higher education (HE) worldwide because of the influences of globalisation (Wagner,2004).

Internationalisation research can be classified as part of the significant ideological shifts in higher education that support the development of a new type of academic culture: competitive, neoliberal, consumerist, and managerial. (Rizvi, 2006; Pol, 2012). Internationalisation techniques, on the other hand, are needed to encourage

diversity of cultures, engaged, critical, and collaborative research and teaching academic orientations (Leask, 2013; Teekens, 2007). As a result, for institutions, instructors, and students, it is both a strongly ideological and a productive subject of engagement (Cai, 2004).

HE foundations are rapidly changing as a result of expanding international and financial goals, in order to 'go global' (Robson,2011). The internationalisation of higher education has been defined as "the process of incorporating a universal, intercultural, or global measurement into the reason, capabilities, or delivery of postsecondary education" (Knight, 2003). However, the difficulty in developing an internationalisation definition is in applying it collectively to different cultures, perspectives, and educational systems (Knight J. , Concepts, rationales, and interpretive frameworks in the internationalization of higher education, 2012).

According to Altbach (2009), internationalisation is a strategy that enables societies and institutions to respond to the many demands of globalisation, providing individuals with better education within a globalised world. However, the definitions discussed focus their attention on different aspects, emphasising different points. For example, Altbach (2009), emphasises policies and initiatives to address a global agenda, whereas Yang (2010), examines the process of making university goals internationally compatible.

The WTO General Agreement on Trade and Services (GATS) established four trade modes, which are often cited in relation to the internationalisation of higher education detailed below (World Bank, 2002):

- E-learning programmes, virtual universities, and distant education are instances of cross-border provision of services when consumers remain in the country.
- The second mode represents cross-border consumption, which includes students enrolled in full-time foreign courses and exchange programmes.
- The third mode denotes a provider's presence in another country via branch campuses, twinning partnerships, and university-to-university franchising. This is the approach that the International Multidisciplinary PhD Studies in Educational Technology & Learning Environments (IMPDET) intends to take in order to expand to other countries.
- The fourth mode is the presence of representatives in another country to deliver the service; an example of this mode is the movement of teachers and researchers from one country to another.

Because of the nation's interdependencies, businesses, especially higher education institutions, have taken advantage of expanding their products and services across borders (Callan,2000). Higher education internationalisation in Europe, for example, began with the European Community Action Scheme

for University Student Movement (ERASMUS), a programme that encouraged student mobility between European universities (de Wit, 2015).

In December 2020, the current Prime Minister, Boris Johnson, announced that the UK was pulling out of ERASMUS and would be creating a new scheme called the Turing Scheme (<https://www.turing-scheme.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/Turing-Scheme-Programme-Guide.pdf>).

Creating an international student curriculum should allow indigenous citizens to be creative in addressing a contextual issue (Han,2011). Recognising this fact, the Higher Education Academy of UK universities has developed an evidence-based framework that serves as a national reference point for the higher education sector, allowing institutions to tailor their approach to local circumstances while also benchmarking performance (Welch and Cai, 2010).

Internationalisation is a continuous process defined as the process through which higher education systems' curriculum, research, and service functions become globally compatible and cross-cultural. (Yang, 2002; Knight, 2004).

Higher education internationalisation, according to Söderqvist (2002), is the process of transforming a higher education institution into an international higher education institution by incorporating an international dimension into all aspects of its holistic management in order to improve teaching and learning quality and achieve the desired outcomes.

2.2.1 Emergence and evolution of higher education in the UK

Because of a rapidly changing historical, political, and economic process, internationalisation is becoming increasingly complex and diverse in many ways (Knight, 2008) Higher education's internationalisation is not only becoming more important (Knight, 2004), but it is also taking on new forms and approaches (Egroun-Polak, 2012). Higher education has been internationalising since the Middle Ages and Renaissance periods, when a university was already a fully recognised international institution (Yang, 2002, p.183).

Internationalisation has undergone a series of stages and transformations. According to de Wit (2005), the historical perspective is divided into three periods: internationalisation during the Middle Ages and Renaissance; internationalisation between the 18th century and WWII; and internationalisation from WWII to the Present.

According to de Wit (2005), the majority of publications on today's internationalisation of higher education in Europe refer to the Middle Ages era, which continues until the end of the 15th century, merging into the Renaissance period, which runs from approximately 1400 to 1600. During this period, there was a great deal of student and scholar mobility, Latin was introduced as a common language, and a standardised study programme began to emerge.

One could argue that this period laid the groundwork for current developments in higher education internationalisation. According to Schoole (2009), the modern

characteristics of internationalisation are similar to some activities from this earlier period. This is demonstrated by mobile students as well as the dominance of English as a standard academic language. According to de Wit (2005), the most important aspect of higher education between the 18th and WWII was the export of higher education systems in the form of ideology dissemination from colonial powers to colonies.

During this time period, social, cultural, and political nationalism flourished. During this time, three international aspects of higher education can be identified: 1) higher education system export; 2) research dissemination; and 3) student mobility. However, the period is described as being primarily focused on national higher education (Hammerstein,1996). In the 1990s, the internationalisation of higher education shifted from a traditional focus on mobility to 'internationalisation at home,' which included curriculum internationalisation, the formation of international organisations, and the formation of regional and global university collaborations (Alemu, 2014).

According to a trend of international education expansion at the beginning of the twentieth century, which grew primarily after WWII, both superpowers, the United States and Europe, had clear political reasons for promoting international education exchange and cooperation, which included gaining a better understanding of the rest of the world and maintaining and expanding their sphere and influence (de Wit,2005). According to Wilkins (2013), the

internationalisation strategy in higher education was once primarily concerned with student and staff mobility or international cooperation and collaboration for development purposes, but is now primarily concerned with curriculum relevance, institutional quality, prestige, competitiveness, and innovation potential.

This is due to the rapid rise in economic globalisation, advances in information technology, and the implementation of market-oriented mechanisms, all of which have had a significant impact on the internationalisation of higher education in many countries. The underlying motivation has shifted away from historical, political, cultural, and academic considerations and toward economic considerations. It could be argued that higher education's internationalisation is still shifting from non-profit to for-profit (Knight, 2008).

(See Appendix 6 – UK internationalisation impacts and strategies facts and figures from HESA,2017)

2.2.2 Approaches to defining internationalisation in the context of higher education

Despite the lack of a universal definition of internationalisation, clear evidence of it exists in universities, since the majority of them are international in nature and engage in various international activities, such as student/staff exchanges, research exchanges, MOUs, partnerships, and collaboration. This section

addresses the various definitions of higher education internationalisation produced by scholars.

Knight stated that there was considerable debate over definitions, even when she started writing about the topic over 20 years ago: “Internationalisation means different things to different people, and as a result there is a wide variety of interpretations attributed to this concept” ((Knight, 1997), p5). A brief analysis of the problem of defining ‘internationalisation’ in HE identifies three critical features that might be central to a definition:

1. Process - to convey that internationalisation is ongoing, continuing, and developmental (Knight, 2003).
2. Integration of internationalisation activity to the institution as a whole, with the intention of creating sustainability. (Knight, 2004).
3. Relationship - to the primary functions of teaching and research (Qiang, 2003).

As a result, this short list of features covers a wide range of different aspects and can be used in a variety of contexts (Koutsantoni,2006a). The definition also ensures that it has meaning in different educational markets and countries by not identifying any aspect that is overly precise, as they differ between countries and institutions (Knight, 2003). Furthermore, based on the three critical issues, Elkin (2005), depicted university internationalisation as follows:

“It should aim to create values, beliefs and intellectual insight in which both domestic and international students and staff participate and benefit equally. It should develop global perspectives, international and cultural and ethical sensitivity and useful knowledge, skills and attitudes for the globalised marketplace.” (Elkin, 2005), p. 321.

Therefore, this definition will provide a focus for identifying and further investigating relevant issues, and these will be cross-referenced back to this definition throughout this study at the appropriate points.

There is a substantial body of literature on the definition of internationalisation, its goals, practises, implications, and a variety of other topics. Its meaning varies depending on the field of study. Arum and van de Water (1992) proposed a definition of international education in the early 1990s in order to have a common ground when discussing it; they referred to it as "the multiple activities, programmes, and services that fall within international studies, international educational exchange, and technical cooperation." This is not to say that the term is new, as it has been used for centuries to describe any international activity prior to this date.

According to Knight's (1994) research, there were primarily four different approaches used to describe 'internationalisation' as a concept in the mid-1990s Process approach, Activity approach, Competency approach, and Organisational approach. She did, however, want to add a more specific definition to avoid

confusion: "Internationalisation of higher education is the process of incorporating an international dimension into a university or college's teaching/learning, research, and service functions. An international dimension is defined as "a perspective, activity, or service that introduces or integrates an international/intercultural/global perspective into the major functions of a higher education institution" (Knight, 1994, p. 7).

Some of these definitions, such as Knight's (1994) definition, place an emphasis on the student academic experience in terms of teaching and research as the primary functions of education. Soderqvist (2002, p.29) defined it as "a change process from a national higher education institution to an international higher education institution leading to the inclusion of an international dimension in all aspects of its holistic management in order to improve the quality of teaching and learning and achieve the desired competencies." Since then, scholars have attempted to change the terminologies used to best describe the term and make it generic enough to apply to a variety of educational systems and countries.

De Wit and Hunter's definition is one of the most recent (2015, p.21). They defined internationalisation as "the process of encouraging the integration of multicultural, multilingual, and global dimensions within the educational system in order to instil in learners a sense of global citizenship." This definition used specific terms to emphasise the importance of breaking down cultural and linguistic barriers in order to integrate international students from all over the

world and prepare and motivate them to act as global citizens in an interdependent world. This broad understanding of internationalisation in education corresponds to one of the current research interests, which is to embed the student social experience within the context of the university's international strategy.

This does not imply that previous definitions were incorrect. Rather, it means that they are complementary to one another. It also demonstrates that internationalisation as a concept and practise has broadened over time as a result of the diverse student population, to include students' academic and social experiences. As a result, it was worthwhile to examine different internationalisation agendas at universities and what universities do to be internationalised.

An extensive literature review was attempted to learn about the current state of internationalisation of higher education and related factors. The relevant information published in scholarly papers with a research focus, as well as the references, is listed in the table.

Table 2.1 Summary of definitions of internationalisation in the literature

Scholar	Year	Level of Focus	Approaches	Definition of internationalization
Arum & van de Water	1992	Institutional	Activities	“The multiple activities, programs and services that fall within international studies, international educational exchange and technical cooperation” (p. 202)
Knight	1994	Institutional	Process	“The process of integrating an international and intercultural dimension into the teaching, research and service functions of the institution” (p. 7)
Van der Wende	1997	National	Ethos	“Any systematic effort aimed at making higher education responsive to the requirements and challenges related to the globalisation of society, economy and labour markets” (p. 19)
Söderqvist	2002	Institutional	Changing process	“A change process from a national higher education institution leading to the inclusion of an international dimension in all aspects of its holistic management in order to enhance the quality of teaching and learning and to achieve the desired competencies” (p. 29)
Knight	2003	Sectoral/ National	Process	“The process of integrating an international, intercultural or global

				dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of post-secondary education” (p. 2)
Teichler	2004	National	Changing process	“Internationalisation can best be defined as the totality of substantial changes in the context and inner life of higher education relative to an increasing frequency of border-crossing activities amidst a persistence of national systems” (p. 22)
Elkin, et al	2005	Sectoral/ National	Changing process	"It should aim to create values, beliefs and intellectual insight in which both domestic and international students and staff participate and benefit equally. It should develop global perspectives, international and cultural and ethical sensitivity and useful knowledge, skills and attitudes for the globalised marketplace’”
Hudzik	2014	Institutional	Ethos	“Commitment confirmed through action to infuse international and comparative perspectives throughout the teaching, research and service missions of higher education enterprise...It is an institutional imperative not just a desirable possibility...It not only impacts all of campus life but the institution's external frames of reference, partnerships, and relations” (p. 7).

De Wit & Hunter	2015	Institutional and national	Process	“The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions, and delivery of postsecondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff, and to make a meaningful contribution to society” (p. 3)

Table 2.1 demonstrates how attempted definitions of 'internationalisation' in higher education change over time. These changes could be interpreted as a dynamic shift away from fragmented international activities and toward a process-based approach based on social development and higher education (Knight, 1997, p. 5).

According to de Wit (2010), “agreement was not only not made on its significance, but also on its historical dimensions, concepts, and strategic concepts; its relationship with development in society and with higher education in general, and its status as a study and analysis area” (2002, p. xv). In short, Brandenburg and de Wit(2011), are attempting to summarise the broadest trend within the conceptualisation and evolution of internationalisation.

The main point here, according to Brandenburg and Wit (2011), is that the concept of internationalisation of higher education has evolved from a minimalist, instrumental, and static term to one that encompasses policy-driven processes in

universities. Existing internationalisation concepts are, in general, more similar than diverse (Haan,2014). Overall, the various definitions of the term internationalisation highlight three dominant common features: internationalisation is a process rather than an event; its goal is to integrate people from different backgrounds, cultures, and knowledge systems; and internationalisation is beneficial and necessary in the majority of universities around the world (Murphy, 2007), p. 170.

According to Harman (2005), the majority of definitions are still abstract and distant from actual internationalisation practises: "The current idea of purifying the concept can reflect a wish for theoretical development, but it does not match the "impurity" of daily institutional reality" (p. 256).

As a result, internationalisation definitions, according to de Wit (2013, p.27), should go a step further, showing, for example, the similarities and contrasts between intercultural, international, and global features, or including more basic developments and ideals.

2.2.3 Stakeholders in the internationalisation process of UK's HE.

Higher education in the United Kingdom is widely regarded as a global success story, reflecting a long history of strong academic communities and extensive stakeholder engagement. Despite this, the sector has seen nearly constant change over the last two decades, with the trebling of tuition fees in England and

differential funding regimes in UK devolved administrations regarded as the most significant of these reforms (McCann, Hutchison, and Adair 2019).

Brexit and COVID-19 have increased uncertainty about the security of future income streams. If demand from EU students falls, competition to recruit UK home students is likely to increase in the post-Brexit environment. The post-Brexit scenario is especially difficult in Scotland and Northern Ireland, where the devolved administrations currently pay the undergraduate fees of EU nationals studying there.

While the primary functions of universities are teaching, research, and knowledge transfer, the modern university is also expected to contribute to regional development, which Jongbloed, Enders, and Salerno (2008) refer to as their 'third mission' (312). The extent to which the "third mission" is integrated into daily academic routines and practices at all levels varies because universities and academics tend to prioritise their established missions of teaching and research (Fonseca 2018). In contrast to teaching and research, there is frequently a lack of a clear overarching strategy for the third mission, providing few incentives for academics to participate. Instead, the dominant discourse is centred on generating marketable outputs in accordance with NPM. The importance of participating in the third mission is frequently understated among academics who prioritise other activities.

Because of the wide range of activities in which UK universities are involved, as well as the public nature of some of their funding, which entails public responsibility, the range of stakeholders is diverse, both in terms of geography, interest, and whether the relationship is formal or informal, direct or indirect. For example, as funding constraints have increased, most universities aim to attract high-fee-paying international students at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels, while also supporting a localism agenda; thus, the community of stakeholders in the field of student recruitment can be local, national, and international. Furthermore, much of the scientific community's interaction is borderless, and academics have their own informal networks of contacts in their discipline that are often based in institutions all over the world.

While identifying the full list of stakeholders for the Higher Education sector can be difficult (Alves, Mainardes, and Raposo 2010), there appears to be some agreement that the key stakeholders of UK universities include; registered and prospective students, alumni, the scientific community, central government, devolved administrations, local government and its various departments including town planning, academic and support staff, the Office for Students, and the Office for Students and Scholars. Table 1 provides a list of sector stakeholders as well as an overview of the various interdependencies between stakeholders, highlighting how different stakeholders are interdependent. According to Wolfe and Putler (2002), there is often significant heterogeneity in the views, roles, and

influence of the various stakeholders, necessitating different approaches by the university in their stakeholder interaction. Furthermore, each university is expected to have its own set of stakeholders based on its underlying strengths and weaknesses, teaching programmes, research specialisations, and recruitment markets (Jongbloed, Enders, and Salerno (2008), Alves, Mainardes, and Raposo (2010)).

According to Frooman (1999), each stakeholder employs a unique strategy to influence decisions, either by influencing the resources themselves or the outcomes produced by such resources, and universities must recognise such influence and act appropriately to manage the outcomes. The influence that a stakeholder has on a university may wax and wane over time (Alves, Mainardes, and Raposo 2010), necessitating a regular review of operations and recalibration of the relative importance of each stakeholder in order to adopt strategies to manage that relationship and ensure the institution's long-term health (Massen 2000; Benneworth and Jongbloed 2010; Falqueto et al. 2020).

Table 2.2. **Stakeholders and stakeholder interdependency in the higher education sector.**

Stakeholder	Interdependency
Panel A: internal stakeholders	
Academic Staff	UK and devolved government re student numbers and fee levels, all categories of students, alumni, USS, UCU, UKRI (UK Research and Innovation), charity research funders, commerce.
Support Staff	All categories of students, alumni; local pension provider; campus unions.
Undergraduate (UG) Home students	UK and devolved governments re student numbers, fee levels, student loans, visa requirements and UK border agency rules; overseas governments and recruitment agencies; academic and support staff; Office for Students; NUS (National Union for Students), NHS (National Health Service) and general health and social care; student bed providers; charity research foundations; local business; local residents.
Undergraduate (UG) International students	
Postgraduate Taught (PGT) Home students	
Postgraduate Taught (PGT) International students	
Postgraduate Research (PGR) Home students	
Postgraduate Research (PGR) International students	
Panel B: External Stakeholders	
UK government	Universities re overall student numbers and funding, immigration monitoring, research excellence, discipline availability.

Devolved governments	Universities re overall student numbers and funding, discipline availability.
Local Authorities	Academic staff, all categories of students; student bed providers.
Office for Students	UK government; academic staff, all categories of students.
National Health Service (NHS)	UK and devolved government,
Alumni	Academic staff, donors
Universities and Colleges Union (UCU) other campus unions	Academic and support staff.
Universities Superannuation Scheme (USS) or other pension providers	Academic and support staff.
UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	UK government; academic staff; PGR students.
Charity research foundations	Academic staff; PGR students
Student -bed providers	All categories of students, NHS.
Donors	Alumni, lenders, investors, commerce.
Lenders	UK government; all categories of students; donors; investors.
Investors	UK government; all categories of students; donors; lenders.
Local business	All categories of students.
Chamber of Commerce	All categories of students.
Local residents – community	All categories of students; local authority.

Table: 2.3 Evolution of main international education terminology

Generic Terms			
Last 10 years	Last 20 years	Last 30 years	Last 50 years
Regionalization	Globalization	Internationalization	International education
Planetization	Borderless education	Multicultural education	International development cooperation
Glocalization	Cross-border education	Intercultural education	Comparative education
Global citizenship	Transnational education	Global education	Correspondence education
Knowledge enterprise	Virtual education	Distance education	
Green internationalization	Internationalization 'abroad'	Offshore or overseas education	
Global rankings	Internationalization 'at home'		
Specific Elements			
Last 10 years	Last 20 years	Last 30 years	Last 50 years
Regional education hubs	Education providers	International students	Foreign students
International competencies	Corporate universities	Study abroad	Student exchange
Degree mills	Liberalization of educational services	Institution agreements	Development projects
Visa factories	Networks	Partnership projects	Cultural agreements
Joint, double, combined degrees	Virtual universities	Area studies	Language study
Branding, status-building	Branch campus	Bi-national cooperation	
	Twinning and franchise programs		

Source : (Knight,2014)

2.2.4 The influence of global ranking on universities

The globalisation and internationalisation of higher education have undoubtedly contributed to the emergence of the world's main university rankings, defined here as a "international comparison of institutional performance and reputation" (Hazelkorn, 2011, cited in Hazelkorn, 2012, p. 342). The first initiative, known as the Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU) or Shanghai ranking, was published in 2003 by Jiao Tong University's Centre for WorldClass

Universities. Its introduction inspired many imitators and had a visible impact on the development of this field. The Times Higher Education World University Ranking (hereafter the THE ranking) was published a year later (2004), based on THE's collaboration with Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) that lasted until 2009 (known as the THEQS ranking). THE began working with Thomas Reuters in 2010 and fundamentally changed its methodology, whereas QS established its own university ranking system, known as the QS World University Ranking, in 2011. (Hereafter the QS ranking). The QS ranking is the most influential for slightly more than half (52 percent) of participants in the European University Association (EUA) survey on rankings and institutional strategies, followed by the THE ranking (50 percent) and ARWU (48 percent) (Hazelkorn et al., 2014). However, in response to methodological criticisms levelled at these early initiatives, some supranational organisations began to advocate for the establishment of alternative ranking systems.

The European Union sponsored the launch of the European multidimensional ranking, also known as UMultirank, which was intended to increase transparency in European higher education by providing detailed information on specific institutional profiles and performance (Hazelkorn, 2012; Westerheijden, 2015). For this discussion, it is critical to examine the main methodological characteristics of the four selected global rankings (ARWU, the THE and QS rankings, UMultirank) in terms of their key categories and indicators, because

only on this basis can the analysis of their international(isation) metrics be continued.

Table 2.4 . Methodological designs of ARWU, the THE and QS ranking and U-Multirank, with emphasis on categories and indicators, associated with internationalisation of higher education

	Categories	Indicators	Weight
ARWU 2017	1. Quality of education	Alumni of an institution winning Nobel Prizes and Fields Medals	10%
	2. Quality of faculty	Staff of an institution winning Nobel Prizes and Fields Medals (20%) Highly cited researchers in 21 broad subject categories (20%)	40%
	3. Research output	Papers published in Nature and Science (20%) Papers indexed in Science Citation Index-expanded (SCIE) and Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) (20%)	40%
	4. Per capita performance	Per capita academic performance of an institution (i. e., full-time equivalent academic staff – domestic and international; without distinction)	10%
THE 2018	1. Teaching	Reputation survey (15%) Staff-to-student ratio (4,5%) Doctorate-to-bachelor's ratio (2,25%) Doctorates-awarded-to-academic-staff ratio (6%) Institutional income (2,25%)	30%
	2. Research	Reputation survey (18%) Research income (6%)	30%

		Research productivity (6%)	
	3. Citations	/	30%
	4. International outlook	International-to-domestic-student ratio (2,5%) International-to-domestic-staff ratio (2,5%) International collaboration (2,5%)	7,5%
	5. Industry income	/	2,5%
QS 2018	1. Academic reputation	Academic reputation from Global Survey	40%
	2. Employer reputation	Employer reputation from Global Survey	10%
	3. Faculty/student ratio	Faculty-student ratio	20%
	4. Citations per faculty	Citations per faculty from Scopus	20%
	5. International faculty ratio	Proportion of international students	5%
	6. International student ratio	Proportion of international faculty	5%
U-Multi- rank 2017	1. Teaching & Learning	*For full list of indicators, representing each category, see the Catalogue of indicators (U-Multirank, 2018). <i>International orientation – indicators:</i> International orientation of BA programmes International orientation of MA programmes Opportunities to study abroad International doctorate degrees International joint publications International research grants Foreign language BA programmes Student mobility International academic staff	/
	2. Research		
	3. International orientation		
	4. Regional engagement		
	5. Knowledge transfer		

		International doctorate degrees	
		International joint publications	
		Foreign language MA programmes	
		Program international orientation	
		Foreign language long first-degree programmes	

Source: ARWU (2017); THE (2017); QS (2017); QS Intelligence Unit (2017);

U-Multirank (2018)

The advancement of quality education and the exploration of innovation in higher education has fueled higher education's internationalisation. Many ranking agencies include HE internationalisation in their global rankings. The ranking is based on three distinct parametric criteria: (1) the teaching-learning process, (2) the research output (Boden, R., et al, 2006), and (3) internationalisation (Yemini, M., et al, 2016). Table 5 depicts major ranking agencies and the weightage of various criteria on the internationalisation of higher education based on the performance indicators chosen. Table 6 lists the various performance indicators used by global university ranking agencies to assess the contribution of higher education to internationalisation. Internationalisation receives 10% of the weightage on average. When combined with the specific scores obtained by an institution in the other criteria, it becomes a significant determinant in the overall ranking. The number of international students and faculty, among other performance indicators, are used to assess the level of internationalisation (Aithal & Suresh Kumar, 2020).

Table :2.5 List of ranking agencies and their weightage for internationalisation of higher education

S. No.	Ranking Agencies	Weightage for Teaching-learning	Weightage for Research output	Weightage for Internationalization
1	Times Higher Education Ranking model, UK	30%	60%	7.5%
2	QS World University Ranking model, UK	40%	20%	10%
3	Round University Ranking (RUR), Russia	40%	40%	10%
4	U.S. News & World Report's Best Global Universities Ranking (USA)	No	90%	10%
5	Global University Ranking, Russia	20%	20%	10%

Table 2.6: Internationalisation as a performance indicator

S. No.	Ranking Agencies	Weightage for Internationalization	Performance Indicators & weightage
1	Times Higher Education Ranking model, UK	7.5%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of international students: 2.5% Percentage of international staff : 2.5% International collaboration : 2.5%
2	QS World University Ranking model, UK	10%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Faculty International Student Ratio
3	Round University Ranking (RUR), Russia	10%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of international staff in percentile (2%) Share of international students in percentile (2%) Share of international co-authored papers (2%) Reputation outside the region (Country/ Continent) (2%) Institutions internationalization level (2%)
4	U.S. News & World Report's Best Global Universities Ranking (USA)	10%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International collaborative publications to country.
5	Global University Ranking, Russia	10%	International Activities like : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Membership of a university in the international academic communities Number of foreign students from an aggregate number of students.

Times Higher Education (THE) scrutinize the research universities on five parameters namely Teaching, Citations, Research, International Outlook, and Industry Income. These are further divided into 13 carefully crafted performance indicators.

Table: 2.7 Ranking parameters

THE Ranking Parameters

S. No.	Ranking Parameters	Performance Indicators
1	Teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reputation survey • Staff-to-student rat • Doctorate-to-bachelor's ratio • Doctorates-awarded-to-academic-staff ratio • Institutional income
2	Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reputation survey • Research income • Research productivity
3	Citations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research influence
4	International Outlook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of international students • Proportion of international staff • International collaboration
5	Industry Income	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer

Source: (THE ,2018)

Rankings depict the global field of higher education as a competition among various actors, such as HEIs. Furthermore, they establish goals for improvement

(rank order) and outline what to improve through their attributes. Furthermore, the top universities serve as ideational models. As a result, university rankings as a phenomenon are inextricably linked to global convergence in higher education and innovation policies, which is frequently motivated by perceived gains for the knowledge-based economy. Higher education is only valued for its economic potential, creating a sense of economist reductionism in the development.

With a few exceptions, there is growing concern about the academic performance of European HEIs in light of global university rankings that show them performing poorly in international comparison. The top HEIs in the United States have higher rankings. National discourses about academic institutions and their reform continue to differ across European nation states. This reflects the relatively limited scope of international regulation in higher education. However, the development of a European policy problem of academic performance has marked the beginning of institutional reforms in Europe, often drawing on global narratives on higher education (Schofer & Meyer, 2005), as echoed by university rankings.

Rankings have a difficult time identifying direct impacts, but they have an indirect impact on ongoing higher education reforms by raising new issues of concern and identifying obvious solutions to them. They also support existing reform agendas. We can see some paradoxes in university rankings and possibly in the global ranking system. Despite the fact that the producers of ranking

information have no norm-giving authority over HEIs or national administrations responsible for higher education, they appear to have a significant influence on higher education policies and institutional reforms in Europe. The producers of rankings have very little accountability, despite the fact that their policy instruments are becoming increasingly powerful in shaping national policies.

(Further detailed information can be found - https://www.hesa.ac.uk/files/International-Benchmarking_2011.pdf)

2.2.5 Approaches and strategies for internationalisation in higher education

An explicit global dimension is included in roughly half of mission statements (in the two-thirds of strategic plans that have one). In this case, the most common theme (representing nearly half of all references) is 'making the world a better place.' The next most common global themes are research, education and students, and reputation and reach (Taylor,2019).

Table: 2.8 The global dimension in mission statements

Source:(Lewis,2020)

Approximately 60% of strategic plans contain at least one strategic theme title that explicitly mentions a global dimension. This is usually a central theme (as opposed to an enabling theme). A little less than one-third of theme titles contain generic words like 'international' or 'global.' Among the rest, roughly half have an outward-facing 'global engagement / contribution' dimension, roughly a third have an inward-looking 'profilebuilding' dimension, and the rest are concerned with aligning the local and the global.(HESA,2020).

Figure 2.1 The global dimension in strategic theme titles

Distribution of global dimensions within UK HEI strategic theme titles (n98)

(HESA,2020)

Approximately 40% of strategic plans articulate explicit Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with the vast majority of these including at least one (often several) KPIs with an international dimension. Among KPIs with an international

dimension, the most commonly used relate to international student recruitment in the UK (and, in some cases, the income derived from this). KPIs related to research are the second most popular. Transnational Education (TNE) activity and student experience are tied for third place. Other international KPIs concern world rankings, international employee profiles, and environmental sustainability. (IES,2020)

Table 2.9 Focus of KPIs with an international dimension in UK HEI strategic plan

Source: (IES,2020)

Although the general content and thrust of these strategies are similar, there appears to be a distinction between the approaches, which are fundamentally either student-centered or university-centered (Caruana,2008).The university-centered approach is more concerned with the university's reputation, branding,

and image, whereas the student-centered approach is much more concerned with the concept of the global citizen (Caruana,2008) and the materialisation of the "knowledge economy and learning society" (Fielden,2007).

A typology of the generic approaches followed by HEIs in the planning and implementation of the strategy has been presented by several significant authors on the issue (Aigner,1992; de Wit, 1995; Knight, 1997,2004). While some concepts overlap, four separate approaches were identified: action, competency, ethos, and process (Qiang, 2003).

However, Knight (2004), added two more new categories: rationales and cross-border. In addition, Knight renamed the category 'ethos' to 'at home'. She explains that the change in typology is because 'at home' focuses on the intercultural/international dimensions of a campus. Knight also modified the 'competency' category to 'outcome'; however, the competency approach is more applicable for this study. The study's goal is to investigate the issues and challenges that UK universities face in advancing internationalisation from the perspective of their staff. The competency approach emphasises the development of skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values in students, faculty, and staff. The central issue in this approach is how knowledge generation and transfer help to develop competencies in higher education personnel so that they become more internationally knowledgeable and interculturally skilled. Thus, in this approach, the development of internationalised curriculum and programmes is a means to

an end of developing appropriate competencies in students, staff, and faculty. As a result, the holistic approach to the development of internationalisation competency is more applicable to this study.

While each method has a key feature that distinguishes it from the others, it is critical to think of them as distinct strands that form different aspects of internationalisation.

Scholars use approaches to IHE typologies to identify the distinguishing features of the definitions they are addressing. For example, (Knight,1994; de Wit, 1999 ;2002) summarise the various approaches that institutions use to plan and implement internationalisation on a practical level (see Table 2.10). These approaches are centred on the various fields of study pursued by researchers or organisations.

Table 2.10 Approaches to internationalisation

APPROACH	DESCRIPTION
Activity	Activities such as study abroad, curriculum and academic programs, institutional linkages and networks, development projects and branch campuses . This was synonymous with 'international education' in the 1970's and 1980's (Qiang, 2003)
Outcomes	Desired outcomes include student competencies, increased profile, more international agreements, partners or projects, competitive advantage
Competency	The development of attitudes, values, skills and knowledge across the whole institution of students, academic and support staff
Ethos	The development of intercultural initiatives and perspectives in a supportive environment and climate that recognise the importance of internationalisation to an HEI
Rationales	Primary drivers including academic standards, income generation, cultural diversity, student and staff development
Process	Integration or infusion of an international or intercultural dimension into teaching, research and service functions through a combination of a wide range of activities, policies and procedures
At home	The creation of a culture or climate on campus that promotes and supports international or intercultural understanding and focuses on campus-based activities
Abroad (cross-border)	Cross-border delivery of education to other countries through a variety of delivery modes (face-face, distance, e-learning) and through different administrative arrangements (franchises, twinning, branch campuses)

(Middlehurst & Woodfield, 2007, p 30)

The activity approach frequently results in rather fragmented and uncoordinated internationalisation programmes that fail to consider the relationships, impacts, and benefits of internationalisation activities (Knight, 1997). This framework has three basic characteristics: it aims at an ideal goal that distinguishes one action from another; it acts through artefacts (tools, language); and it incorporates the societal aspects of its achievement (Özturgut,2014).

The competency method is more directly linked to students', faculty's, and staff's development of knowledge, skills, interests, values, and attitudes (de Wit,1995). As a result, it concentrates on the academic community's human elements, such as students, faculty, and administrative staff. The cornerstone to this approach is how knowledge generation and transfer may help higher education employees gain international capabilities (Qiang, 2003). As a result, the development of internationalised curricula and programmes is seen as a crucial means of ensuring students' future employability (Qiang, 2003).

The process approach requires the participation of both organisational and academic structures (de Wit, 1999). A range of activities, policies, and processes help to integrate or infuse an international, intercultural component into the institution's teaching, research, and service operations (Qiang, 2003).

According to Knight (2004), the rationales approach to strategy focuses on why internationalisation is critical for a higher education institution to become more international. Knight (2004), also observes that the justification for internationalisation is becoming more explicit and changing, as discussed in detail in section 2.2.3.

The ethos approach, now renamed 'at home,' defines internationalisation as the creation of a campus culture or climate that promotes international/intercultural understanding and is focused on campus-based activities (Perez-Encinas,2018).

The cross-border approach is defined as the provision of education to other countries across borders, using a variety of delivery methods, e.g. face-to-face, distance learning, e-learning, and administrative arrangements such as franchises and twinning (Fielden, 2006). All these approaches aid in describing and evaluating how internationalisation strategies are designed, implemented, and conceptualised. As a result, as illustrated in Figure 2.1, different methods reflect different approaches to the adoption and development of internationalisation dimensions (Koutsantoni, 2006a).

2.2.6 Key drivers, rationale, and strategic focus for internationalisation

There are several reasons why universities should internationalise to achieve their goals (Davies, 1992). According to de Wit (2002, p.45), “as the international dimension of higher education gains greater attention and recognition, people tend to use it in the way that best suits their purpose.” A better understanding of the rationale will aid in explaining the term ‘internationalisation’, as well as how these strategies integrate the international dimension into core higher education missions (Ralyk, 2008). Since the 1990s, many scholars have developed a framework for categorising higher education rationales for internationalisation (Teferra, 2013).

A few authors argue that increased global competition has resulted in an urgent need for internationalisation (Armstrong, 2007; McCarthy, 1998; Ray and Solem,

2005). According to McCabe (2001), internationalisation will be the foundation for the development of skills and tools for surviving in a globalised world.

Furthermore, many scholars argue that universities require global knowledge as well as the ability to work professionally and socially in an international and multicultural context contend that providing international understanding to UK graduates is also necessary for future employment. There are two methods for categorising rationales that reflect the increased internationalisation of higher education (Crowther,2000; Dewey,2009; Vapa-Tankosic,2009).

The first is known as the ‘traditional four categories’ framework, which was proposed and developed by deWit (2002). The second is a collection of national and institutional justifications by Knight (2004).

Academic, cultural/social, political, and economic rationales are the four defined categories, according to de Wit (1995). These reflect the connection between the internationalisation process and its potential economic, political, socio-cultural, and academic goals (Wende, 2001; Craciun, 2015). These four categories are not mutually exclusive and have points of convergence and divergence (Jones, 2007).

The second category is related to Knight's revised working definition (2003), which addresses internationalisation in higher education at the institutional and national levels. The collection of national and institutional rationales presented here focuses on the diversity of players involved in the internationalisation process (Knight, 2008).

As shown in Table 2.8 below, these two classification methods are not mutually exclusive; the traditional four categories can also be classified into national and institutional levels, and vice versa. According to Knight, there is no single rationale for internationalisation, and the reasons and motivations are interconnected in either a complementary or contradictory way. "Rationales are changing and closely linked to each other; they can be complementary or contradictory, especially because they can differ according to the interests of diverse stakeholder groups," she claims (1999, p. 205).

One rationale may be found in more than one category, as shown in Table 2.8. This illustrates the perplexing character of these justifications, which may serve several purposes. Knight (2004) contends that categories are blurring and that there is no distinction between national and institutional rationales. Table 2.11 shows all these justifications:

Table 2.11 Rationale driving internationalisation in higher education

Rationales	Existing	of emerging importance
Academic	Enhancement of quality International academic standards International dimension to research and teaching Extension of academic horizon Institution building Profile and status	National Level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources development • Strategic alliances • Income generation/Commercial trade • Nation building/Institution building • Social-cultural development and mutual understanding Institutional level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International branding and profile • Quality enhancement/International standards • Income generation • Student and staff development • Strategic alliances • Knowledge production
Economic	Economic growth and competitiveness Labor market Financial incentives	
Political	Foreign policy National security Technical assistance Peace and mutual understanding National identity Regional identity	
Social/Cultural	National cultural identity Intercultural understanding Social and community development	

Source: Adapted from (Knight, 2008, p. 25)

For economic, political, academic, and sociocultural reasons, higher education leaders have increasingly sought to internationalise their institutions (Childress, 2009). According to de Wit (2015), "we cannot ignore the fact that higher education internationalisation is also being challenged by increasingly profound social, economic, cultural, and political issues" (p. 3). These challenges highlight the significance of internationalisation in the development and modernisation of higher education institutions, particularly universities. The four rationales are discussed next.

Political rationale concerns national security, stability, and a nation's role, position, and ideological influence (Lutabingwa, 2005). Political justification is national and regional, rather than institutional in nature (deWit, 2002). Internationalisation is thus regarded as a “diplomatic investment in future political relationships” with other countries (de Wit 2002). The findings of the International Association of Universities (IAU) in 2003 and 2005, as reported by (Knight, 2003, 2005), and in 2010, as discussed by Beelen (2011), revealed that political reasoning was not among the top ten rationales for internationalisation.

However, it is critical to recognise that this rationale is constantly updated in response to current political and economic situations in a country or the world, so the importance of a particular rationale may rise or fall over time (Wit,1995).

Economic rationale refers to a country's desire to use higher education to benefit the global economic marketplace. Globalisation and economic transformation have gradually ushered in a wave of internationalisation in higher education, with the goal of generating money to help with financial troubles (Maringe, 2013). The aim to train students to succeed within global competition, earn wealth, and contribute to economic progress and competitiveness is one of the economic rationales (Childress,2009).The external and internal effects of economic globalisation have changed higher education's approach to internationalisation (Bagley, 2015).

Economic globalisation and trade liberalisation are important factors in terms of external impact (Altbach, 2007). The World Trade Organization (WTO), according to Altbach (2002), has encouraged higher education to enter the global marketplace through the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS). Within the ongoing GATS negotiations, there is agreement to regard higher education as a package of education; a commodity being marketed nationally and internationally with a buyer model, rather than a model of public responsibility (De Vita, 2003). Thus, higher education's international dimension has been defined as "a commodity or service that can be traded across borders" (McRoy, 2009).

The goal to meet worldwide quality standards in teaching, research, and services is part of the academic rationale. The argument is based on objectives connected to higher education's aims and functions (McRoy, 2009).

This justification focuses on educational aspects of internationalisation, such as the exchange and sharing of ideas, cultures, knowledge, and values (Hazelkorn, 2008). In today's modern and globalised world, the pursuit of experience necessitates vast resources, not all of which are available at any specific university. International cooperation among higher education institutions has thus become a critical requirement (Foster, 2018).

Within the context of this potentially challenging research situation, overseas research collaborations are seen as central to the UK's overall competitiveness

and academic reputation on the global stage (Middlehurst, 2011). International research also allows for the diversification of income streams, as well as access to international expertise, with 40 percent of UK research output produced in collaboration with co-authors from other countries (UK, 2008b).

According to a more recent British Council study, 80 percent of a country's research impact is directly related to its level of international collaboration (British Council, 2016), and international collaborative research has a higher citation rate, which is a common measure of quality (O'Malley, 2012). The majority of the research collaborations investigated were specifically funded projects, such as UKIERI and PMI2 Connect, and involved "multi-dimensional institutional partnerships involving a range of 30 other international activities, frequently involving partners from several different countries" on a regular basis (Middlehurst, 2011; p :21). Academic rationales also emphasise that research opportunities arise as a result of academic staff developing teaching-based partnerships with colleagues in other countries, which foster strong relationships and cultural understanding (Middlehurst, 2011).

According to Warwick & Moogan (2013), internationalisation is a technique for reinforcing educational quality or boosting other academic benefits. This benefit is seen as a significant factor in the advancement of higher education since it considers both internationalisation and quality development. Positive change can be achieved through internationalisation of higher education, such as

strengthening an institution's core activities, improving the human, technical, or management infrastructure, or allowing for the development of new initiatives (Meek,2017).

Another goal arising from the academic approach may be the international visibility and reputation of the institution. As a result, many universities, not just in Western countries, are working hard to gain international recognition as world-class universities in teaching, research, and services. (Knight, 1997; deWit, 1999; Qiang, 2003; Pan,2013).

The cultural and social rationale emphasises student development in order to improve the quality of their lives, as well as the role and importance of a country's culture, diversity, and language. This cultural rationale is based on the belief that it is necessary to resist the “homogenising effects of globalisation” ((Knight J. , 1997), p. 11), as well as to respect nations' culture and language. According to de Wit (2002) p.23, “The most crucial goal for internationalisation of higher education is to extend the values and principles of the national culture of the countries to the world community”.

Furthermore, Paul (2013), claims that internationalisation is an endeavour to increase and assist students' and faculties' global ability to work, interact, and communicate in a multicultural environment, as well as their ability to respect ethnic and cultural diversity.

Internationalisation enables students to investigate their implicit and explicit beliefs about social issues, as well as to develop a more global sense of responsibility and citizenship (Altbach, 2002). According to Räsänen (2007), developing international awareness among students, as well as recognising the interdependence of different regions of the world, is becoming increasingly important. The main argument for this cultural aspect, according to Leask (2013), is that "a university education is about more than just preparing students for the demands of professional practice in a globalised world." It is also important to consider the moral responsibilities that come with local, national, and global citizenship."

The four rationales presented above are based on three of Stier's proposed ideologies: idealism, instrumentalism, and educationalism (Stier,2004). Internationalisation contributes to the creation of a democratic, egalitarian, and equal world (Stier, 2010). This is largely based on Western value systems, and it reduces the likelihood of conflict between nations and cultures. Internationalising higher education is viewed as a global commodity that helps to meet the demands of the capitalist world from an instrumentalist perspective. This ideology underpins the economic justifications for internationalisation, with the primary goals of ensuring a sufficient workforce and facilitating labour mobility.

Furthermore, internationalisation can be a response to enriching the overall academic experience of both students and teaching staff. This ideology underpins

academic rationales in which personal growth and self-actualisation are primary goals (Stier,2004). Internationalisation is a complex process that is fuelled by an effective and ever-changing mix of political, economic, social-cultural, and academic rationales (de Wit, 2015). However, no framework is universally applicable to all institutions (Tian,2015). Each university must devise the most appropriate goals for internationalising their programmes and organisations. Because the institutions studied are in the United Kingdom, some common literature motivations relevant to the analysis of higher education internationalisation were selected for this study.

According to Altbach and Knight (2013), “internationalisation strategies are filtered out and shaped by the institution’s definitive internal context, the types of universities, and how they are embedded nationally. There are various levels of internationalisation strategies, and the relationship and integration of these strategies must be addressed (Knight,2008). Internationalisation consists of two broad complementary strategic components that enhance and strengthen the internationalisation dimension of university functions: programme and organisational strategies (Hudson,2003). The programme strategy encompasses a wide range of academic activities and initiatives in teaching, learning, education, and university services.de Wit (1995), claims that programme strategies initially classified the characteristics of internationalisation programmes into four categories: 1) activities related to research; 2) activities related to education; 3)

extracurricular and institutional services; and 4) technical assistance and development cooperation activities.

Knight (1997) revised the four categories to focus on (1) domestic and offshore external interactions and services. The shifting character of the internationalisation environment from 'aid' to 'trade' has resulted in the transformation of the category of 'technical assistance and development cooperation' into the category of 'external relations and services' (de Wit, 1999; 2002), p. 111, called the categories "a mix", in that some seemingly unrelated activities are grouped together under a single umbrella category. (1) academic programmes; (2) academic research and collaboration; (3) technical assistance; (4) knowledge export; (5) transnational education; and (6) extracurricular activities.

Knight (2004, p. 16), categorises all these internationalisation activities into two broad categories: domestic or campus-based internationalisation and cross-border education, which she refers to as the "two interdependent pillars" of internationalisation.

Figure :2.2 Two pillars of internationalisation: At home and abroad/cross-border.

Source: Adapted from Knight (2012, p.244)

The key distinction between 'internationalisation at home' and 'cross-border education' is that the former is concerned with on-campus internationalisation strategies, whereas the latter is concerned with off-campus activities (Knight,2012).

Internationalisation at home focuses on internationalising curriculum, learning, and teaching processes in order to benefit a large number of students who are not generally exposed to intercultural and international learning experiences (Altbach P. G., 2013). This transformation has gradually spread throughout the world. Wächter (2001), defined this phenomenon as “any international activity other than outbound student and staff mobility”. Beelen (2015), on the other hand, criticised

this definition because, rather than emphasising what ‘internationalisation at home’ is, it focuses on what it is not.

Domestic internationalisation, according to Beelen (2011), should include “a set of ‘at home’ instruments and activities that aim to develop international and intercultural competencies in all students” (p. 65). As a result, Beelen (2015), devised a definition of the concept that may aid in its implementation: “Internationalisation at home is the purposeful integration of international and intercultural dimensions into the formal and informal curriculum for all students within domestic learning environments” (p. 69).

This definition focuses on incorporating the intercultural dimension into the learning and teaching process (Beelen,2015). Home internationalisation raises students’ intercultural awareness and skills, allowing them to succeed in a competitive global labour market (Barnett, 2004; p. 17). Table 2.4 shows the activities that fall within this domestic dimension.

Table 2.12 Activities within domestic dimensions

	Categories
Curriculum and Programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Curricula with international focus, content or relevance ◆ International, intercultural, global or comparative dimension infused into existing courses ◆ Foreign language skills/study ◆ Area or regional studies ◆ Joint or double degrees
Teaching & learning process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Recruitment of international students ◆ Recruitment of international faculty ◆ Virtual student mobility for joint courses ◆ Integration of international, intercultural case studies, role plays and reference materials
Extracurricular activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ International and intercultural campus events
Research & scholarly activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Joint research projects ◆ International conferences and seminars in home campus ◆ International research partners or agreements ◆ Published articles and papers ◆ Research exchange programmes ◆ Integration of visiting researchers and scholars into academic activities on campus

Source: Adapted from Knight (1997, p. 15; 2004, pp. 14-20)

The internationalisation of curriculum and academic programmes tends to be a priority within domestic internationalisation strategies. According to Leask (2015), curriculum internationalisation entails “incorporating international, intercultural, and global dimensions into curriculum content as well as learning outcomes, evaluation tasks, teaching methods, and study programme support services” (p.209). 'At home' internationalisation has been referred to as a ‘movement,’ and has been criticised for focusing on means rather than objectives and shifting to a 'instrumental mode' (Brandenburg and Wit, 2010); for a tendency to use activity rather than results as quality indicators (Whitsed and Green, 2013); and for pretending to be guided by high moral principles while not actively pursuing them (Whitsed and Green, 2013). (Wit,2010). Mestenhauser (2007), criticised the insufficient conceptualisation of

internationalisation at home, as well as the lack of any distinguishable application of learning theories. Clearly, there is still room for improvement.

Cross-border education is defined as the movement of personnel/students, curricula, projects, research, or any form of education across national or regional jurisdictional boundaries (Knight, 2004). Cross-border education is synonymous with transnational, offshore, and borderless education (Knight, 2007). Table 2.5 lists Knight's original categories for cross-border programmes or activities ((Knight, 2007), pp. 25-26).

Table 2.13 Impact on Cross border Education.

Category	Forms and conditions of mobility		
	→ Development Cooperation	→ Educational Linkages	→ Commercial Trade
PEOPLE: Students Professors/scholars Researchers/ Experts/consultants ↓		Semester/year abroad Full degrees Field/research work Internships Sabbaticals Consulting	
PROGRAMS: Course, program, subdegree, degree post-graduate ↓		Twinning Franchised Articulated/validated Joint/double award Online/distance	
PROVIDERS: Institutions Organizations Companies ↓		Branch campus Virtual university Merger/acquisition Independent institutions	
PROJECTS Academic projects Services ↓		Research Curriculum Capacity-building Educational services	

Source: (Knight, 2007, p. 25-26)

Cross-border education includes two notable trends, as shown in the table above: first, a vertical downward shift from student mobility to programme mobility and provider mobility, and second, a significant shift from development cooperation to competitive trade or trade aid from left to right (Knight, 2007, p. 25). The most important component of these categories is student mobility, and more emphasis is currently being placed on delivering various academic courses and programmes to domestic students (Stohl, 2007). According to Knight (2004), these two streams of education, at home internationalisation and cross-border education, should be viewed as interdependent rather than independent: cross-border education has significant implications for 'at home' internationalisation and vice versa. (Knight, 2012) describes three generations of cross-border education from a historical perspective, as shown in Table 2.11.

Table 2.14 Three generations of cross-border education

Cross-border Education	Primary Focus	Description
First Generation	People Mobility Movement of students or professors to foreign country for education purposes.	Students: travel abroad in the forms of full degree or for short-term study, research, fieldwork, internship, or exchange programmes. Professors: travel abroad to teach, conduct research, or seek professional development.
Second Generation	Programme and provider Mobility Movement of programmes or institutions/companies across jurisdictional borders for delivery of education	Programme Mobility Twinning Franchised Articulated/Validated Joint/Double Award Online/Distance Provider Mobility Branch Campus Virtual University Merger/Acquisition Independent Institutions
Third Generation	Education Hubs Countries attract foreign students, researchers, workers, programmes, providers, research and development (R&D) companies for education, training, knowledge production, innovation purposes	Student Hub Students, programme providers move to foreign country for education purposes Talent Hub Students, workers move to foreign country for education and training and employment purposes Knowledge/Innovation Hub Education researchers, scholars, HEIs, R&D centres move to foreign country to produce knowledge and innovation

Source: Knight (2012, p.4)

The term ‘first generation’ refers to student and employee migration from one country to another (Knight, 2012; Yeravdekar, 2014). As Wächter (2003), pointed out, this generation had no structural involvement in higher education (Lee ,2004). This aspect has changed in accordance with the quantity, modes (full degree abroad, exchange, internships, semester/year abroad), and destination countries. The term ‘international mobility of students’ has been defined as “crossing borders to begin studies in the destination country” (Teichler,2017), p. 187.

One of the most visible indicators of internationalisation is student recruitment (Cudmore,2006).Historically, this movement has been associated with knowledge transmission and exposure (Zezeza,2012). However, as a result of globalisation, these activities are now linked to revenue generation and profit-making. According to statistics, the number of students taking advantage of mobility has increased dramatically, from 238,000 in the 1960s (Chen, 2000, as cited in Knight, 2012), to 0.8 million worldwide in 1975 (Noorda,2014), to 4.1 million in 2010 (OECD, 2012), and to an estimated 7.8 million students by 2025 Knight (2012). This modification is depicted in Table 2.7 below.

Table 2.15 Global Mobility of International Students 1960-2025

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Source: OECD, (2012)

In contrast to student mobility, the second generation is concerned with programme mobility. Since the 1990s, this movement has grown significantly (Shields,2013), allowing students to gain international skills and experience without having to leave their homes (Trondal,2012). Branch campuses and virtual universities have emerged as new modes of international mobility. Over the last two decades, the number of joint degrees and exchange programmes has more than tenfold increased (Knight, 2012).

The third generation is represented in various educational hubs. According to Vita (2012), an educational hub is "a deliberate effort to build a critical mass of strategically engaged local and international actors in cross-border education, training, knowledge production, and innovation initiatives."

These educational hubs are the most recent manifestations of internationalisation, heralding the start of a third wave of cross-border initiatives. They are based on and may include first and second generation cross-border activities, but they represent a broader and more strategic configuration of actors and events (Roxa,2012). Without articulated institutional commitment and proper support for organisational strategies, in-program strategies cannot be sustained (Schoorman,1999). Organisational strategies contribute to the institutionalisation of an international dimension through appropriate policies and administrative systems (de Wit, 2002).

According to Foster (2014), higher education institutions must first establish their organisational structure, which will be guided by their motivations, mission, and vision, before they can implement internationalisation programmes. The current literature on internationalisation of higher education proposes four models in general. Models, according to (Elkin, 2005), are mapping techniques that allow measurement of an institution's current level of internationalisation as well as future internationalisation aspirations. These four models are profiled next:

The Davies (1992), model is a very early model of internationalisation of higher education, first published in the Institutionalisation of Approaches to Internationalisation.

Figure 2.3 Institutionalisation of approaches to internationalisation

Source: Davies(1992, p.16)

Davies (1992), investigated some of the organisational consequences of internationalisation in universities, with a focus on the institutionalisation of international strategy. Using the Davies model, the path to the implementation of an internationalisation strategy is determined by its importance to the institution (from marginal to central) and its implementation style (from ad hoc to highly systematic). The Davies model considers internationalisation to be a policy goal for HEIs rather than a process. As a result, the Davies model does not take into account how external and internal factors can change or interact. Overall, despite being somewhat out of date, Davies' early work is critical for understanding the current stage of internationalisation in higher education in the United Kingdom for this thesis.

Rudzki (1993), developed a model with four key components: (1) student mobility, (2) staff development, (3) curriculum innovation, and (4) organisational change. According to Rudzki, the goal of “achieving excellence in teaching and research” is achieved through a combination of these four dimensions (Rudzki, 1995) p. 421. In this model, institutions go through two distinct modes of

internationalisation: reactive and proactive modes, with five stages in each, as illustrated in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 The four dimensions of internationalisation.

Source: Rudzki (1995, p. 421)

During the reactive mode, an institution approaches the internationalisation initiative in five stages, as shown in Table 2.8. The first stage begins with the formalisation of academic staff members who have contacts with other institutions in other countries. The link is then established and formalised in stage two, through agreements between the institutions.

Following that, in stage three, management seeks to control expanding activities through central control. In stage four, there is a potential conflict between management and the organisation's staff, which may result in the abandonment of the goodwill of a portion of the academic staff and a reduction in activities. Stage five is distinguished by maturity or decline, as well as the possibility of

shifting to a more proactive mode (Rudzki, The application of a strategic management model to the internationalization of higher education institutions, 1995).

Table 2.16 Reactive model of internationalisation

Stage 1	Contact	Academic staff engages in making contact with colleagues in other countries, curriculum development, limited mobility, links lack clear formulation of purpose and duration.
Stage 2	Formulation	Some links are formalized with institutional agreements being made. Resources may not be available.
Stage 3	Central/Control	Growth in activity and response by management who seek to gain control of activities.
Stage 4	Conflict	The organizational conflict between staff and management leading to withdrawing of goodwill by staff. Possible decline in activity and disenchantment.
Stage 5	Maturity or Decline	The possible move to a more coherent that is a proactive approach.

Source: Rudzki (1995, p. 437)

The proactive mode, on the other hand, which can be preceded by a reactive mode, begins by exploring the HEI's understanding of the term "internationalisation," as shown in Table 2.13, and then analyses the need for and reasons for internationalisation. Using tools such as SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis, a normative approach could be taken here. After deciding on a strategy and a policy plan, resources must be allocated, and networking with other organisations should begin. The strategy implementation stage comes next, followed by performance evaluation against policy. The final stage is a re-evaluation of policies and strategies, which can be viewed as a return to the first stage in an effort to enrich the process continuously.

Table 2.17 Proactive model of internationalisation

Stage 1	Analysis	Awareness of what internationalisation is and what it entails-What kinds of internationalisation activities are available-international audit, SWOT analysis, Cost-Benefit Analysis.
Stage 2	Choice	Strategic plan, policy drawn up, resources allocated, networking with internal and external organizations.
Stage 3	Implementation	Measure performance
Stage 4	Review	Assessment of performance against policy and plan.
Stage 5	Redefine	Process of continued improvement and the issues of quality this entails

Source: Rudzki (1995, p. 437)

The Rudzki model can be used by HEIs to determine where an institution stands in terms of its strategic focus on internationalisation and its practicality. The model began to depict a process view of internationalisation as a strategic development. Rudzki's work is critical for this thesis because it provides the first rough assessment of an internationalised institution's current organisational strategy.

The descriptive nature of Rudzki's study and Davies' (1992), prescriptive model was central to this thesis, underpinning the goal of analysing and proposing improvements to UK universities' internationalisation strategies. These purely prescriptive or descriptive models, on the other hand, do not reflect the operationalisation process or the dynamic interaction between stages of internationalisation practises. Knight (1994) created a model for the internationalisation cycle that explains how an institution's internationalisation process works. The cycle has six steps in this model, which an institution can

follow at its own pace. While the six phases have a sequence, it is also important to recognise the two-way flow that will occur between the various steps. The framework makes an attempt to describe the steps or phases involved in incorporating an international dimension into any university culture and systems. The first phase begins with an institutional acknowledgement of the importance of internationalisation in terms of "need, purpose, strategies, contentious issues, resource implications, and internationalisation benefits" (Knight, 1994, p. 26). This is followed by the second stage, which includes senior administration, the board of governors, students, faculty, and staff committing to the institution. The planning and third stages include developing institutional policies and priorities that reflect internationalisation's needs and values.

Knight admits that effective internationalisation cannot take root unless the institution carefully executes a fourth step, the operationalisation phase, which includes specific activities and programmes both on and off campus. This is followed by a fifth stage of systematic review, which is intended to monitor the program's effectiveness by all academic units and departments. The stage of reinforcement in Knight's framework is distinguished by institutionally developed incentives, recognition, and reward systems.

Figure 2.5 Internationalisation cycle

Source: Knight (1994, p.12)

Knight's (1994) cycle is important for this thesis because it reflects an understanding of internationalisation as a process with a strategic plan and an objective. Knight's model is useful in demonstrating how to foster a culture in which the international dimension is integrated into the operations of a campus community or an institution. This model, however, has a flaw in that it makes no recommendations for how to interact at different points in time between the steps and does not address how internationalisation affects other functions of the institution.

Knight's model, postulated in the 1990s and subsequently modified over the next decade has provided other scholars with the tools to embellish, improve and further develop a much broader scope that incrementally captures the need to

strategically focus on mainstreaming internationalisation within and across all other functional boundaries of the institution. Specifically, de Wit (2004), and Perez-Encinas (2018), have taken us usefully into this territory, which has helped shape the overall conclusions in chapters four and five.

In five stages, Söderqvist (2002), depicted the evolution of mass internationalisation of higher education institutions from a marginal activity to a strategic approach. Based on Knight's (1994), work, this model has been expanded to focus on an organization's process of internationalising higher education (as shown in Table 2.19).

The Söderqvist model's internationalisation activities and programmes demonstrate how higher education is becoming more diverse and expansive. It represents a genuine shift from 'internationalisation as a marginal activity' to 'company internationalisation' with the goal of improving educational quality. Rather than referring to the process of internationalisation of higher education in an abstract, generic way, as (Knight, 1994; de Wit, 2002) did, this model provided specific activities or programmes relating to each stage of the process.

Table 2.15 Stages of internationalisation in higher education institutions.

Zero Stage Internationalisation as Marginal Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ There are some free movers. ✓ Internationalisation is an exotic and status phenomenon – some important actors in the organization travel to conferences. ✓ Foreign languages are taught.
First Stage Student Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Awareness of the need to internationalise; ✓ Commitment to planning and implementing different programmes enhancing the mobility of students; ✓ Creation of international offices to handle the routines of student mobility.
Second stage Curriculum and Research internationalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Awareness of teachers necessary to make internationalisation of the curriculum and research possible; ✓ Organizing of teacher mobility; ✓ Internationalisation taken as a means to enhance the quality of education; ✓ Different ways to internationalise the curriculum; ✓ Appointment of international coordinators to handle curriculum and research internationalisation.
Third Stage Institutionalization of Internationalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Internationalisation is given a strategy and a structure; ✓ Networking both through cheap travel and new ICT; partnerships and strategic alliances; ✓ The quality of internationalisation is receiving more attention; ✓ Multiculturalism; ✓ Appointment of an internationalisation manager.
Fourth stage Commercialising the Outcomes of Internationalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Exporting education services; ✓ Franchising education services; ✓ Licensing; ✓ Joint ventures; ✓ Strategic alliances; ✓ Creating of organs to promote commercialization.

Source: Söderqvist, (2002, p. 38)

Although Söderqvist did not specify the context, it is believed to be relevant to the context of European higher education.

To summarise, these four models offer the institution useful organisational tools for improving the effectiveness of internationalisation practises. However, it must be recognised that they are Western in nature and have a Eurocentric character, or that they were built primarily on the basis of developed world experiences. It should be noted that this thesis was conducted in the context of the United Kingdom, and that the motivations for developing countries to participate in international activities may differ from those of their more developed and technologically advanced counterparts (Altbach,2004). Indeed,

internationalisation practices are not value-neutral; they are rooted in cultural dimensions such as culture, place, time, and manner (de Wit, 2017). To be successful, it is necessary to identify the most appropriate situations and institutions, because “each organisation has its own organisational culture and operating systems that influence the choice and success of various strategies” (Knight J. , 1997), p. 16). However, the four models discussed above are significant in that they are attempts to ‘visualise’ the various aspects of the internationalisation of higher education, in order to comprehend how it works.

From the literature, there are two alternative approaches to building institutional internationalisation strategies: the ‘framework approach’ and the ‘model approach’.

The framework or model approach from which internationalisation components are derived is inextricably linked to the reliability and nature of the research. The 'framework' approach is argued to be appropriate for this study because the goal is to investigate issues and challenges related to internationalisation strategies in higher education in the UK.

Beerkens (2003), argued that university internationalisation is not only clearly defined within the framework approach, but also distinguished between different elements and how they can be classified as 'at home' or 'cross-border,' and so on. The author has thus developed the internationalisation strategies for this study, not only using the key common components suggested in Knight's theoretical

frameworks (Knight, 1994,2004,2011,2012), but also with a view to adapting and developing the UK context. The key activities relevant to the research sites are depicted in Figure 2.6:

Figure 2.6 The internationalisation strategies addressed in this study

Figure 2.5 depicts the two dominant features of this study of strategic internationalisation programmes: organisational strategies and programme strategies. All five components of organisational strategies can be divided into two categories: managerial and service (Taylor,2004). There are three major

aspects to programme strategies, which can be classified into two categories: 'internationalisation at home' and 'internationalisation abroad' (Altbach, 2004).

In this respect, higher education internationalisation can be understood as both an action and a process that contributes to higher education's ultimate purpose. In general, the proposed paradigm emphasises two key criteria for successful internationalisation. First, higher education institutions require a strategic plan, which Elkin (2008), recommends as a vital component of progressing an institution toward its targeted level of internationalisation. Rudzki also emphasises the importance of including international components in current institutional missions, values, and goals (Rudzki, 2013).

2.2.7 Benefits and cost of internationalisation in higher education

Internationalisation of higher education has numerous advantages. Internationalisation is an efficient method of developing a workforce capable of adapting to international environments (Jie,2006). Higher education is about appreciating cultural differences, and one of the benefits of internationalising higher education is that it fosters understanding among university constituents (Altbach, 2007; Ayoubi, 2007; Maringe, 2009).

According to Stejar (2011), the financial benefits of implementing new internationalisation strategies in higher education can create successful economic engines not only for the educational institution but also for the larger community.

International education graduates of the twenty-first century, according to Bartell

(2003), should be able to comprehend the current world. These advantages are inextricably linked to the economic and political justifications for internationalising higher education.

According to Knight (2012), internationalisation is defined as the expansion of educational hubs and their impact on the national economy. Over 2.5 million students study outside of their home countries, with an increase to 8 million expected by 2022 (Rumbley, 2009). The revenue generated by the host higher education institutions benefits international students significantly. These include income from living expenses, transportation, health insurance, and assistance to accompanying family members (Institute of International Education, 2012); Özturgut (2014), argue that the key rationale is the academic rationale, which is further linked to Stejar (2011), economic rationale, as evidenced by the positive aspects of internationalisation including improved academic quality. Earnings generation and brain gain have the potential to benefit developed countries. Western developed countries are gaining significant financial advantages in all areas, including the ratio of international students, academic franchisors to foreign providers, and quality guarantors (Davis, 2008).

Internationalisation also benefits local students, the University, and the country by diversifying and improving the learning environment. It also has the ability to improve the lives of international students by creating graduates who are well-versed in international issues and sensitive to cross-cultural differences. These

benefits stem from social and cultural considerations (Campbell & Brown, 2003). Student mobility permits them to relocate to a new setting where they can learn about the links between their local and global settings (Hayden, 2003).

According to Miller and Robbins (2004), one of the key methods employed to frame a cost-benefit analysis was economic efficiency. According to the experts, economic efficiency tried to ensure that a project's advantages surpassed its expenses (Miller & Robbins, 2004). Following that, the authors define some intangible gains and costs.

Qualitative elements were recognised as consequences that cannot be quantified, such as personal feelings and emotions, public perception and public relations, and society and cultural norms and values. Emotions, attitudes, and perceptions were used to categorise them. Because of their qualitative nature, intangible gains and expenses were virtually usually expressed in narrative form (Campbell & Brown, 2003).

The International Universities Association (IAU) conducted its fifth global survey on higher education internationalisation in 2018, the first of which was conducted in 2003. The current survey received responses from 907 institutions in 126 countries around the world. The most recent survey, as well as previous editions, included questions about respondents' perceptions of the benefits of internationalisation and why their institutions chose to participate in it. According

to the findings of these surveys, internationalisation in higher education has the ten benefits listed below:

1. Enhanced international cooperation and capacity building.
2. Enhanced internationalisation of the curriculum/ internationalisation at home.
3. Enhanced prestige/profile for the institution.
4. Improved graduate employability.
5. Improved quality of teaching and learning.
6. Increased international awareness of/deeper engagement with global issues by students.
7. Increased international networking by faculty and researchers.
8. Increased/diversified revenue generation.
9. Opportunity to benchmark/compare institutional performance within the context of international good practice.
10. Strengthened institutional research and knowledge production capacity.

2.3 Challenges associated with internationalisation in higher education

While internationalisation of higher education institutions has a greater potential to provide people from diverse backgrounds with access to higher education, its implementation faces challenges that vary depending on the context and nature of internationalisation strategies. This section investigates some of the existing issues that have presented obstacles to the internationalisation of higher education. Indeed, there are several barriers and obstacles to successfully internationalising a higher education institution. There are discussions about the risks and challenges associated with internationalisation strategies and implementation when screening a broad range of publications (Ayoubi, 2007). In terms of risk, many critical issues are identified, such as brain drain (Altbach, 2013); the problem of ‘degree mills’ and low-quality providers (Knight, 2015) the quality of joint degree-level programmes (Knight, 2013) the marketing of higher education (Teichler, 2004) inequality in access (Teichler, 2004), to educational opportunities (Murphy, 2007); (Egron-Polak, 2012), loss of cultural or national identity (Jibeen, 2015).

Several key institutional issues have been identified in terms of challenges, including a lack of financial resources (Alemu, 2014), a lack of human resources (Leask, 2013) a lack of institutional structures (Zolfaghari, Sabran, & Zolfaghari, 2009), a lack of policies, strategies, concrete plans, or appropriate mechanisms to facilitate internationalisation (de Wit, 2015). One of the major challenges identified by (Stohl M. , 2007) was a lack of interest on the part of the faculty and staff in the

internationalisation process. As a result, (Stohl M. , 2007) emphasises the importance of leadership skills combined with assessment and accountability measures as part of a practical set of solutions.

This would necessitate a shift in higher education executive leadership from traditional departmental leadership to curriculum design and teaching leadership. Stohl (2007), model appears punitive and draconian, with a risk-based and reward-based structure. Physical barriers to student mobility, particularly international recruitment and study abroad, are significant: national security measures and new travel and study protocols (Miyokawa,2009).

de Wit (1999), discussed the importance of quality assurance and assessment when developing and implementing an internationalisation strategy for higher education institutions. The authors explained how, by design, a sensitive approach to assessment and evaluation must be given to the diversity of higher education institutions. de Wit (1999), also discussed the challenges of ensuring quality in internationalisation and provided a framework for institutions to use in developing and revising their strategies and policies.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

A networking-based conceptual framework from the study, incorporating the approaches, rationales, and strategies for higher education internationalisation, was found to be satisfactorily and substantially supported by the network theory of internationalisation and networking elements and motivations, according to a

study conducted by Munusamy and Hashim (2020) on the internationalisation of higher education. According to the conceptual framework, the approach, strategy, and rationale for internationalisation can be explained in terms of internationalisation networking through international expansion, market penetration, international integration, multi-lateral governance, bridging mechanisms, partnerships, and strategic alliances (Munusamy & Hashim, 2020). The theoretical framework of this study seeks to incorporate Knight's (2015) definition of internationalisation, with a focus on the three most important terms of higher education internationalisation - the international, intercultural, and global dimensions. These three aspects are supported by the conceptual and organisational framework for higher education internationalisation, which enables the integration of the identified internal and external factors.

Figure : 2.7 Conceptual Framework

2.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis for the current study have been informed by studies on many elements of internationalisation. First and foremost, this chapter examines internationalisation as a driving force behind higher education emergence, development, and expansion. According to a number of academics, internationalisation tactics are motivated by a variety of factors, including political, economic, social, cultural, and cultural growth conditions. Higher education institutions of diverse sizes and scope are using different methods to internationalisation.

People in most higher learning institutions frequently use both, which are also known as programme and organisational strategies. To explain how such systems will work in practise, several authors have proposed models that help determine what stage of internationalisation is being developed, as well as how to minimise the risks and obstacles that must be addressed. Internationalisation barriers include a wide range of factors capable of limiting or preventing internationalisation, as well as inherent internationalisation issues (Altbach & Teichler, 2001).

The purpose of the literature review is to provide insight into the field of accessible studies, which gives meaning to the objectives of this study, as outlined in chapter One. The following observations were made by the author of this study based on the available literature described and examined.

Higher education internationalisation is a global phenomenon that has existed for decades and can be traced back to the Middle Ages. Furthermore, the frameworks discussed in the review show that internationalisation is not a new phenomenon, as numerous in-depth studies are being conducted all over the world. International experts created the majority of the Internationalisation Framework. As a result, more detailed evaluations and feedback from various perspectives will aid in the expansion and improvement of the literature and understanding of this trend known as higher education internationalisation.

The overall significance of student mobility in relation to internationalisation is noted in the literature, to the point where some authors, such as Knight, refer to it as the face of internationalisation. This significant focus on a single aspect, according to the researcher in this study, may result in the sacrifice of certain other critical aspects of higher education internationalisation, such as the promotion of peace and mutual understanding; a more productive cultural life; and an increase in academic quality through curriculum internationalisation. The experience of international students in foreign countries should be one of the primary elements of internationalisation, as this is a key indicator of whether or not internationalisation is taking place.

Although the current literature provides valuable insight into the mechanisms for accelerating higher education internationalisation, it rarely discusses the

improvement in overall performance of universities implementing internationalisation methods.

The next chapter presents an overview of the study design and methodology used to conduct this study.

Chapter 3 – Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Bajpai (2011, p. 7) defines research methodology as:

“a systematic and scientific procedure of data collection, compilation, analysis, interpretation, and implication pertaining to any problem”.

According to Wilson (2010), research methodology is used to obtain new information in a meticulous way. According to Goddard (2004), research strategies are used to investigate new information or to seek answers to unanswered questions. When investigating an exploration issue, a researcher is frequently confronted with a large number of impediments. These impediments can be reduced by employing the proper methodology (Taylor et al., 2015).

The purpose of this chapter is to introduce the study’s methodology and to discuss and legitimise the techniques used to complete the exploration. Other significant areas related to the research approach are also included.

As a study technique to understand the phenomenon, a research design was proposed, with the goal of determining a data generation plan to be used to address the research questions (McMillan, 2014). There are numerous research designs available; however, the overarching goal is to produce findings that allow you to draw the most accurate and reliable conclusions from the answers to your research questions (Creswell, 2007).

This study aims to contribute to a better understanding of the phenomenon of internationalisation of higher education in the United Kingdom as seen through the eyes of the study participants. Based on a qualitative approach to the research, the interpretive model was used in the study. This interpretive research is based on ontological inquiry and the epistemological belief that the people who participate as research subjects create social reality (Cohen, 2011).

The interpretive paradigm filters our understanding of a problem. Because knowledge is constructed and perceived by individuals, it is relative and specific (Cohen, 2011). As a result of this research, a university is recognised as an institution with leaders who strategically determine what is required for its survival.

The study's first section tries to explain how to describe and comprehend higher education internationalisation. In order to investigate the concept and significance of internationalisation in higher education, this addresses the first major research question. Concept analysis is a method of investigation that results in the definition of key terms being clarified (Baldwin, 2009). Clarification of the key concepts incorporated within a research study, according to McMillan (2014), is an important stage in ensuring the appropriate application of a concept.

Furthermore, when the meaning of a concept is unclear, the concept's usefulness in assisting with fundamental research tasks is severely hampered (Rodgers,

1989). Concept analysis is therefore the appropriate methodology for defining concepts such as ‘higher education internationalisation’ (Baldwin, 2009).

The second section of the study concentrated on the methods used by universities in the United Kingdom to improve internationalisation. This study looks into how universities react to the internationalisation of higher education activities. The second section discusses the university's internationalisation strategies and challenges. Face-to-face and telephone semi-structured interviews were deemed appropriate for the qualitative approach. This method focuses on understanding internationalisation experiences at a single university (Eisenhardt,2007).

3.2 Research aim and objectives

As discussed in chapter 1, the purpose of this study is to explore the relevant issues and the motivations that underpin strategies for internationalisation in higher education institutions in the UK. The study explores the various challenges faced in the process of implementation. It is important to identify and analyse the activities, performance indicators, challenges, and the support from government and other institutions within this process. Neuman (2003), contends that research methods are at the heart of data collection in the social sciences and that, with some strategies, any research investigation requires an effective combination of approaches to collect, process, and analyse information. He goes on to say that the nature of the research study influences the method used, and thus the methodology used for the research should complement the study’s objectives.

To help achieve this aim, the following objectives have been set:

- To critically explore the concept of internationalisation in higher education.
- To critically assess the strategies used by the UK universities to advance internationalisation.
- To critically appraise the challenges faced by the universities in implementing strategies in internationalisation.

It is helpful to refer at this point to the form of data collected and the way the research was carried out, as these are central to discussion of the research philosophy and approach pertinent to this research. These areas will be addressed within this chapter.

In order to achieve the above objectives, this study was based on the collection of qualitative data, through the use of in-depth interviews with key informants and interviews with other related staff associated with internationalisation policies and processes in UK universities. More information on the methods of data collection used in this research are given later in the chapter.

3.3 Methodological reflection

Many theorists have proposed that all researchers bring a worldview or paradigm with them that influences how they plan and conduct research (Creswell, 2007).

Researchers bring to our work a unique way of seeing and interpreting the world.

According to Guba (1994), a researcher's paradigm includes not only their basic

belief system and methods chosen, but also the ontological and epistemological considerations they identify as most appropriate. According to Mertens (2005), paradigms are a set of philosophical assumptions that guide and direct both thinking and action.

The idea of translation allows a researcher to map out the interrelationships among components that influence internationalisation. However, as with all research of this kind, a researcher's position in regard to the power structure he or she is researching, and how this influences the translation acts that the researcher is both performing and seeing, remains an issue. We must consider how the researcher's stance influences the procedures of recognising, tracing, and reading the phenomena under study, and how this position influences the research findings. This is first and foremost a power issue.

There is no doubt that a power relationship exists between the researcher and his or her research subjects – the researcher's position has a significant impact on what information is traced and how that information is interpreted. Power dynamics between insiders and outsiders have long been a source of debate among anthropologists (Sherif,2001), geographers (Poth,2016), and other cognate disciplines (Clough,2007).

In terms of researcher positionality, Crotty (2010), contends that “there is no such thing as objectivity in social research. All research findings are created by the researcher in such a (post-structuralist) approach all research is a process of

translation.” It is clear that, when it comes to the “first-order approximations” or “starting points” that matter in mapping the relationship between actors in a network, the researcher's positionality defines which entity should be approached, traced, and analysed, and thus how the school space could be translated and presented into a thesis.

The researcher, as a translator within this study, will never be an all-seeing and all-knowing researcher who uncovers the entire complexity of a case, no matter how well the field work is done, and should not claim this. He/she should instead aim to trace and map the most important connections influencing the outcome of the case at hand. In this study, this entails focusing on the "translation" processes that both policy implementers and the researcher engage in: processes shaped by the dynamics of prescription and negotiation, as well as the back-and-forth movement between the positions of prescriber and negotiator.

All the researchers can do is try to highlight the underlying uncertainty in these positions as much as possible. Rose (1997), reminds us that when it comes to positionality and knowledge production, geographers and other field workers should "keep these worries, and work with them.

"Rose's words are instructive in this regard:

“We cannot know everything, nor can we survey power as if we can fully understand, control or redistribute it. What we may be able to do is something rather more modest but, perhaps, rather more radical: to inscribe

into our research practices some absences and fallibilities while recognizing that the significance of this does not rest entirely in our own hands.” (Rose, 1997).

For decades, philosophers and researchers have disagreed about whether quantitative or qualitative approaches should be used (Clough and Nutbrown, 2007). In this qualitative–quantitative debate, also known as the positivist/empiricist and constructivist/phenomenological split, the issue of validity is a common point of contention between supporters of one approach and supporters of the other (Tashakkori, 1998; Clough and Nutbrown, 2007). A positivist perspective requires controlled settings as the norm, whereas constructivists are concerned with external validity and emphasise the importance of conducting research in natural settings (Tashakkori, 1998).

Over time, many researchers realised that positivism and constructivism are only incompatible when their most strict and pure interpretations are used (Tashakkori, 1998; Trochim, 2006). According to Tashakkori (1998), the paradigm or worldview that sees quantitative and qualitative approaches as compatible has been labelled in a variety of ways, including pragmatism.

Understanding concrete and practical questions about the world and how things work within it does not always require placing a scholar's research within a theoretical framework (Patton, 2002). According to Patton (2002), one does not

have to be concerned with theory or pledge allegiance to any single epistemological perspective in order to solve real-world problems, improve educational programmes, and develop policies. Theoretical frameworks and theory generation, according to Patton (2002), will be of greater concern to students writing dissertations and academic scholars (Patton, 2002), p. 136.

Even though internationalisation studies are primarily concerned with the social world, it is critical to collect multiple perspectives on the phenomenon under investigation in order to gain the most objective and accurate understanding of a topic. Therefore, the topics addressed in the following sections of this chapter. Personal beliefs may motivate researchers to conduct pragmatic research; however, researchers seeking to address educational problems, policies, and practises must rely on something more powerful than their beliefs alone. as stated by (Phillips, 2000). According to Phillips (2000), p. 3, researchers must form opinions based on beliefs that are likely to be true as a result of rigorous investigation; in other words, they must seek knowledge.

Despite the fact that internationalisation studies are primarily concerned with the social world, it is critical to gather multiple perspectives on the phenomenon under investigation in order to gain the most objective and accurate understanding of a topic. As a result, the topics covered in the following sections of this chapter will focus on the issues surrounding the pursuit of knowledge from a broader perspective.

3.4 Methodological organisation

A variety of factors influence research and knowledge-seeking. This chapter section will address the key areas that contextualise the methodology and methods of this research. These are values, theory, ontology, epistemology, and practical considerations, according to (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Methodology is a broad research strategy that specifies how research should be conducted. It consists of a set of beliefs and philosophical assumptions that shape the understanding of the research questions and guide the selection of research methods. A dissertation or thesis' research methodology is an essential component that helps to ensure consistency between the tools, techniques, and underlying philosophy.

One method of developing research methodology is based on the theoretical concept of the "research onion" proposed by (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). The research onion provides a lengthy description of the main layers or stages that must be completed in order to develop an effective methodology (Morrison, 2011). The research methodology begins with the definition of the main philosophy, followed by the selection of approaches, methods, and strategies, as well as the establishment of time horizons, all of which carry the research logic to the research design – the main techniques and procedures for data collection and analysis (figure 3.1)

Saunders (2008), propose the research ‘onion’ as a method for analysing the research process.

Figure :3.1 Research ‘onion’

Source: Saunders (2008, p. 138)

The research onion consists of six main layers:

- Research philosophy - establishes the research's foundation by defining ontology – the nature of reality, epistemology – the nature of knowledge or facts, and axiology – the research's values, beliefs, and ethics.
- Approach to theory development - can be inferred from the preceding level's research philosophy and often includes deduction — the study begins with a pre-existing theory, then poses a query or hypothesis, and collects data to corroborate or refute the hypothesis. induction - the inquiry begins with observation and data collecting, then progresses to description

and analysis to build a hypothesis; Abduction is the process of seeing an empirical phenomenon and then conducting investigation to arrive at a best estimate or conclusion based on the data available.

- Methodological choice- specifies whether quantitative and qualitative methods, or various combinations of both, will be used.
- Strategy- – to collect and analyse data using the following methods: experiment, survey, archival research, case study, ethnography, action research, grounded theory, narrative inquiry.
- Time horizons- This layer defines the time frame for the research – cross-sectional or short-term study, involving data collection at a specific point in time; longitudinal – data collection repeated over a long period of time in order to compare data.
- Data collection and analysis techniques and procedures include the use of primary/secondary data, selecting sample groups, developing questionnaire content, preparing interviews, and so on.

The research onion, proposed by Saunders, et al. (2012), is a tool that aids in the organisation of research and the development of research designs by working through the layers of the research onion step by step. However, because the research onion model was designed primarily for business studies, it would be incorrect to adapt it “as is” for future research. The analysis of literature on futures study’s methodology revealed that futures studies is a distinct research field because it deals with phenomena that

have not yet occurred, and thus it is based on specific ontological and epistemological assumptions that lead to the adoption of strategies, techniques, and methods that differ from those used in business studies.

3.5 Research Philosophy

Cohen, et al. (2007), observes that the philosophical status of the researcher has a significant impact on how research is conducted. The epistemological position of the researcher, how he or she defines the essence of knowledge, will determine his or her contribution to this knowledge and the selection of the methodological techniques used to discover it. Crotty (1998), distinguishes several widely used paradigms, such as positivism, constructivism, subjectivism, pragmatism, and critical paradigms. He goes on to claim that most social science research stems from positivism and social constructionism. Because this is a social science study, the following debate will centre on these two philosophical perspectives.

May (2011), concludes that research philosophy can be clearly described as a way of thinking and conducting research using research paradigms. They also state that the study of research philosophy reveals some significant context influences, such as the individual's mental model, expectations, the way things are seen and analysed, and the variety of assumptions correlated with truth, among other influencing factors. They create a backdrop for, or influence, researchers' expertise.

Crossan (2003), believes that there are numerous reasons why researchers should understand the issue of research philosophy before delving into a specific research area. Easterby-Smith (2012), provide similar explanations, referring to them as follows: Firstly, by understanding the research philosophy, the researcher can refine and specify the research methodology and overall research strategy to be used in the research. It will help in gathering the evidence, origin of the evidence, and the way to interpret such evidence.

Secondly, the knowledge of the research philosophy will assist the researchers to evaluate different methods and leave out the inappropriate ones by identifying their limitations at an early stage; and

Thirdly, by understanding the advantages and benefits of research philosophy, it equips the researcher with greater exploratory and creative skills to implement the research methodology.

According to Saunders, et al (2012), it is critical for a researcher to understand research philosophy because every researcher bases their opinions and forms their perceptions of the world on the assumptions they hold, implicitly or explicitly. Quinlan (2011, p. 95), encapsulates research philosophy when she says:

“Every research project is underpinned by a philosophical framework which evidences the worldview within which the research is situated, and which can be seen in every step of the research process”.

Although the labels used to differentiate between different philosophical positions of interest to this research vary across a wide range of secondary sources, a useful approach is to consider the categorisation used by (Saunders, 2015), which distinguishes between realism, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism. Realism is in the same camp as positivism, but interpretivism is more important in this analysis, so it will be discussed. Positivism is where one prefers to function with:

“Observable social reality and the end product of such research can be law-like generalizations similar to those produced by the physical and natural scientists” (Remenyi, 2005), p.32).

Realism is basically in the same camp as positivism, but interpretivism is more important in this analysis, so it will be discussed. Crowther (2008), confirm this by demonstrating that positivist studies typically take a deductive approach.

The positivist model is linked to observable facts and tests to collect numerical data, whereas the researcher’s own views and expectations play little role in shaping the study. In this philosophical context, the researcher’s approach could be viewed as similar to that of a natural scientist. According to interpretivism, the social world of business and management is far too dynamic to lend itself to the concept of definite ‘laws’ in the way that the physical sciences do. The interpretive position holds that it is critical to investigate the subjective meanings that motivate people’s actions, in order to comprehend them. People tend to have

a wide range of interpretations for situations in which they find themselves, even when the situations themselves are identical.

These various interpretations are likely to have an impact on their behaviour and the essence of their social interactions with others. People, in this sense, not only interact with the world, but also attempt to make sense of it through their perceptions of events and the interpretations they derive from others (Saunders, 2015). In this context, the interpretive viewpoint asserts that truth is socially constructed, in accordance with the social constructionist school of thought.

A researcher in the field of interpretive philosophy is a social agent who values individual differences. The researcher can employ a variety of techniques to focus on various aspects of the research problem (Saunders, 2012). This is a naturalistic approach to data collection that may include interviews, observations, and secondary data.

It is the interpretivist's task to attempt to understand the subjective reality of those they study, in order to make sense of and appreciate their motivations, behaviour, and intentions in a way that is relevant to the research subjects being undertaken. There is a strong element of analysis within the interpretivist tradition of the qualitative data collected through the in-depth interviews with key informants and the interviews with specific staff engaged in the process of internationalisation in higher education in the United Kingdom, and it was essential for this study to

explore their views and expectations in relation to internationalisation concepts, challenges, and strategies.

3.6 Research Approaches

In relation to conducting research, two key approaches to research have traditionally been established. They are divided into two types: deductive and inductive methods. The deductive method is linked to testing theory, and Saunders (2015), define the approach as one in which the researcher:

“Develops a theory and hypothesis (or hypotheses) and designs a research strategy to test the hypothesis” (p.124).

Deduction necessitates a well-organized approach and the collection of detailed quantitative data. The driving force behind the data collection process is the theory and the hypotheses that arise from it ((Bryman & Bell, 2007), p. 11).

In contrast, the inductive approach necessitates the creation of a hypothesis based on observation. It is also described as a method where one's experiences including what is learned from others, are synthesized to come up with a general truth (Gill,2010). This method seeks to define patterns and relationships in order to generate hypotheses by extracting meanings from collected data. There are no assumptions in this approach at the start of the study, and the existence of the research results is unknown before the research is completed (Neuman, 2003). The inductive approach entails collecting qualitative data, demonstrating the need

to understand the meanings that humans attach to events, and gaining a thorough understanding of the research context.

Both deductive and inductive methods have been criticised by theorists, with the deductive method being criticised for a lack of clarity about how to choose a hypothesis to be tested. The inductive approach has been questioned on the grounds that “no amount of empiric evidence can actually make it possible to create a hypothesis” (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012), p. 126).

This study examines participants’ perceptions and understanding of the concept of internationalisation. The research design for the study is qualitative analysis using in-depth semi-structured interviews. The intention was that themes would emerge from the interview data collected, which justifies the inductive approach for the study.

3.7 Research Design

Much has been written about qualitative research methods' dominance and limitations (Marshall, 1996; Creswell, 2007; Cohen, 2011; McMillan, 2014). Some critics claim that the qualitative research process is flawed and that it is inferior to quantitative research. Such criticisms may be viewed as unfair if the purpose of qualitative research is not known (Denzin, 2009).

The idea that qualitative research is performed or produces the same results as quantitative research is a methodological error, because each type of study has a distinct goal and employs distinct instruments (Creswell, 2007). According to

Cohen (2011), when a decision is made between quantitative and qualitative analytical methodologies, this should primarily be influenced by the research question, rather than the researcher's personal preference.

Qualitative research is important for this study because it is more descriptive, holistic, exploratory, and contextual in nature, with the goal of producing a rich description of the phenomena under investigation (Creswell, 2007).

A number of previous reports on higher education internationalisation have sought out quantitative data rather than qualitative data in order to explain the phenomenon (Chan, 2008; Childress, 2009; Cross, 2011; Taylor, 2004; Warwick, 2014; Welch, 2004). This study's researcher was also familiar with higher education internationalisation through qualitative data development using two approaches to contribute to and enrich understanding of the phenomenon. The participants' perspectives on internationalisation of higher education were investigated in this qualitative study.

As a result, qualitative analysis provided natural knowledge to improve understanding of the phenomenon. This enabled researchers to investigate, make sense of, and interpret the phenomenon in light of the context provided by respondents (Leech, 2007). The qualitative approach's entire point is that it is naturalistic. It investigates real people in natural settings rather than artificially isolated individuals. (Babbie; Denzin, 2009).

The basic premise of qualitative research is that people who participate in their social environments influence reality (Cohen L. L., 2011). The dominance of qualitative research is frequently based on the desire to find significance in small and purposefully chosen samples, and researchers are the primary tool for data generation, inductive interpretation, and an overall explanation of results (Leech, 2007).

As a result, the primary goal of qualitative research is to contribute to the analysis and enhancement of understanding rather than to validate previous findings.

3.8 Research Strategy

This study examines internationalisation within the university system and includes interviews with one person in each university with a role related to internationalisation. The study also considered and discussed thoroughly a model put forward by Knight (1994), based on the internationalisation cycle, as well as two supplementary models drawn up by (De Wit, 2004; Perez-Encinas, 2018). All these models were then subjected to rigorous scrutiny in order to identify points of convergence and divergence between the research documented here. This work has enabled the author to identify new dimensions which were not obvious or visible in the three-academic work.

As a result, a range of recommendations have been formulated and these appear in chapter 6.

3.9 Selection of the Universities

The act, process, or technique of selecting samples is known as sampling. A sample is a subset of the population chosen for research (Bryman,2011). A proportionate sample can be appropriate for the study of a problem or research issue, according to (Sekaran, 2016). It is impossible to collect data from everyone in the population, since a researcher would not have access to the entire population. In any case, due to time, resource, and access constraints, it is difficult to obtain all of the data from all known instances. Consequently, this is not always necessary when conducting research. This is where sampling methods are useful. They provide:

“a range of methods that enable you to reduce the amount of data you need to collect by considering data from a sub-group rather than all possible cases” ((Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012), p. 210).

The main goal of the sampling approach is to select a representative sample from the population being studied, so that the survey sample’s results accurately reflect the entire survey. Creswell, for example, emphasises the importance of choosing the best candidates for interviews (2007). This study’s participants were chosen from universities in the United Kingdom. These universities were selected based on their profile, year of establishment, international agenda, geographical location and those who responded positively to participate in the study allowing

the researcher to investigate the implementation of higher education internationalisation.

The cases were chosen in this manner to demonstrate a university's willingness to engage in internationalisation operations. The study's findings were expected to provide the knowledge required to resurrect internal and global opportunities for implementing internationalisation methods.

Babbie (2013), understanding that it is often necessary to select a sample based on knowledge of the population, its elements, and the purpose of the research guided the selection of participants at universities. While random sampling is a common method because it allows for the selection of each member, giving the population a better chance of generalising the findings (Cohen,2011), it is ineffective in understanding a complex phenomenon such as human behaviour.

In a complex sample, random sampling entails identifying the entire population, which can be difficult. Furthermore, for representational purposes, random sampling entails uniformly distributing the sampled characteristics across the population (McMillan, 2014). To select targeted participants at the universities, a purposeful sampling technique was used. Purposive sampling, according to McMillan (2014), focuses on the collection of information-rich cases that can potentially shed light on the issues addressed by a research study. Green (2014), elaborates on purposeful sampling within science, explaining that specific subjects are chosen to be included on the basis of judgement, as these subjects are

assumed to promote a deeper understanding of the phenomenon. According to Cohen (2011), sampling in qualitative research should be guided by the conceptual problem of the analysis.

At the start of the selection process, all UK universities were considered potential cases. All universities were emailed with the research information, and those that responded positively were chosen.(See Appendix – Interview guide and Interview Schedule) The universities were selected based on their positive response towards participating in the study.. The type of university was the second criterion-Ancient ,Russell group,Red Brick, Plate Glass (Times Higher Education,2020). The university's accessibility and location (England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland) were also considered. Some universities that responded but did not meet the research timeline were not considered this was due to the outbreak of Covid-19 unavailability of staff and universities were shut.

The sample was chosen using purposeful sampling for the interviews with key informants because it was felt that each informant had something to contribute to the study. The researcher identified the participants through contacts and networks, social media, and emails

To gain a comprehensive understanding of each university's internationalisation strategy in the UK, key personnel familiar with their internationalisation strategy activities were interviewed. The following were the primary selection criteria for these employees:

The chosen interviewee must have:

- Responsibility (personal or shared) for the university's overall international strategic development.
- Participate in cross-border decision-making and implementation activities, including initial partnership negotiation and establishment
- Must be involved in the process of universities internationalisation activities.

(Dean, International office staff, strategy and policy making , Vice chancellor, Planning director, student recruitment and partnerships)

The interviewees were initially contacted by the author's letter after identifying the appropriate interviewees from each university. The invitation letter served three functions. First, the author introduced himself and explained why he was writing the invitation letter. Second, the author clearly stated the key research questions in order to ensure that the interviewees were fully prepared for the interview. Third, the author stated unequivocally that the information gleaned from the interview, as well as the true identity of the interviewee and their university, would be considered confidential.

A small number of individuals were chosen through snowball sampling. In the snowball sampling method, a researcher identifies one study participant and asks that individual to identify the next individual, after the researcher has completed

the research with the first person (Quinlan, 2011). When the study was conducted with the selected participants they mentioned and recommended other colleagues from different universities with similar profile and who could potentially contribute to the research. The researcher further contact them and conducted the interview after getting a positive response and following. However, in accordance with confidentiality agreements with study participants, the studies may not explicitly refer to a specific organisation or person and have thus been anonymised.

Table :3.1 List of Participants

University	Type of University	Location	Job Title	International Strategy
University 1	Red Brick	England	International Officer	Yes
University 2	Plate Glass	Scotland	Vice-Chancellor	Yes
University 3	Russell Group	England	Strategic Development Officer	Yes
University 4	Plate Glass	Wales	International Officer	Yes (in process)
University 5	Red Brick	Northern Ireland	Director of Marketing and Recruitment	Yes
University 6	New University	England	International Regional manager	Yes

University				Yes
7	Russell group	England	Director of Partners	
University			Head of Transnational	Yes
8	Red Brick	Scotland	Education	
University			Head of faculty marketing and	Yes
9	Plate Glass	England	Student Recruitment	
University				Yes (in
10	New University	England	Business Partner	process)
University				Yes
11	Red Brick	Wales	International Director	
University				Yes
12	Ancient	England	Partnerships Director	
University			Marketing and strategic	Yes
13	Red Brick	England	partnership officer	

(Authors creation for the study)

3.10 Data collection

A data-generation strategy is essential in qualitative analysis because the study's reliability is dependent on the reliability of the data generation methods used (McNamara,2009). Primary data processing was accomplished using semi-structured face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, and Skype calls. The use of interviews as a data generation strategy provides in-depth knowledge of the participant's point of view and position on a specific subject (McMillan, 2014).

Boyce (2006, p. 3), believes that conducting intensive individual interviews with a small number of respondents can be a useful way of examining their

views and opinions on a specific concept, programme, or circumstance. Cohen (2011, p. 307), believes that interviews are a type of interaction between the interviewer and the interviewee. It is:

“initiated by the interviewer for the specific purpose of obtaining research-relevant information and focused by him on content specified by the research objectives of systematic description, prediction or explanation”.

The interviewing process, according to Pontin (2000), is one in which researchers gather information from targeted informants or stakeholders who have a relationship with and an interest in the subject. Their attitudes, values, responses to services, or personal experiences could all be gathered. Conducting interviews where: According to Saunders (2015), it is part of the inductive nature of research to conduct interviews where:

“the purpose here would be to get a feel of what was going on, so as to understand better the nature of the problem” (p. 126).

This suggests that interviews aim to understand the social environment in which the research is conducted, rather than simply collecting statistical evidence. Interviews can be conducted one-on-one, face-to-face, or over the phone. According to Saunders (2015), interviews can be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured. The style chosen is determined by the research topic. An unstructured interview is one in which no questions are planned and

instead “emerge during the course of the interview” (Quinlan, 2011), p. 133).

The researcher, on the other hand, must be familiar with the aspects or issues that they wish to investigate. The interviewer will ask questions, and the interviewee will be free to respond openly, with the interviewer only referring to points worth following up on. The format of such interviews is very similar to a conversation.

Structured interviews are diametrically opposed to unstructured interviews. A structured interview (also known as a standardised interview) is a quantitative research tool widely used in research, according to (Adam,2008). The final interview type is semi-structured interviews. These interviews include a list of questions on a specific subject, which is sometimes referred to as an interview guide, but the interviewee has a great deal of leeway in answering. The interview questions are not necessarily asked in the order specified in the interview guide. As the interview progresses, the set of questions can be changed.

The interviewer may change the order of the questions and may also ask similar but unexpected questions that were not originally included, in response to what are considered important answers. This method can lead to the discovery of previously unknown and useful information, thereby improving findings. The semi-structured in-depth interviews used in this study had the primary advantage of allowing informants to open up in a relaxed environment and discuss their experiences (Liamputtong, 2005).

By assisting in the creation of a participant's interpretation of truth, it enabled the researcher to gain rich knowledge with a small number of participants (Jensen, 2013; Collier,1996). It was also a tool that allowed the researcher to directly observe the research problem (Patton, 2002).

The next section discusses semi-structured in-depth interviews, which were an important part of stage two of the data collection process for this study.

The interview method is based on the perception of causal inferences. The method of interviewing, like any other form of data collection, is not without limitations. Prejudice resulting from poor questions, bias in answers, and the possibility that the interviewee might say what the interviewer wants to hear are all potential faults that might arise (Kvale,2004).

However, bias was avoided in this study by asking all study participants the same questions and avoiding leading questions. All interviews were recorded verbatim to reduce the possibility of bias. Knowledge has been gathered to create emerging trends. A primary approach to the participation of multiple or extremely experienced informants from various perspectives who interpret the focal phenomenon adds credibility to the data (Eisenhardt, 2007).Participants in higher education, in this case, people involved with internationalisation at the institutional level, should be highly skilled and knowledgeable. Thirteen participants were interviewed face-to-face in their workplace offices and over the phone. Invitations to participate in an interview were sent out, and

interviews were scheduled once the participant's signed letter of consent was received. (see Appendix -2)

However, arranging a meeting was difficult due to the busy schedules of possible participants and start of a global pandemic lockdown, which could not have been foreseen by the researcher. Each interview lasted approximately one hour.

The interviews were semi-structured in nature. The interviewees were given the freedom to discuss subjects other than the topic at hand. For example, some interviewees not only provided the required data, but also shared their personal feelings, opinions, and personal stories about their cross-border activities with the author. As a result, more useful information was obtained. In particular, for the semi-structured interviews, the interviewees provided some additional contacts for future interview opportunities.

According to the author, there were two critical aspects that could have been improved in order to better manage the interviews. To begin with, having interviewees focus on the questions is critical; otherwise, time management is difficult. Some interviewees, for example, were very enthusiastic about the interview questions and shared a large amount of less useful information during the interview. As a result, the interview ended up lasting longer than expected. Second, due to confidentiality concerns, a few interviewees felt passive in response to the questions, resulting in limited information being obtained. This recorded information was transcribed manually by the author.

3.10 Data Quality

In order to ensure research data quality, several quality criteria were established: data source, interviewees checking transcripts, data cross-checking with documentation information, interviewee qualifications. First and foremost, before meeting with interviewees, the researcher conducted extensive research on the websites of both their university and partners to provide additional background information. The goal of this was to give the researcher the confidence to question interviewees if they provided any contradictory information. As previously stated, the "qualifications" of the interviewees were critical to data relevance and quality. Interviewees must have relevant experience with university internationalisation activities. Furthermore, their position must be senior in order for the researcher to obtain insightful data on motivation, decision making, and implementation challenges.

There were some data differences provided by interviewees. The researcher either asked for an explanation during the interview or followed up with the interviewees afterwards to acknowledge the data. Thus, the data quality was ensured by using these criteria and information cross-checking procedures.

At the end of each interview, the researcher explained the application of the findings to the interviewees, and the findings will be used as a reference guide and destroyed once the research is completed.

3.11 Data analysis

Moore *et al.* (2012, p. 25) add that data analysis is:

“a process of piecing together data, of making the invisible obvious, of recognising the significant from the insignificant, of linking seemingly unrelated facts logically, of fitting categories one with another and of attributing consequences to antecedents”.

Because qualitative data collection can be ongoing and vast, data collection tools and any other study-related knowledge should be used (Cohen L. L., 2011). Qualitative data analysis, according to Bajpai (2011), entails the formulation of conclusions rather than performance analysis. In the analysis of qualitative data for this research study, a basic standardised format for the analysis of the collected data has been adopted, with no use of software.

The use of computer software was examined but rejected due to flaws in software packages and the fact that recognition software does not accurately depict the interviewee’s gestures, emotions, and body language (Rubin, 2012). As a result, software is unable to ‘focus’ on raw data in the same way that the researcher’s eye can. Indeed, a manual approach to qualitative data analysis is often more convenient and accurate, as feeding a huge amount of data into a software package can be difficult and time-consuming. The data in this analysis was manually sorted and processed by creating separate folders for each stage of the

process. To ensure anonymity, the real names of respondents were replaced by random numbers, after transcribing the audio recordings of the interview.

When interviews or other methods of data generation are used, concepts emerge that can be best interpreted with the help of a suitable method for qualitative data analysis. There are numerous qualitative data analysis methods, such as grounded theory and discourse analysis, to name just two. In this study, thematic analysis was used (Braun, 2006).

Thematic analysis was used to create the study's meaning because thematic analysis allows for the identification of emerging and dominant themes as the study's subject. The dominant themes are typically highlighted, with the end goal of demonstrating the analysis's significance.

Data analysis in qualitative research makes sense from the perspective of the participant's definition of the situation (Cohen, 2011). Thematic analysis was used in this study because, unlike other methods for qualitative data analysis, it is simple in terms of information demand and does not necessitate the complexity of qualitative research theoretical foundations (Howitt, 2011).

This method's theoretical versatility was important because it allowed the researcher to establish themes without restriction. Furthermore, the use of a thematic approach was motivated not only by its versatility, but also by its potential to allow the investigator to use multiple data sources. As a result, the

researcher can assess the data in a flexible and systematic manner thanks to the intrinsic qualities.

Thematic analysis methodology, like many other methods, has inherent limitations. The thematic approach, as with many qualitative data analysis methods, is labour-intensive and time-consuming. On the other hand, while its adaptability is lauded by some commentators, there is no agreed-upon standard approach; instead, various researchers use the thematic approach in a variety of ways (Howitt, 2011). Other flaws in the thematic approach, according to Braun (2006), can be caused by unclear or ambiguous research questions.

Based on these assertions, the value of an analysis will be brought into question unless the researcher takes the initiative to mitigate these potential vulnerabilities. Because there were no predetermined codes or categories to investigate, the emerging themes were documented. For this study, data was analysed manually not only because the study revealed inconsistencies between software and manual analysis, but also because manual analysis allowed the researcher to understand hidden meanings and concepts; it also allowed the researcher to have a personal data experience (Rademaker, 2012).

Thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) was used to target the identification and investigation of common themes across the entire dataset. During this phase, the researcher was guided by the research questions, theoretical underpinnings,

and themes emerging from the data itself. The researcher also performed the analysis manually to gain a better understanding of the dataset.

There were three separate steps involved in the analytical process . First, all data was placed in Internals/Sources, where separate files for each interview were created. This was followed by “repeated reading” of the data actively to familiarise with the data. The second step involved generating initial codes, and then matching them up with data extracts that validate the code, and finally collating data extracts within each code.

This involved adding colour nodes (themes) to the transcripts, copying data from individual transcripts, and compiling each code as Braun and Clarke recommended in separate computer files (2006).

The unit of coding was an “extended account” (Riessman, 2000, 7), which consisted of block quotes that reflected participants’ comments on one topic or one question. The reason for this was to ensure that specific meanings of responses would not be lost at later analytic stages and to ensure that the responses would be analysed within the context they were made. The list of the initial themes can be found in Appendix 7. The third step involved generating the main themes. At this point, the initial themes were revisited in order to reorganise the data in order to relate back to the research questions as well as the background literature. Some of the themes were reorganised under one larger category.

Finally, the long list of themes and categories were grouped under FIVE main headings.

This research adds to the core data collection effort, which is conducting qualitative, semi-structured interviews with informants in person and over the phone/skype. The key codes were purposefully designed in order to target the research questions, as exemplified (See table 3.2)

Table :3.2 Interview schedule with themes (First step)

THEMES	o <u>INTERVIEW SCHEDULE</u>
Meaning	In the context of higher education, what is your understanding of internationalisation?
Agenda	Does your institution have an internationalisation agenda? ➤ If yes, what is the rationale for pursuing this agenda?
Drivers	What are the principal drivers of internationalisation in your institution?
Themes	What would you say are the key themes of your internationalisation agenda?
strategy	➤ How is the internationalisation agenda implemented i.e. what strategies or measures has your institution adopted to pursue internationalisation activities?
Resources	➤ Do you have a unit/division that is specifically responsible for internationalisation If yes, do you believe it is sufficiently resourced to achieve the internationalisation agenda?
Mechanism	➤ What mechanisms are in place to promote internationalisation in your institution?
leadership	➤ How is the University leadership supporting internationalisation at the institution?
Challenges	➤ What challenges have you encountered or perceive in attempting to implement your internationalisation agenda?
approach	➤ How would you differentiate your institution's approach to internationalisation in relation to other institutions?

Likewise, the key codes are used repeatedly within each case, but with different university names. For example, in the coding process, the common code Motivation is used, and it also connects codes related to individual universities, as shown below.

In the context of higher education, what is your understanding of internationalisation?

PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	•intercultural and global perspectives that we're trying to work through the universities, teaching research and business activity.	optimism in university's views about the curriculum making a global impact.	research
	•curriculum to mobility opportunities	The university has significant awareness about student mobility and is currently dealing with highest rate of student mobility.	student mobility
	•environmental sustainability	The university is positively inclined towards collaborating with students globally.	collaboration globally
	-	-	curriculum

UNIVERSITY 4	•Working with partnerships	There is a strong support for activities like research, teaching, partnership taking internationalisation into consideration.	research
	•international student recruitment	There is an acknowledgement about the university's intent towards making a global impact.	collaboration
	•offering an international experience	-	global impact
	•curriculum also includes global perspectives	-	-
	•research exchanges	-	-
	•staff exchange	-	-
	•inward and outward student mobility	-	-
	•Internationalisation of the whole community	-	-

Further see appendix – 7 -16 for initial findings and themes for all the interviews

3.12 Ethical Issues

Ethics is also an important aspect of any research project. Researchers are expected to be extremely ethical in their analysis and approach to the topic under consideration, as are the participants or respondents (McMillan, 2014). When gathering data, it is critical for any researcher to have permission to access the data. According to Punch (2014), research should never cause harm, and the

researcher must obtain full informed consent while also protecting privacy and confidentiality. Cohen (2011, p. 53), asserts that prosecutors, by analogy, cannot conduct investigations as a matter of law. They must first obtain permission and demonstrate the value of their research.

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS), where the researcher is pursuing her doctorate, has a strong ethical approval process in place. UWS does not allow any research to begin until it has been approved by a peer-reviewed ethical committee. This ethical approval process is assessed and amended on a regular basis in accordance with good practice guidelines for conducting academic research. Any regulatory obligations, such as the new General Data Protection Rules (GDPR regulations), must also be adhered to. Confidentiality, anonymity, data protection, and permission are all taken into account during the ethical approval process. A 'participant information sheet,' created by the researcher, is given to potential participants as part of this process. This document explains the research's purpose, as well as the study's goals and objectives, and emphasises that participation in the study is entirely optional. as well as the opportunity to Participants should be informed that they have the option to withdraw from their involvement at any moment. It also explains why participants have been invited to participate, as well as the level and nature of involvement required of them (e.g., to complete a survey or participate in a focus group or interview). It also confirms that participants will not be exposed to any physical, psychological, or

legal risk or harm. Participants are requested to sign a consent form confirming their willingness to participate and, if applicable, their approval to be video/audio recorded once they have expressed their readiness to participate. It's also stated to potential participants what will happen to the data they acquire and how it'll be managed, including how it'll be stored, safeguarded, used, and disposed of.

For this study, the researcher submitted a complete application for ethical approval. Once approved, the research could begin. Participant information sheets were distributed to the participants. Prospective participants were assured as part of the ethical approval process that every precaution would be taken to maintain confidentiality and anonymity, and that data collected would be managed in such a way that the data and participants' identities would not be disclosed to any unauthorised party. The signed consent forms of the participants were then collected and securely stored.

In terms of ethics and data management, all data collected and captured was securely stored and kept out of the hands of unauthorised parties. UWS is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office, which oversees ensuring that GDPR and related legislation are implemented legally.

3.13 Chapter Summary

The third chapter presented a thorough consideration of the study's research design, methodology, and the methodology used during the research process. The thesis provides an interpretive qualitative study of higher education internationalisation at UK universities. Face-to-face and telephone interviews with thirteen respondents were used to collect data. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data. The analysis's worth was justified by the explanation of the research positioning, the validity of the research process, the findings' reliability, credibility, and transferability. The chapter that follows discusses the findings from the interview data collected.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to present the main research findings derived from interviews with participants at the selected UK universities. The rationale for investigating the topic of internationalisation in the context of UK higher education was established in both the literature review and the research methodology chapters. This chapter looks at internationalisation from the perspective of those who are directly involved in the process of internationalisation.

The discussion that follows provides insights into the complexities and challenges of internationalisation, as well as a map of the scope and meaning of internationalisation from the standpoint of UK higher education. The study's findings shed light on the interpretations, perceptions, and experiences of internationalisation staff as they navigate different paths through a rapidly changing higher education landscape.

Thirteen interviews were carried out in a range of different universities in the UK, and these are profiled with the responses in the sequence shown below.

Table :4.1 List and Profile of participants

University	Type of University	Location	Job Title
University 1	Red Brick	England	International Officer
University 2	Plate Glass	Scotland	Vice-Chancellor
University 3	Russell Group	England	Strategic Development Officer
University 4	Plate Glass	Wales	International Officer
University 5	Red Brick	Northern Ireland	Director of Marketing and Recruitment
University 6	New University	England	International Regional manager
University 7	Russell group	England	Director of Partners
University 8	Red Brick	Scotland	Head of Transnational Education
University 9	Plate Glass	England	Head of faculty marketing and Student Recruitment
University 10	New University	England	Business Partner
University 11	Red Brick	Wales	International Director
University 12	Ancient	England	Partnerships Director
University 13	Red Brick	England	Marketing and strategic partnership officer

The interview questions aimed to fulfil the research questions:

- What is understood by the term ‘internationalisation’ in the context of higher education?

- What strategies have institutions implemented to advance the internationalisation agenda?
- What challenges have universities encountered in their drive to advance the internationalisation agenda?

as well as the objectives of study discussed in chapter 1 and chapter 2:

The perspectives are used in this chapter to highlight responses from each participating university that forwarded an individual for interview who they felt was best placed to comment on their internationalisation agenda. The names of the participants are withheld, in order to protect their anonymity and to comply with the ethical requirements outlined in chapter 3.

The following ten themes emerged from the answers to the interview questions:

- Perception of meaning of internationalisation in the context of UK higher education.
- Agenda, importance, and rationales for internationalisation of UK higher education
- Drivers of internationalisation
- Key themes of an internationalisation agenda
- Strategies, measures, and implementation process in internationalisation
- Resources for internationalisation
- Mechanism to promote internationalisation

- Leadership support in the process of internationalisation
- Challenges encountered in implementing an internationalisation agenda.
- Differentiation approach compared to other universities.

These ten themes are now discussed in turn below:

4.1.1 Perception and meaning of internationalisation in the context of higher education

All the participants were aware of and understood the concept of internationalisation, either through their roles or their involvement in the internationalisation process at their respective institutions. They could also discuss and explain their understanding of internationalisation in relation to their institutional activities. According to most respondents, internationalisation entails establishing partnerships with various universities both at home and abroad, student recruitment, staff and student mobility, research collaborations, and curriculum internationalisation. The perspectives of some key informants are reflected in the comments below:

"It pertains to our activities and relationships with overseas institutions in terms of learning, teaching, and research, as well as all recruitment of students to study on our campus, as well as our students' opportunity to study or work abroad for placement periods." Students from other institutions, on the other hand, are welcome to come and study here for a limited time, and this is due

to the nature and content of our programme." (*Interviewee 2, University 2*)

“It is what we do for our students, staff, what we do for community and commercialization is a thread through every activity, including our research, our teaching partnership, stuff, recruitment, agent, which meant that we always have front of mind, that what we're doing, we want to have an impact globally. Right. And that were always not just thinking locally, but globally”. (*Interviewee 7, University 7*)

The views expressed above appear to reflect the concept of internationalisation in other UK academic locations, the university's external image, and its relationship with institutions in other countries.

The first idea of higher education internationalisation is centred on curriculum internationalisation. Participants who shared this perspective defined internationalisation of higher education as incorporating an international and intercultural dimension into traditional curriculum, teaching, and learning methods, or adopting a comprehensive package of joint degree-level programmes from prestigious foreign universities. The following viewpoints were stated by participants:

“Internationalisation of higher education entails developing an internationalised curriculum, course, or international programme... .. for satisfying the needs of international students, not simply those from our own country. Furthermore, all other University services for those courses, including infrastructure, academic staff, student activities, teaching, and learning process management, and so on, must be harmonised and supported.” (*Interviewee 5, University 5*)

“Define it as international, multicultural, and global perspectives that we're attempting to implement through universities, research, and corporate activities. So, it's all about internationalisation and how we include it into our curriculum, as well as options for mobility. And right now, the theme that's resonating loudly is looking at environmental sustainability.” (*Interviewee 8, University 8*)

According to the perspectives expressed above, internationalisation is specifically defined as having an internationalised curriculum for both domestic and international students. Furthermore, internationalisation of higher education is defined as the incorporation of an international and intercultural dimension into traditional programme content.

Second, the mobility of institutional stakeholders is seen as an indicator of higher education internationalisation. Most participants viewed internationalisation in this area as the movement of domestic students and personnel. For example:

“Internationalisation of higher education is reflected in the way that students can go to study overseas in their final year after completing their initial phase within two or three years in the UK.” (*Interviewee 10, University 10*).

Others equated higher education internationalisation with a friendly environment for international students. This was evident in many of the participants’ responses to the presence of overseas students on the university campus. One of the participants, for example mentioned:

“Internationalisation of higher education means to integrate into the educational system of other countries. Our university will become a place where international students can come to study regardless of their countries of origin”. (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

Third, higher education internationalisation is defined as the variety of collaborative inter-institutional programmes in all areas of higher education. One of the participants, for example, shared their understanding based on their own experiences:

“Internationalisation of higher education is about co-supervising Ph.D. students, publishing international articles or scientific research results, organizing joint academic activities, exchanging faculty staff and students.” (*Interviewee 13, University 13*)

Some respondents defined internationalisation of higher education as a university's ability to be recognised globally and achieve high rankings. One of respondents stated:

“Internationalisation is the ability to gain the recognition from other universities in the region and the world. This recognition is shown in the university's ranking order. Therefore, if the universities would like to have a high-ranking position, they must comply with international criteria for research and teaching.” (*Interviewee 4, University 4*)

Furthermore, internationalisation is seen as a way for people to aid one another for mutual gain and long-term development. One participant, for example, characterised internationalisation as follows:

“Internationalisation is the international collaboration in the fields of teaching and research between countries. It must bring mutual benefits not only for the developing countries but also for the developed nations. In other words, all parties involved in this process should share a genuine equality to achieve mutually beneficial and reciprocal targets.” (*Interviewee 9, University 9*)

Furthermore, internationalisation is seen as an irreversible trend in higher education development in the context of globalisation and environmental sustainability, as well as preparing students for global competitiveness, according to an interviewee from university 5.

“In the coming time, internationalisation of education is necessary, as the economy now, if you want to grow, you want to compete, you must integrate, and of course, that is international integration. So, it's all things to do with internationalisation and how we work that through our curriculum to mobility opportunities. And the theme that's coming through quite strongly now is looking at environmental sustainability. It's also about preparing our students to compete in the global competition and creating that sense of growth.” (*Interviewee 5, University 5*)

Table :4.2 Interview Data Summary – Question 1

Interviews	Meaning of internationalisation (Indicators)								
	Student Recruitment	Student and Staff Exchange	Partnerships	Ranking and global Impact	Curriculum Internationalisation	Research and Publications	Diversity	Community	Sustainability / Growth and Development
University 1									
University 2									
University 3									
University 4									
University 5									
University 6									
University 7									
University 8									
University 9									
University 10									
University 11									
University 12									
University 13									

4.1.2 Key drivers and rationale for internationalisation in higher education in the UK

All the participants mentioned that their universities have an internationalisation strategy. Most participants believe that internationalisation has an impact and effect on the quality and development of teaching, learning, and research. One of the participants exemplifies this point of view as:

“The internationalisation of higher education fosters the sustainable development of the university. It makes the educational quality better, the research quality better, meeting all the quality standards for educational

institutions at national and international level. The overall purpose is to improve the educational quality of the whole institution.” (*Interviewee-11, University-11*)

The data from the participants demonstrated a wide range of benefits when it comes to international collaboration on academic programmes. One of the participants gave the following example:

“We are just going to the through the strategy. We've got Malaysia, Singapore key locations where we're delivering teaching..... There are two major factors to consider. International student mobility and the development of TNES are two of the most important aspects of TNES. The third reason is that we want to increase our global standings. Worldwide graduates, global relationships, global research, and global impact are the four pillars that underlie our current international approach.”. (*Interviewee 4, University 4*)

The findings of the interviews suggest another motivation for internationalisation in the UK universities , which is centred on research and knowledge generation, as seen through the eyes of the participants. Some participants stated that internationalisation allows the university to engage in international scientific collaboration and to publish internationally when collaborating with counterparts at world-class institutions.

This finding demonstrates that international research collaboration not only helps academics advance their academic profiles and share their academic successes with the rest of the world, but it also helps the institution's overall competency, reputation, and ranking. Participants who agreed with this point of view also discussed the advantages of international research collaboration on academic programmes. They emphasised the importance of research in producing employable graduates with high-quality learning outcomes. The following comments represent the perspectives of the participants:

“Internationalisation of higher education not only helps our institution to become a centre of scientific technology where people around the world can come and do research but also innovate the degree programmes to meet the needs of society.” (*Interviewee 6, University 6*)

The data from the interviewees suggest a different justification for internationalisation in the UK universities: one that focuses on gaining access to new information and technology. One interviewee explained this as follows:

“As I said, the internationalisation of higher education facilitates the favourable condition for the lecturers to access the world’s advanced knowledge, curriculum, teaching, and research methodology to improve professional quality of faculty. If the students participate in international cooperative activities, they can gain international experience for their better future employment.” (*Interviewee 3, University 3*)

Participants who agreed with this viewpoint also stated that international credentials are required for obtaining and retaining a faculty position. The findings of the interviews also reveal another educational relevance, emphasising the link between internationalisation and increased university competitiveness on a national, regional, and global scale.

The economic logic underpins efforts in this study to improve the human resources/capital required for a country to remain internationally competitive and to foster collaboration and brain gain. Three individuals' perspectives, for example, exemplify this motivation:

“Whether the learning output can compete in the international labour market is the most important matter. As you can see, the primary mission of the university is to help the learners to participate in the international labour market. If the university does not participate in international integration, it will not catch up with the updated knowledge of science and technological innovation. Thus, the University must join in the international integration to help the learners not only to be able to work within the nation but also in the foreign countries. Now mostly we have just focused on staff development, made the most of the government funding, providing high-quality human resources to meet the sustainable

socio-economic development, building research collaborations, providing scholarships to have brain gain.” (*Interviewee 5, University 5*)

The financial benefits are exemplified in most of the participants’ expectations, for example:

“We also pay attention to the financial benefit, however, the currently we have not had any international cooperative programmes that bring us financial benefit; it is only mutually beneficial for both sides. However, that does not mean we do not care ... That means our goal is for educational quality development first.” (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

According to the preceding example, the participants had a financial stake in internationalisation. In other words, financial assistance is regarded as an essential component of their internationalisation efforts. Most of the participating UK universities, however, do not consider economic reasoning to be one of their primary goals.

According to the findings of this study, this viewpoint prioritises learning foreign languages and cultures, preserving national culture, and respecting diversity. As an example, interviewee 8 made the following statement:

“We commit to providing students with basic knowledge of cultural theories and methods of cultural studies, basic and systematic knowledge of the elements and aspects of culture. In my opinion, the reason that

internationalisation is important is because we need to have a product that meets the requirement of the development of our country and the region.”

(Interviewee 8, University 8)

This rationale emphasises the promotion and protection of national and cultural identity.

To summarise, the majority of research participants felt that their universities needed to become more international. Participants who agreed with this viewpoint stated that internationalisation of higher education in the UK was a pressing need because it was viewed as a critical issue for the survival of a university. One of the participants made the following remark:

“In my opinion, internationalisation of higher education will be a likelihood of survival for a university. That would mean if the university still maintained the traditional way of thinking, then inevitably the university won't develop, and gradually it will become weaker and wither. BREXIT and Covid -19 has and will make a negative impact on bringing international students on the campus.” *(Interviewee 12, University 12)*

Data from interview participants also suggested that improving human resources was seen as a key element for advancing internationalisation. The necessity for professional development through various types of internationalisations was stressed by several interview participants. In the face of global competition, the education system has played a critical role in addressing societal requirements,

assisting the UK's economic success, and strengthening national capacities.

According to another interviewee:

“Internationalisation is the need to meet the demands of society. The actual social need here is to meet the demand of internationalised economic life rather than just within the local or national context. There many economic treaties signed between UK and other countries. Therefore, the improvement of the quality of education to meet the social demands of the workforce is one of the decisive factors.” (*Interviewee 7, University 7*)

Most participants agreed that there are a variety of causes and motives for a university to internationalise. The majority of respondents said that generating revenue and attracting a diverse population of students from various cultures and backgrounds are the main factors that lead to a university's aims, and objectives being met. The following remarks highlight the participating universities' internationalisation drivers:

“Want student diversification. So, a good range of students from different countries, different cultures. There's income generation. Yeah, well, that that's important. And the ability to network for research is critical as well. So having a global research network is very important and the partnerships we develop allow that to happen.” (*Interviewee 2, University 2*).

Other key findings also mention that there is a high degree of awareness about exposure of students to individuals from multiple cultures and backgrounds. Concerns about social justice issues were raised in relation to the curriculum. In addition, UK universities see decolonisation as an issue that must be addressed.

According to the findings, a university international strategy is supported by four pillars: global graduates, global partnerships, global research, and global impact.

There is a high level of understanding among participants of the changing pace of technology and its integration. Strategies for staff development in the use of technology must be included in universities’ mission statements.

Table:4.3 Summary of the findings

Interviews	Key drivers and rationale for internationalisation in higher education in the UK												
	Staff and Student Development	Partnerships and TNEs	Reputation and Recognition	Rankings and global Impact	Curriculum Internationalisation	Culture exchange	Financial and economic Benefits	Brain Gain	Quality and learning outcomes	Diversity	Research	Social Impact	Sustainability
University 1													
University 2													
University 3													
University 4													
University 5													
University 6													
University 7													
University 8													
University 9													
University 10													
University 11													
University 12													
University 13													

4.1.3 Agenda and mechanisms adopted to drive internationalisation in UK universities

All participants agreed on what the key themes of internationalisation are. Three of the participants mentioned that these themes are in line with their university's strategic plan. All of the university interviewees agreed that student and staff mobility was regarded as the most important theme for internationalisation. One participant, for example, stated:

“Graduate international students. One of the key themes both inward and outward students and staff. With us global partnerships are a big theme Both strategic partnerships, which are top-down research led partnerships than TNE partnerships, which is the area we're developing.” (*Interviewee 11, University 11*)

Building partnerships with domestic and international institutions is an important part of internationalisation, as demonstrated by the preceding statement. A few respondents also mentioned difficulties in forming partnerships, due to restrictive policies and legal issues, and they see language barriers or cultural differences as the most important factor that UK universities must consider.

Another important theme is making a global impact and forming research partnerships, which aid in forming a brand identity and obtaining a high QS ranking. One participant made the following remarks:

“Then global research will be another key strand for us and the global impact in terms of our ranking and global brand. And then we have all of our exchange partnerships with a range of different European universities. And then we have all of our exchange partnerships with a range of different European universities.” (*Interviewee 9, University 9*)

In addition, one of the respondents said that alumni partnerships are a key topic in the process of internationalisation, allowing the institution to attract more international students and employees, which is also related to a university’s economic and financial success. During this interview, the following statement was recorded:

“One is to stay connected with our global alumni as well. And that network can bring a whole different type of variety of different benefits to both of them in nine countries that they're from it to attract international students, attract international staff. And then really, again, I think it's a really strong agenda.” (*Interviewee-10, University-10*)

The growth agenda was a fundamental theme that embraced all aspects of internationalisation. Interviewee 2 explained this:

“We need more and more students. We may need more international students as partners. We need more research funding. We need more students coming to us on exchange programmes. We want more visiting scholars who have become for several months and work with us on

research projects. We need more doctoral students. So absolutely is. I'm simple. Growth agenda, wherever. However, whoever is getting more of what we do.” (Interviewee 2, University 2)

Creating an effective curriculum and offering the best teaching and learning experience for students were two other significant themes expressed by the participants. Staff and student development programmes are critical within the internationalisation process.

Summary of the findings question 3

Table :4.4

Interviews	Agenda and mechanisms adopted to drive internationalisation in UK universities									
	Resource Management	Inward and outward Mob	Partnerships	Rankig and global Impact	Growth	Effective Curriculum	Alumini	External Stakeholders	Relations with Communit	Research Collaborations
University 1										
University 2										
University 3										
University 4										
University 5										
University 6										
University 7										
University 8										
University 9										
University 10										
University 11										
University 12										
University 13										

4.1.4 Strategies, measures, and the implementation process in Internationalisation of Higher Education practices in the UK

Because of the many facets of higher education internationalisation in the UK, several approaches have more than one dimension. The strategy is considered as vital for a university's identity and how the institution considers itself as a competitor in the world marketplace, according to most participants.

In other words, the strategy is seen as a reflection of the university's image and how it wishes to project that image to prospective international students. The strategy is the result of the realisation that in order to keep foreign student numbers as a single drive, a formal document demonstrating expertise in the international student market is required. The following remarks from key informants highlight the strategies implemented:

“It wasn't just enough to recruit people, when people got here you also have to have the right sort of services and support. So, the international office had produced several documents really analysing the situation so there had been discussion at the university executive and so on, some discussion around issues of the rising of internationalisation. The students' experience and strategy committee had also produced some papers arguing we needed a stronger international strategy.” (*Interviewee 4, University 4*)

Four participants mentioned the strategy as a formalised reflection of research and the research community's diversity. One participant, for example, stated:

“I think this is to ensure that we’ve already got diversity in terms of the population of researchers, academic postgraduates, postdoctoral... to get the best wherever they come from. So, I think in terms of internationalisation, the strategy itself is not dictating, it’s a matter of ensuring that we’re achieving the best possible population of researchers that we can, but in a sense, it’s formalised by the international strategy because it’s saying we want to have that diversity.” (*Interviewee 13University 13*)

According to the quotation above, diversity in terms of where researchers emerge from is also about recruiting the "best" researchers, regardless of nationality. Given how easy it is to find people of a single nationality, the question here is whether having the best researchers allows for such diversity.

On the other hand, one participant stated that an internationalisation strategy justifies certain university activities. The following are some of the responses from the participants:

“I think a lot formally laid out strategy gives it a bit more authority than if it’s not a formally set out strategy. Whether it changes people’s individual behaviour significantly I’m not sure because I think everyone has been aware of the international dimension of what we do whether we have a

strategy or don't have a strategy, but certainly having a strategy makes it easier to justify things like international exchange programmes or taking international students.” (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

One participant stated that their university's internationalisation strategy emerged because of a few key drivers. The following suggestions were made:

“The national policy...the pursuit of privatisation, multi-dimensional approaches, the collaborative agreements have been made, the obvious financial need to recruit overseas students and generate external research, so it's the changing context which is driving a lot of this.” (*Interviewee 2, University 2*)

When discussing the internationalisation strategy, the term "multi-dimensional" appears to refer specifically to partnerships and students, international students, and home students. Most respondents also believe that by implementing the policy, the gap between these two groups of students will be bridged, as well as the university community as a whole, emphasising the importance of internationalisation and cross-cultural engagement.

Others, on the other hand, see the university's strategy as an incomplete document because it does not prescribe instruments for action and no follow-up appears to be indicated:

“There is nothing wrong with the strategy, but it’s still very abstract, and it’s not instrumentalised...Most people say ‘yeah I accept that’, but I think it’s more important to make something of the strategy, challenge those in charge of the strategy to put instruments in place...Does the expected level now understand that us, academic staff reading this strategy, that we will follow that?...Strategy is the beginning and if you endorse that, take the next step, and the next step is: what is the university going to offer to support staff and students to follow this strategy.” (*Interviewee 9University 9*)

In terms of strategies and metrics, all the respondents are focused on international student recruitment via TNEs and Partnerships. There is also widespread agreement and a strong emphasis on research collaborations and exchange programmes.

A few participants, on the other hand, describe marketing as a central and embedded strategy for the university, such as within 'other' strategies:

"We haven't written down 'this is what we're going to do.'" In truth, the marketing strategy is nearly entirely contained within the teaching and learning strategy, research strategy, mission strategy, and research relations strategy. The top-level stuff, I believe, is branding and positioning, which is the whole marketing plan. So, what the university truly wants to be and where we see itself in the next 5-15 years, and a lot

of that, as well as marketing strategy, has to do with how markets evolve again." (*University 7, Interviewee 7*)

It was interesting to hear about the international localisation strategy, which helped to increase the number of students, as well as funding and global ranking, for example:

“Well, to the international student growth, we’ve got a particular project that's running at the moment called International Step Change and..... that's got ten work packages associated with it, and that is the implementation strategy for that particular strand of the international localisation strategy. It is doing two parts of that work for us in terms of implementing the research, global research. Our learning and teaching committee to make sure that our mobility programmes are embedded in the curriculum and the quality audited and controlled, and the same would be for our TNE development as well.” (*Interviewee 10, University 10*)

Other major themes mentioned in strategy implementation included work and study abroad, collaboration with international institutions and organisations, research development, and partnership building, as stated by one of the participants:

“So, there is a requirement on programs in the right way, approval to address the issues. Decolonisation is the creation of international investigation through them. We have a study abroad and work abroad,

elements of policies in place which operations source of potential partners overseas for our students and vice versa to bring students into us. And we have a kind of partnership that manages our international franchise operation, and we have a policy that will practice around the development preparations, around research and the development of postgraduate programs.” (*Interviewee 5, University 5*)

Another strategy used by one of the universities was the recruitment and expansion of the international department, as well as increasing the budget for internationalisation activities and increasing and building personal relationships.

One participant made the following statement:

“We may need more international students as partners. We need more research funding. We need more students coming to us on exchange programs. We want more visiting scholars who have become for several months and work with us on research projects. We need more doctoral students to get our wrath up. (*Interviewee 6, University 6*)

Other findings included the importance of vision and mission, national policies, having an overseas agent, cultures, and leadership in internationalisation implementation.

Table :4.5 Summary of the findings

Interviews	Strategies, measures, and the implementation process in Internationalisation of Higher Education practices in the UK										
	Various committees	surveys and feedbacks	diversity of students and staff	exchange programs	research and collaboration	partnerships and collaborations	multi dimension (Home and international students)	activities (marketing , L&D , Growth Strategies)	Relations with Community	localisation (funding arrangements)	international department
University 1											
University 2											
University 3											
University 4											
University 5											
University 6											
University 7											
University 8											
University 9											
University 10											
University 11											
University 12											
University 13											

4.1.5 Resources for Internationalisation advancement in Higher Education in the UK

All the participants mentioned having a department in charge of internationalisation. Most also said that this department is organised into sub-departments that are responsible for aspects such as partnerships, student recruitment, research, placement, and student support:

“We have an international development office which manages student recruitment and student mobility. And then we have a separate academic partnerships office which manages the TNE partnerships and those strategic partnerships that they do, both UK based partnerships as well as international. So those two offices, both set within are marketing, recruitment, and international directorate. Yeah. So, we have this single umbrella directorate. We also have a separate admissions department which works alongside TNE and digital marketing, which contributes to that. So, now I think we're quite well resourced. But we are exploring a restructuring process, so that might change a little bit. We must go through the consultation phase for that.” (*Interviewee 3, University 3*)

Like the preceding statement, other respondents mentioned restructuring the department, making changes to the process, and recruiting new staff due to a lack of stability and with the aim of meeting global competition. The following statement highlighted some resource-related issues:

“And that is me and my team involved in it, partnerships and the international recruitment team. We have recruited a director for that role and that person will start in May. So, we will have a dedicated international department. I've only been there five years and I've been in our department. I've been a director. I've been in a department. I've been in and directorate. There is a lack of stability, certainly within my institution” (*Interviewee 11, University 11*)

Others also mentioned that a lack of funding in the international department is a challenge. This statement reflects the challenges encountered:

“And I think that is reflective of a lack of focus on the internationalisation agenda with that appointment last night of the pro vice chancellor international. He is working at a level, and he has authority to get people and to get money. So, I am optimistic that things are going to change very dramatically because I have been so sort of, you know, trying to run along with quite a small budget, quite a small t that both of those have expanded quite significantly. Probably going to take about it 10 months before you see the results of that.” (*Interviewee-7, University -7*)

Five respondents also mentioned having an international department, but believe it is under-resourced to meet global competition and the institution's strategy.

The following comments reflect the perspectives of some key informants:

“We are now. But I think in terms of the ambition of the strategy, you know, for the whole universities, how its nationalisation embedded and to have the global outlook and all the things we're trying to do, I think probably we could do with a table resource where we have even said that in university. But it's all it's all a question of the ambition and the scale at the kind of timescales over how quickly they want this.” (*Interviewee 8, University 8*)

There was also mention of a lack of clarity and the absence of a strong leadership position in two institutions. Disagreements between academic staff and international departments were also mentioned by respondents.

Promotion was mentioned by all participants as important for recruiting international students, building partnerships, improving global rankings, and creating brand image. Connecting overseas agents for international student recruitment was one of the most common findings. As one of the participants indicated, most promotion is done online and through the international departments:

“If we want to promote outbound student mobility opportunities, the Go Global team will run a profile-raising event across our campuses. They'll do social media campaigns.” (*Interviewee 9, University 9*)

Two respondents also stated that student surveys aid in promotion and understanding of what they require, which aids in the improvement of internationalisation in the UK universities. For example, one participant said:

“They'll do survey surveys of students to find out what students want, what type of programs, where in the world they want to have them. They'll also work with the academic staff to develop programs that the staff want to see embedded in the curricula. And then in terms of in student recruitment, yes, we work with a global network of agencies, and we also have the articulation partnerships that act as a pathway.” (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

There was also a strong emphasis on promoting international activities through scholarships and scholarship bodies. One respondent, for example, mentioned that:

“We work through, the agents we've got sort of sponsorship bodies, government sponsored scholarship bodies, that extra through movement. those are the other main roots vein, business partners to achieve the recruitment.” (*Interviewee 12, University 12*)

A few interviewees also mentioned that alumni play an important role in promoting and bringing in new students to the UK, and that they assist them in the pre-departure process. The following comments reflect the perspectives of some key informants:

“I think the alumni have quite a significant role to play. I think that alumni can be involved in, um, different activities. They can talk about those experiences. They can help with pre-departure visits; they can help with doing presentations. so I think they can help them on many different levels., and at the end of the day, I think that, you know, students are prospective students, and their parents like to hear from alumni because, you know, they might be, you know, same nationality the same way. Talk about that experience from the same cultural perspective as well. So, I think alumni, there's a, there's a power tool to alumni on involving alumni in the process.”

(Interviewee 4, University 4)

Other responses referenced research and TNE collaboration once again. In addition, the institutional vision and strategy play an important role in promoting partnerships and raising university rankings.

Table :4.6 Summary of the findings

Interviews	Resources for Internationalisation advancement in Higher Education in the UK												
	international department	placement and student sup	senior leadership	marketing department	research and collaboration	partnership and TNE	Staff and trainings	Separate budget	Relations with external part	campings and activities	student and staff developm	Scholarship bodies	alumni
University 1													
University 2													
University 3													
University 4													
University 5													
University 6													
University 7													
University 8													
University 9													
University 10													
University 11													
University 12													
University 13													

4.1.6 Leadership support in the process of internationalisation in UK

Higher Education

Leadership, according to all the participants, had a critical role in formalising and implementing an internationalisation strategy. Several participants said that the leadership in the international office is highly helpful and that they are driving internationalisation across departments by encouraging initiatives such as research, student recruitment, partnerships, and collaborative projects. One responder, for example, stated:

“The vice chancellor is personally involved two chairs, the International Strategy Board, which report and to the senior management team. So, there's direct leadership from the vice chancellor. We are looking to appoint a PVC international very shortly. So that person will take over the chair of the International Strategy Board. So, yes, we have strong leadership. We also have a PVC education minister who chairs the International Step Change Board, which is responsible for driving the international student growth. So, it has very senior support. The heads of colleges are all supportive of the project as well. So, it's looking quite good.” (*Interviewee 10, University 10*)

One participant also emphasised the department heads and vice chancellors sponsoring and participating in numerous student societies and festivals that

promote connection and communication between students and the institution. The following remarks demonstrate the leadership at the chosen university:

“So, we've got representation., do a lot with our students, society, science and social sciences. So, they play an active role in that. So, we have a spring festival gala. and you can always see the pro vice chancellor with, some extensive institution. So, there's visibility and, sort of interaction with our students. So, a very important thing that we have to focus on.”

(Interviewee 6, University 6)

Furthermore, as stated by Interviewee 11 below, the findings imply that leadership aids in the development and support of partnerships, exchange programmes, and pedagogy exchange.

“Also, overseas trips promoting the university overseas e set up, new partnerships overseas research for or teaching and learning. The senior staff broadly, engaged. So, for example, we have a, a partner institution in China we work with. We do quite a lot as an institution with staff exchange and exchange of curriculum, collectively and individual support to grow our internationalisation. *(Interviewee 11, University 11)*

A few respondents also stated that current leadership is ineffective in meeting expectations, and that they are establishing a team and appointing new leadership roles to keep up with global competitiveness. One responder, for example, stated:

“The way it works has been working is that we have a, um, deputy vice chancellor who been operating as a lead for internationalisation. But we have appointed a non-academic or non-PVC, to meet the global requirements and competition. As we don’t find it effective, this person who is gone, who will carry the vice president's international title for international matters, not for other matters before international masters. So we do have, some, member of the university executive who will be undertaking that role in future.” (*Interviewee 9, University 9*)

According to the above statement, the leadership must be knowledgeable and experienced in both teaching and non-teaching tasks.

4.1.7 Challenges encountered in implementing internationalisation agenda in UK universities

Because of the changing environment, more competition, and more awareness, all the respondents said that they had encountered a few challenges in the process of internationalisation. For example, meeting the expectations of staff and students was cited as a major issue. The following remarks demonstrate the difficulties encountered in implementing the internationalisation agenda at one participating university:

“Challenges have been founded in attempting to implement your internationalisation agenda and managing expectations in terms of the speed of growth. Everyone wants everything to happen immediately. And trying to sort of map things out across a time to manage expectations and allowing enough lead time for us to look at data about portfolio and to benchmark ourselves to make the decisions about which courses to invest in and promote and recruit students on to.” (*Interviewee 4, University 4*)

“So, I think that's the biggest challenge is the managing expectations. And then, you know, it's so competitive in the world. It's trying to find the appropriate way. Well, we've got good ways of promoting ourselves, but it's, you know, that conversion in terms of how to persuade students that they'd have the best academic experience of living experience with us rather than somewhere else.” (*Interviewee 7, University 7*)

One respondent, on the other hand, believes that the global strategy document is open to different interpretations by different people, resulting in diverse interpretations and, as a result, varying levels of commitment to it. The following was said by one of the participants.

“I think that internationalisation means different things to different people. So as a university’s international strategy, the way I read it may be very different from the way you read it, and that might be totally different from people in engineering and maths and pharmacology and different issues for modern languages. So, in that sense, the other dimension I think that comes in is partly the operationalisation of the strategy, but at the same time, considering the different needs and wishes of staff and students across departments.” (*Interviewee 10, University 10*)

Furthermore, three respondents stated that the main challenge to internationalisation in the UK universities is a lack of mixing among people of different nationalities and cultural differences. As an illustrative example,

“I do think that international groups, whether they’re British, German, French, or overseas, will tend to congregate with their own, and I think that’s the biggest factor that internationalisation actually has to get over.” (*Interviewee-5, University -5*)

Many respondents also mentioned the difficulties that some academics may face when teaching and dealing with international students. They believe that those academics should be given more assistance. Participants made the following remarks:

“Maybe some of the academics that have been here for a long time and find teaching international students a problem, you know, a lot of work needs doing around awareness, I think. If you’ve got somebody that’s been used to, you know, they understand British students and how to teach them, and suddenly they’ve got a class that’s the majority international students, they are not coping very well with that kind of change, and they need help with that I think as well.” (*Interviewee 9, University 9*)

“We’re trying to take a holistic approach. I mean, obviously, you don’t do this kind of work unless you embrace the whole ethos. It’s fair to say there are a lot of people on campus who, I wouldn’t say resist it, but just don’t see it as particularly important. And always when you’re looking to do outreach activities, it’s the people who are not embracing the idea that are the most important ones, otherwise you end up doing the same sessions for the same people and preaching to the converted.”. (*Interviewee 6, University 6*)

One of the respondents also cited an interesting issue of 'resistance to change' as one of the challenges given by the international approach, for example, the following comments:

“There will be some people uncomfortable with it... something we do have to recognise is there was an implication for the university making sure that we... international people who come to [this university] whether they're students, staff, whatever, actually feel welcome in [this university] and, sort of, you know, helping the culture of the city as well, recognising this is an international university.” (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

Almost all participants mentioned cost and economic issues, such as funding being a major challenge and believing that the strategy comes at a price that the university must be able to bear, and that a more global mindset is required to think outside the box and be able to sell a university to the rest of the world. This viewpoint could be regarded as showing a conflict between the university's national mission or concentration and the internationalisation effort.

The main issue with the university's strategy, according to four of the UK universities, is related to the university's 'conservative' management structure and leadership, implying the 'business' nature of the university's identity, as stated by one of the participants:

“The university is structured on very conservative traditional lines and an international strategy...is dictated by its existing management structure,

and its existing management structure is...antiquated. I don't feel any sense of coordinated process that feeds back into the institution. There are lots of people going out doing work internationally. We never get to hear about what it is they're doing unless it's by chance, so the communication process... lots of individuals doing lots of individual work. I don't see how that pin back into a corporate strategy. If the corporate strategy is more students and higher ranking in the league tables, if that's all it is, then that's fine." (*Interviewee 13, University 13*)

A few interviewees also mentioned that increased academic pressure may be a barrier to internationalisation. They also believe that internationalisation and international strategy will result in a cultural shift in people's "ways of seeing and doing things," which may be resisted, for example:

"The other thing that I think will make it difficult is that, in essence, what's needed by all of us, in part anyway, is potentially the need to change our way of seeing things, and way of doing things, and to achieve cultural change. One of the barriers is that because staff working in higher education are most of the time working under a great deal of pressure, it's actually very hard for them to actually secure time to step back long enough to be able to reflect on what they're doing rather than just doing it." (*Interviewee 13, University 13*)

According to one respondent, resources are a barrier to the implementation of an internationalisation strategy:

“Resources is the other one obviously, student support services – do we have enough? Do people understand it? Cultural awareness, lots of different things which are likely to get in the way of this. It’s not something that’s going to happen overnight either. So, visions and statements and aims and aspirations are all very well, but I’m not sure just how realistic and what time scale we’re talking about”. (*Interviewee 3, University 3*)

Finding sponsorships and grants to recruit overseas students is vital, according to the research. Internationalisation could be boosted by including foreign curriculum, expanding staff exchange programmes, and collaborating on research projects. In recent years, government policies and environmental sustainability have become a key challenge.

Table :4.6 Summary of the findings

Interviews	Challenges encountered in implementing internationalisation agenda in UK universities													
	Resource management	Managing expectation	Growth and Competition	Benchmarking	Language and cultural bar	partnership and TNE	Leadership support	Separate budget	Awareness	Interest of staff	student and staff development	Cultural differences	University Strategy itself	Communication
University 1														
University 2														
University 3														
University 4														
University 5														
University 6														
University 7														
University 8														
University 9														
University 10														
University 11														
University 12														
University 13														

4.1.8 Different approaches of internationalisation strategies adopted by UK universities to meet competition

Some respondents said it was a difficult subject to discuss, since they had never considered how their university is different compared to other universities. However, one respondent claimed that location is a differentiator, and that marketing and attracting students is simple for them.

These opinions are summed up in the following remarks:

“That's quite a difficult thing that everyone does such a lot of good work. So, I think in terms of inward students, the one thing that we have that very few others have is a wonderful location by the sea. And so, we use that a lot of student experience it as very positive feature. And we do a lot of location-based marketing. The visuals and things. So, I guess that's the key differentiator for us is that, you know, we're a university on the beach, but we have a very good work life balance that kind of that we support, and we offer good graduate employment opportunities as well. So, you know, without going into lots of detail, that's you know, if we've if we were to pick one or two key difference and make it different, then that would be it”. (*Interviewee 12, University 12*)

Six institutions stated that the ability to find work after graduation was the most important aspect in allowing students to choose their desired institution. For example, Interviewee 1 stated:

“We have a very strong emphasis on employability. And what we do, we tend to choose partners overseas who work in the same way. We're also very interested in the employability of our graduates. So, we tend to seek partners in not just in terms of mission and values. So that would certainly be one thing. I think all universities will now approach internationalisation as a joint operation between not just student recruitment but also research and rankings.” (*Interviewee 1, University 1*)

Another factor was research facilities, which attracted more students and employees to some universities due to their high ranking for this. Focusing on graduate results, employability possibilities, and assistance, as well as having multiple campuses in various places and university accreditation, distinguishes their institutions from others. A statement was made by one respondent:

“We have different research strengths and areas of interest. So, our location in terms of building, when viewed from a national perspective, and I believe one of our key things that we do well, I believe we can differentiate on going forward in our careers path. We now provide employability assistance for internships, work experience, CVs, career fairs, and interview techniques. Once you're a student, and they're ready to leave, when they graduate, we ranked highly in quite a few timbales for our careers part, and we play them to support them. And this is a critical agenda for students, particularly in the Asian market. How will they help them get

a job? And I think they will point to differentiation. It's our research strengths. And then we've got campuses in Singapore, Malaysia. These are all points of differentiation. I think all our business school as triple accredited and lots of business schools aren't here. I know that's not unique. It's still a differentiation point.” (Interviewee 7, University 7)

Table:4.6 Summary of the findings

Interviews	Different approaches of internationalisation strategies adopted by UK universities to meet competition									
	location and Access	placement opportunities	partnerships	research	Rankings	Career affis and activities	campuses at various locations	reputation and global presence	student experinece	work life balance
University 1										
University 2										
University 3										
University 4										
University 5										
University 6										
University 7										
University 8										
University 9										
University 10										
University 11										
University 12										
University 13										

4.7 Summary of the key findings emerging from in-depth interviews

Meaning of Internationalisation:

- Internationalisation is viewed as a broad range of international policies and programs that must be promoted.
- Internationalisation is associated with the ability of students to study or work abroad for placement periods and prepare them to engage with others in the global labour market and academic communities to meet the global competition.
- Understandings of internationalisation of higher education focus on the internationalisation of a curriculum, teaching and research collaborations, establishing partnerships with other universities both at home and abroad, and developing strong relationships with overseas agents and alumni.

Rationale and Drivers for Internationalisation

- To improve educational quality and research quality, to develop and innovate curriculum, and to build human resource capacity.
- To promote national culture and values along with brain gain.
- Increasing international visibility and reputation; gaining access to new knowledge and technology; increasing competitiveness; and promoting intercultural awareness and mutual understanding.
- To meet national economic demand; to build partnerships and TNES; to develop and innovate the curriculum; to increase research profile and collaborations and build TNES and partnerships; to meet global challenges and match the pace of change in technology.
- Acknowledgement of income and mission should be the key drivers for internationalisation, aligned with national policies.
- Boost rankings.

- Significant emphasis given to partnerships such as exchange of students and staff mobility.

Key Mechanisms to drive international

- Higher number of international students from partners, more research funding and more students coming to exchange programs are among the key intentions of the universities.
- It is observed that there is emphasis on co-operative research and connections with global alumni.
- It is observed that high significance is given to brand awareness and international collaborations. Presence of a global research network is regarded highly, and partnerships are encouraged.
- Significance is given to diversity, and it is intended that this will result in students learning from each other and developing their network. There is acknowledgement about work being done on strategic level, however it is yet to be implemented.

Strategies, Measures and implementation process in internationalisation

- Financial support is critical to the successful implementation of an internationalisation strategy.
- Changes in Brexit and visa regulations are being carefully considered to provide opportunities.
- Unwavering support for international collaboration and recruitment. There is also a policy in place that promotes the growth of international corporations, research, and postgraduate programs.
- Allocating funds to meet well-defined targets demonstrates the university's well-directed approach.
- There is a lot of awareness about the availability of opportunities, but the process and being under-resourced are major roadblocks.
- There is unanimous agreement that alumni play an important role in attracting students, discussing their experiences, and assisting with presentations.
- There is agreement on the importance of utilising the global network of agents for inward student recruitment. Every year, the emphasis is on planning and resource management.

- The presence of a learning and teaching committee to ensure mobility program cohesion with curriculum while maintaining quality and control.

Resources for Internationalisation

- All the institutions have a dedicated international department. Funding is a major challenge in most of the institutions.
- Lack of clarity and recruitment process and less staff in the department causes challenge to meet the expectations.
- There is acknowledgement about the need for increase in dedicated resources. It is observed that the teams work in cohesion and awareness of recent trends like digital marketing is present.
- The strategic plan is not in line with the global competition. Absence of a specific department is handled but multiple teams that work in an agile fashion.
- Lack of focus on internationalisation.

Leadership and management support in the process of internationalisation

- Authorities in the top management like the pro vice chancellor have significant global exposure. Authorities like the pro vice chancellor and the chancellor are approachable and involve themselves among their interactions with the students and the staff.
- There is acknowledgement about leadership supporting overseas trips which have resulted in new partnerships and have contributed to teaching and learning
- A lack of clarity observed in the staff about the understanding of the requirements from board of governors.

Challenges encountered in implementing internationalisation agenda

- Understanding of international isolation agenda is identified to be a key challenge. The findings identify budget management and resource management as challenges during the promotions.
- Resource management, especially on the personnel front has been a concern for the university and there is awareness among the staff about it. This has impacted the work culture as the staff is quoted to be "demoralized".

- There is an agreement to realise the need of impact analysis. For example, some institutions seek to make gains without assessing the potential future implications and this can cause problems later.
- Cultural difference, communication, governance and understanding of the partners are identified as the key challenges faced by the university. The university also identifies rising competition as a challenge to face and expresses that the market has been very competitive. BREXIT may cause research partnerships to fall in volume.
- Preference of communication mediums is regarded as a hindrance, while collaborating among partners. Leadership focus and strategic planning is also regarded as a key challenge. The curriculum will not be internationalised, and attendance at this university will not provide an international experience. Individuals' resistance to and awareness of strategy is a burden.

Differentiation Approach compared to other universities.

- Reputation and ranking are considered to be a major differentiation element. Flexibility and responding according to a changing environment are observed.
- Strong emphasis on employability and choosing partners according to the needs. Location and research facilities are important.
- Offering programs overseas and exchange programs. Changing the curriculum according to needs.

All the responses under the foregoing ten themes have been discussed in the analysis in chapter 5.

Chapter 5 Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter describes and analyses the research findings in light of the relevant literature. The methodology described in chapter 3 goes into detail about data collection methods, procedures, and protocols.

The following research questions are being investigated in this study:

- RQ1 What is understood by the term ‘internationalisation’ in the context of higher education?
- RQ2 What strategies have institutions implemented to advance the internationalisation agenda?
- RQ3 What challenges have universities encountered in their drive to advance the internationalisation agenda?

The ten themes set out in chapter 4 have been consolidated into five themes. This has facilitated a sharper focus on common issues between the ten themes, while retaining their distinctive character. These five consolidated themes are:

- Perception of Internationalisation of Higher Education
- Rationale for Internationalisation of Higher Education
- Strategies and Implementation of Internationalisation
- Risks and Challenges of Internationalisation
- Obstacles to Implementing Internationalisation

Each of these five consolidated themes is discussed in turn below:

5.2 Perception of internationalisation concept of higher education in the UK

The perception of institutional stakeholders affects internationalisation within the practice of higher education. This is because any human action tends to be led by everyone's worldview, which is moulded and changed by their experiences, (Piaget, 1953). Because internationalisation implies different things to everyone, there is a wide range of meanings ascribed to the idea. (Knight, 2004; 2015; Soderqvist, 2002; Yang, 2002).

A review of the literature and interviews revealed that various authors had attempted to define and describe the internationalisation of higher education (Altbach, 2002; Altbach, Reisberg, and Rumbley, 2009; Jiang, 2008), which was particularly useful in understanding the processes. However, developing a definition with a shared, common understanding remains difficult (Cross et al., 2011; de Wit, 2013; Knight, 2012; Warwick, 2014).

The search for a definition within this thesis has drawn on a variety of sources, illustrating the breadth of conceptions of internationalisation. Despite a disputed origin, analysis has revealed that the number of definitions of internationalisation has been increasing (Scott, 1998; Altbach and Teichler, 2001; Teferra, 2008; Altbach and de Wit, 2015; de Wit, Deca, and Hunter, 2015). As these definitions have increased, there has been a corresponding widening of the scope of internationalisation within institutions. Also, there is a growing appreciation of

the tangible benefits to be achieved both by integrating across all institutional boundaries and by making similar inroads into wider external stakeholder communities.

Finally, there is no universally accepted definition; rather, there are numerous definitions and interpretations. As a result, increasing understanding of internationalisation is critical, because the concept has grown in scope with time and within different contexts.

Initially, each interviewee was asked a general question about what internationalisation of higher education means to them. After the interviews were conducted and analysed, the primary significant characteristics of the concept of internationalisation became apparent. Exploring perspectives on higher education internationalisation serves as a catalyst for revealing hidden elements behind the current practise of higher education internationalisation at UK universities.

Internationalisation has been included in university strategic goals and vision statements. This finding is consistent with the findings of Arabkheradmand, Shabani, Zand-Moghadam, Bahrami, Derakhshesh, and Golkhandan (2015), who claim that having a global vision for education and then applying this insight to all aspects of education is the factor that initiates an international trend in educational institutions. The findings of the empirical study conducted for this study sketched out intersecting and multifaceted dimensions of respondents'

understanding of higher education internationalisation. Their perspectives on internationalisation are divided into two widely accepted approaches in the literature: the activity approach and the rational approach (Knight, 2004, Knight & de Wit, 1995).

Many participants, according to the activity approach, see internationalisation of higher education in the UK as components covering activities, procedures, or strategies of their institution's internationalisation. This study supports previous research that connects higher education internationalisation to a minor component of globalisation (Altbach & Knight, 2007).

Respondents who take the rationale approach see the goal or rationale for facilitating international activities or programmes as the internationalisation of higher education. According to Zha (2003), these two approaches to defining internationalisation complement rather than exclude one another. Although neither perspective considers their interpretation of internationalisation of higher education to be a complete definition of the term, these findings send an important message to institutional stakeholders about what they should do and how critical internationalisation of higher education is to the survival and development of their higher education institution.

Higher education can be viewed as taking a variety of internationalisation forms that must be integrated into a university's core functions. These tangible and

visible aspects of university internationalisation are seen as critical drivers in implementing international cooperative programmes and activities.

The first understanding of higher education internationalisation in the UK is centred on curricular internationalisation. The infusion of an international and intercultural dimension into the traditional curriculum, or the adoption of a comprehensive package of joint degree-level programmes from famous foreign universities, was defined by participants who held this position.

Furthermore, in order to run an internationalised curriculum, all other related activities must also meet international standards. This strong emphasis on an internationalised curriculum, programme, or individual course in perceptions of 'internationalisation of higher education' is consistent with the literature (de Wit, 2011). According to the literature, the main component or backbone of institutional internationalisation is the internationalisation of the curriculum (Khorsandi, 2014). Furthermore, all other related activities must meet international standards in order to run an internationalised curriculum. This strong emphasis on an internationally oriented curriculum, programme, or individual course in perceptions of 'internationalisation of higher education' is consistent with the literature (de Wit, 2011). The internationalisation of the curriculum, according to the literature, is the main component or backbone of institutional internationalisation (Khorsandi, 2014). In other words, it has been proposed that

internationalisation of academic programmes is critical in the ongoing effort to internationalise UK universities.

Internationalisation of higher education in the UK is defined in this context as the incorporation of an international and intercultural dimension into the content of traditional programmes. This finding is consistent with Elkin et al. (2008), who proposed ways to internationalise programmes such as incorporating overseas ideas into domestic programmes, blending different cultural ideas, or even adapting international standards.

Internationalisation of UK universities can also be understood as the adoption of joint academic programmes from prestigious foreign universities. From this perspective, internationalisation is viewed as incorporating a range of different ways of internationalising the curriculum. (Luxon & Peelo, 2009).

Internationalisation of higher education in the UK can also be characterised as the movement of institutional stakeholders. Participants in this category described internationalisation as the inward and outward mobility of students and employees. The analysis demonstrates the internationalisation of higher education in terms of having international students on university campuses, which is consistent with the literature in emphasising the importance of international students in the university's development. This perception emphasised not only the rise in the number of international students, but also the extent and magnitude of

the phenomenon, which is not limited to a single region or continent, but rather operates on a much larger global scale (Teichler, 2004; Robson, 2011).

Higher education internationalisation can be defined as a wide range of programmes with international components. It includes even the most basic activities, such as cultural exchange programmes for students and faculty. It also contains:

- High-level commitment to the university's research mission; co-leading international research projects and
- Co-publishing the most recent scientific findings; or having articles published in prestigious international journals.

The finding reinforces de Haan's assertion that "the meaning of internationalisation includes everything related to international" (2014, p. 241).

The study analysis also identifies internationalisation of higher education in the UK as a university's ability to become known globally. The goal of internationalising higher education is to gain acceptance or recognition from the world's higher education systems. The analysis defines internationalisation of higher education as a university's goal of integrating into the global setting and global rankings. The underlying principle of this perception is the belief that internationalisation causes universities to become more internationalised by gaining international recognition.

It's worth mentioning that, rather than a series of milestones, this perspective on higher education internationalisation sees it as a process of transition from a national to an international institution. Increase the amount of collaborative academic programmes, research collaboration, and exchanges between the university and its overseas partners, for example, TNES. This finding is in line with Söderqvist's (2002), description of internationalisation of higher education as "a process of transitioning from a national to an international higher education institution, resulting in better teaching and learning quality and accomplishment of required skills" (p. 29).

Additionally, internationalisation can be considered as people supporting one another for mutual gain and promoting long-term development. This approach will need to be established on a large and detailed scale among partner institutions. In the sense that the international dimension of higher education should be founded on sharing, solidarity, and equality among partners, this viewpoint is consistent with the literature (Morosini, Corte, & Guilherme, 2017).

The study's findings also indicate that internationalisation of higher education in the UK is the most important strategy for achieving the desired growth of universities. Higher education internationalisation has become an essential policy response to the changing global context and the challenges of ever-increasing interconnectedness. Participants here saw internationalisation of higher education as primarily beneficial to the university's modernisation and development in order

for it to be recognised as one of the best universities in the country and around the world (Arabkheradmand et al., 2015).

Internationalisation can be defined as the establishment of networks connecting UK higher education to the wider world. According to this understanding, large foreign universities are currently offering partnerships and operations in the UK (London, 2011); thus, a university can take advantage of this opportunity to establish strategic cooperation with universities all over the world and education consultants from all over the world. This finding is in line with Marginson (2014), who emphasises the need of connecting and integrating an institution's inner, internal environment with the outer world during internationalisation. Global communication and information systems promote these connections, cooperation, and exchanges.

According to this viewpoint, internationalising higher education entails assimilating into the global mainstream. According to the study's findings, internationalisation of UK universities is a critical factor in bringing sustainability, innovation, and modernization to the economy and society. In this changing and interconnected world, the key concept emphasised in the study analysis is the recognition of universities' essential missions, and internationalisation is regarded as the cornerstone of nation building, as well as economic, social, and human development (Enders, 2004; as cited in Morosini et al., 2017).

In a nutshell, the analysis in this thesis presents the fundamental meaning of UK higher education internationalisation as it focuses on its process and goals. The conceptual idea of internationalisation of higher education was recorded in the participants' perspectives as both conceptual and applied strategies. This analysis agrees with de Wit's (2011), criticism which highlights the gap between conceptual definition and actuality. According to de Wit, the reality of internationalisation is far less favourable than conceptual definitions might imply.

5.3 Rationale for internationalisation of higher education in UK

universities

As presented in chapter 2, de Wit (1995), developed a framework of social/cultural, political, academic, and economic rationales for internationalisation in HEIs. Furthermore, many authors have written extensively about the rationale shifts within and between these four groups (Zha, 2003; Knight, 2004).

The role of economic, cultural, social, and political rationales is not disregarded in this study, despite the fact that they are interwoven rather than mutually exclusive. The reciprocal relationship between academic and economic rationales, for example, can be simply expressed by stating that international activities cannot be carried out without money or financial assistance. However, the primary purpose was to improve the quality of life rather than to gain profit. This finding is in line with Smith's (1994), assessment of the relationship between

internationalisation and higher education quality enhancement, as noted in de Wit (2002). For example, the university seeks worldwide contacts with famous foreign universities in order to meet this expectation.

The collaborative academic programmes are seen as an effective way for academic programmes to gain international recognition. These programmes, they believe, are designed not only to improve individual lessons, courses, or programmes, but also to gain international prestige or recognition. Moreover, the analysis shows that the universities' ambitions extend beyond these collaborative academic initiatives to enhance the quality of other national academic programmes. This finding is consistent with Knight's (2004), observation that internationalisation adds an international dimension to teaching, aids in quality improvement, and helps meet international academic standards.

Standardisation of the curriculum, supplementing of imported curriculum books and resources, expanded professional development opportunities, improved international and professional experience for teaching personnel, and improvement of local academic programmes were all highlighted in the report.

An analysis of the interviews indicates another justification for internationalisation in the participants' perspective, which is centred on research and knowledge generation. Universities around the country and in the area, all emphasise the need of developing new information in order to improve their research reputation. This research indicates that international research

collaboration not only allows academics to develop their careers, but also helps to improve the institution's general competency and reputation.

This result backs up Yang's (2002), argument that internationalisation gives universities, faculty members, and students a significant opportunity to participate in the global educational system. Indeed, such chance has significant value, as it aids in the acquisition of current scientific information across a wide variety of fields, as well as steering an institution in the proper way when it comes to authoring international papers or doing research (Tierney, 2004; Stromquist, 2007).

The interview analysis revealed yet another justification for internationalisation, this time centred on academic staff and students acquiring international professional competence. According to the participants' claims, international experiences gained through study, collaborate, or research can significantly improve people's international perspective and culturally diverse competency.

Following the analysis, there is a significant demand for the institution to provide additional exchange activities and cooperative programmes to assist students in furthering their professional knowledge and foreign language skills. This finding is in line with empirical study by Doyle (2013) and Kovacs (1997), who revealed that faculty members who participated in international activities, such as research, benefited greatly from them. These accomplishments include the development of innovative ideas, inspiration for continuing research projects, and valuable

possibilities to establish and maintain regular contact with colleagues in other nations.

This perspective represented the crucial function of internationalisation in improving academic staff qualification and capacity to international norms. Higher education's internationalisation is expected to provide more qualified personnel and, more significantly, a more prestigious reputation for the university. In the literature, internationalisation's contribution to intellectual and scholarly values has been thoroughly established (Childress, 2009; Rizvi & Lingard, 2010).

Another feature of educational importance that emerged from the interviews was emphasising the link between internationalisation and increased university competitiveness at the national, regional, and global levels. The concept that competitive capacity is crucial in determining other traits, such as regional or international reputation and standards, supports this position. This study backs up Altbach's (2004), hypothesis that people will become more aware of the global competitive environment.

The importance of achieving international position, reputation, and recognition was emphasised by interview participants. Adherence to international standards, competition with other institutions, and improving their ability to function globally and achieve reputability are all cited as advantages of internationalisation.

Gaining recognition as a high-quality institution, according to the report, is crucial since it will lead to a variety of good effects for the institution's development. It's worth noting that these anticipated benefits are intertwined and mutual. To begin, this conclusion is consistent with Knight's (2013), findings which defined this reason as an international hunt for ranking recognition. According to Knight (2013), universities should not halt their development processes in order to establish a name and a reputation that is respected by international higher education institutions.

Second, generating revenue, decreasing operational risks and dangers, and gaining resources for operations on the home institutions are all economic motives for internationalisation (Knight, 2004). The economic rationale underpins attempts to improve the human resources/capital needed for the country to remain competitive internationally. The purpose of these initiatives is to give students with a space where they may work together to learn more about the world and its social, cultural, political, and economic challenges (Salaberri, & Sánchez-Pérez, 2017).

Not only was internationalisation deemed necessary, but the majority of higher education leaders polled agreed that their universities require a plan to effectively internationalise.

Integration of the economy, society, and culture necessitates an entirely new set of societal attitudes and ideas. The free trade market emphasises competition for

skilled and professional labour. Understanding and applying international knowledge and abilities is crucial for institutional stakeholders, notably students and teachers. To put it another way, financial assistance is viewed as a vital aspect in assisting their internationalisation efforts. Some universities, on the other hand, are not motivated solely by economic considerations when it comes to higher education internationalisation.

Third, cultural and social motives are critical for preserving national identities, cultural variety, and counteracting globalisation's homogenising impacts (Hawawini,2011). The cultural social reasoning is founded on the concept that "globalisation's homogenising consequences" must be resisted, and that national cultures and linguistics must be respected(Knight, 1977, p.11). This perspective, according to the findings of this study, places a premium on studying international languages and cultures, protecting national culture, and valuing diversity.

Intercultural awareness and reciprocal understanding, according to the findings, are crucial success markers in all international interactions. Exchange programmes can be implemented through a variety of activities with international partners. Both universities profit from these programmes since they increase their cultural knowledge.

Finally, Zha (2003), links the category of agenda to issues such as stability, peace, ideological stance, and protection via mutual resource sharing. According to research, internationalisation collaboration between their educational

establishment and its counterparts in other countries would strengthen mutually supportive partnerships. According to the study analysis, establishing global strategic partnerships will strengthen knowledge and language attainment, environmental interdependence, curriculum enhancement, and research collaboration, which is consistent with the idea of several authors (Altbach & Knight, 2007; Knight & de Wit, 1995).

Specifically, across all cases, all rationale categories were rated highly by interview participants, indicating that internationalisation is expected to have a positive impact on university development. This analysis supports the findings of several researchers and educators (such as Knight, 1995), who agree that internationalisation is a primary driver for innovation and creativity in higher education.

Moreover, all academic rationales were rated higher than economic, social, cultural, and political rationales, suggesting that academic benefits were regarded as the most crucial expectation in the majority of internationalisation programmes. These findings are in accordance with Nguyen's findings (2011). From a philosophical standpoint, the analysis corresponds to de Wit's (2002) point of view in two ways. According to de Wit (2002), internationalisation can strengthen an institution's fundamental structures and activities.

Second, de Wit recognises that internationalisation attempts to help the academic community comprehend, appreciate, and explain the reality of international

interdependence, as well as to equip teachers, staff, and students to work in a worldwide and multicultural setting. While academic incentives are obvious, economic, social, cultural, and political agendas also play a role in shaping the many institutional approaches to internationalisation.

Several authors argue that graduates' international professional knowledge and social intercultural skills are progressively needed to meet the globalisation of society, economy, and labour markets; thus, internationalisation of higher education is crucial in providing adequate preparation for these obstacles (Zha, 2003; Jeptoo & Razia, 2012).

5.4 Strategies and implementation of internationalisation in UK universities

This section investigates university internationalisation processes and how the interpretation of the meaning of internationalisation in higher education pertains to practice-based international integration. The findings are categorised into two major dimensions: domestic and international.

As a result of the various components of higher education internationalisation, some behaviours transcend more than one dimension. One example of this overlap is the international component of international student recruitment, which can be classified as both (Knight, 2011). This international element is included in the category of internationalisation abroad because international students are associated with exchange programmes in this study. According to Huang (2007),

the focus of internationalisation has shifted from developed countries providing technical assistance to developing countries to increasing global competition.

Internationalisation at home is defined by Knight (2004), as internationalisation initiatives or programmes carried out on a home campus. This section on ‘internationalisation at home’ is broken down into six major themes, based on Knight’s proposition (Knight, 2004, p. 17): (1) collaboration communication system, (2) internationalisation of the curriculum, (3) international research collaboration, (4) recruitment of foreign faculty staff, (5) extracurricular activities, and (6) quality assurance or quality review system.

The term communication in this study refers to a variety of academic contacts with foreign institutions and academic peers, with the primary goal of maintaining international connections and planning future collaboration (Knight, 1997). According to the findings, universities are actively seeking partnerships and collaborations. In response to the increasing globalisation process, the historical development of higher education internationalisation has become more visible year by year.

There are six considerations arising from the results, which are:

1. League Table Status
2. Curriculum Content – Joint Degree Programmes
3. Research
4. Co-operative Framework – although this seems to overlap with 2

5. Domestic and International Student Interaction or Mutual Engagement

6. Double international scrutiny of quality

According to the results, international department research collaborations aid in the sustainability of relationships and, as a result, higher league table positions. According to Elkin et al. (2008), most universities have an International Office. The results of Al Shalabi (2011), who described the major responsibilities of international offices around the world in relation to the management of exchange programmes, developing new relationships, and forming collaborative programmes, agree with the results of this study.

Second, curriculum internationalisation is extensively recognized as a key component of UK higher education internationalisation (Leask, 2013). In terms of joint degree-level programmes, this empirical study supports a number of prior research studies that highlighted the importance of international collaboration in academic programmes. According to the interview data, the majority of the institutions in this case established international links with overseas institutions, primarily in the field of degree courses. Knight (2004); Teichler (2004); Teichler (2009).

The finding lends support to a growing body of published literature on the subject (Beelen & Leask, 2011, de Wit, 2012; Leask, 2013; Luxon & Peelo, 2009), which emphasises the development and implementation of joint academic programmes as the pinnacle of university cooperation.

Third, in terms of international research collaboration, these collaborative activities are the result of the realisation that focusing solely on teaching and learning is ineffective; it must be linked to the research area. The results demonstrate that universities encourage two major activities: hosting international conferences and publishing international articles, which Knight (2008), classifies as types of research and scholarly activities. The most effective international activities, according to this study, were those involving the organisation of international conferences and research collaborations.

Fourth, the analysis indicates that foreign faculties play an important role in assisting them in running these joint degree-level programmes within the cooperative framework between the universities and their international partners. According to some interviewees, collaborative programmes like this would improve their teaching methods, expertise, skills, and knowledge.

Fifth, when it comes to international focused extracurricular activities, Knight (1997), defines it as an opportunity for internal and overseas students to interact with one another. These opportunities, according to Knight (1997), are especially important because they can offer local students with international exposure through contact with foreign students. Extracurricular activities can also help international students learn about the culture of the host country and the local students.

Finally, in order to operate on a global scale, an educational institution must adhere to the standards of the global academic community (Arabkheradmand et al., 2015). Obtaining globally renowned status necessitates the implementation of internationally ratified norms in all aspects and levels of education. These components include students, faculty, administrative staff, curriculum, syllabi, teaching, research activities, and assessment (Arabkheradmand et al., 2015).

Cross-border education, also known as internationalisation, abroad, refers to activities that take place outside of a country or across borders. Based on Knight's (2004) classification, the analysis of the interview data is synthesised into two dominant themes: staff and student mobility and building TNEs and collaborations.

The term 'student mobility' refers to not only the physical mobility of students, but also the intellectual mobility of the majority of students (Rudzki, 1995). In this case study, three out of seven components related to mobility of students are available based on the Rudzki (1995) model: recruiting students abroad, exchange programmes, the availability of placements abroad, and field trips.

Student mobility is frequently ranked as one of the most important activities in existing studies on the internationalisation of higher education (Knight, 2003, 2004). The development of international curriculum can be aided by a culturally diverse student body, which can be viewed as a source of information, cultural sensibility, richness, and diversity (Lee & Rice, 2007; Brandenburg & de Wit,

2011). These findings emphasise the high need for international student recruitment, which is in line with conclusions reached by Harris (2008) and Jiang and Carpenter (2013), that universities should prioritise international students as sources of cultural enrichment, rather than merely sources of fees.

Staff exchanges at universities also help to improve skills and knowledge, according to the analysis. This finding supports Knight's (2007), observation about the importance of appropriately qualified academic staff in the internationalisation process. However apart from studying Ph.D. courses in foreign countries, staff can gain key expertise, knowledge, or research experience through other arrangements and activities such as working with a foreign faculty abroad, attending international events, and teaching and seeking information in foreign countries.

According to Arum and Van de Water's (1992), "active approach," internationalisation of higher education can be defined as "many activities, programmes, and services that fall within international studies, international educational exchange, and technological cooperation". More specifically, the primary objective for these activities is to improve educational quality, as well as international reputation and competency. All these worldwide activities of building partnerships and TNEs are primarily aimed at supporting the university's teaching, learning, research, and service activities. This indicates that people's interpretations of the meaning of internationalisation of higher education can be

influenced by the practice of internationalisation of higher education, and that the meaning of internationalisation of higher education can be used to explain how it is implemented.

5.5 Risks and challenges in UK Higher Education sector

Employee conflict over professional knowledge, expertise, or culture is one factor to consider during the internationalisation process. According to the study, depending on where or in which countries teaching staff are educated or trained, their professional knowledge and experience may result in differing perspectives on teaching theories, models, or pedagogies.

The largest risk identified by the investigation was professional knowledge disputes among instructional staff. This problem is more related to on-campus activities than to cross-border aspects of internationalisation. It occurs when establishing a curriculum or administering a course. Some scholarly participants, on the other hand, take a different perspective on the conflict. They feel that these disputes are unimportant, because globalisation of knowledge and advances in information and communication technology have resulted in a global academic paradigm.

Furthermore, the debate about higher education commercialisation as a negative component of internationalisation outcomes has emerged as a key characteristic of the twenty-first century higher education agenda (Chorney, 2008). The term ‘commercialisation’ describes the trends and activities that promote greater

relationships between schools, colleges, and the corporate world (Chorney, 2008, p. 13). As a result of an economic cycle that forces public educational institutions to operate privately, education is becoming commercialised.

This pessimism is also seen as a process in which market values supersede traditional educational values as a public good worthy of pursuit in order to meet the needs of social progress (Chorney, 2008). However, in this investigation, this concern was not determined to be significant. It became obvious that education commercialisation only existed on a small scale and was viewed as a limited risk factor.

The phenomenon of ‘brain drain’, defined as the migration of educated people from developing to developed countries, has long been a source of contention. This issue was identified as one of the greatest risks in the study’s analysis. Institutions have identified another political impact, namely BREXIT, as a major challenge. The current problems caused by the global pandemic are also viewed as a potential risk that necessitates environmental and sustainability measures. Staff conflict over perceptions and cultures is another risk associated with the implementation of an internationalisation strategy. Additionally, as mentioned in chapter one the British Government in the light of BREXIT has pulled out of the ERASMUS programme, substituting their own scheme.

Another issue raised was the issue of the quality of these joint academic programmes, as the entire learning process is carried out in the UK context.

According to these comments, there is still a gap in the learning conditions provided to students by the home university and the partner universities. These conditions include teaching and learning facilities as well as faculty personnel. These conditions, they believe, also have an impact on the outcomes of the courses. In summary, the data analysis suggests several unexpected negative outcomes participants believe may occur as a result of the attempts to develop internationalisation. These issues include ‘brain drain’, ‘academic discord’, ‘unequal treatment of students’, and ‘low-quality providers’.

5.6 Obstacles to implementing internationalisation in UK universities

The obstacles that universities confront in implementing higher education internationalisation are discussed in this section. The outcomes of this study reveal that in most university contexts, barriers to higher education internationalisation take different forms.

According to the results of the study, financial resources are essential for implementing internationalisation methods. Financial constraints were cited by the majority of interviewees as a barrier to completing their internationalisation initiatives, such as setting up exchange programmes, conducting research initiatives, and publishing international papers. Inadequate financial resources are seen as a key impediment to academics and students participating in international activities. This shortfall is the result of relying only on support from the university budget.

This challenge included concerns about a lack of funding for research, exchange of staff, building partnerships and incentivising the student recruitment consultancies. The greatest barrier to internationalisation of higher education in the UK , according to the study, is a lack of funds. This shortage is consistent with the findings of Knight (1997) and van der Wende (1997), who reported that adequate budgeting for internationalisation is a significant challenge for institutions worldwide.

Another major impediment to UK universities promoting internationalisation during the global pandemic is a lack of innovative infrastructure. The study discovered that a lack of modern and well-equipped facilities hampered research and the publication of international articles. Another challenge was identified as a lack of training, as well as the unavailability and limited knowledge of online platforms. Another important aspect of the study's analysis was communication and face-to-face interactions with the students. It must be considered that there is a lack of online expertise to deal with the current environmental changes. This has become all too apparent globally, with changes made to teaching arrangements on an ad-hoc and hurried basis.

Another issue raised was the difficulty lecturers face when participating in international activities such as publishing international articles, conducting international collaborative research, or teaching on jointly taught programmes, due to cultural differences or different educational systems.

Furthermore, the empirical evidence reveals a problem with the approval of paperwork by higher administrative authorities. Respondents were apprehensive while waiting for official clearance, according to the study's results. They also provided various examples to demonstrate how long it takes to get work-related foreign elements approved. The numerous documents that were required to be reviewed or accredited before being utilised created further complications. This approach is predicated on the UK government's restrictive and tightly regulated foreign element policy. This outcome reflects concerns about the lengthy process of obtaining a licence to conduct overseas business. Participants that took on this challenge voiced their dissatisfaction with wasting time and missing out on many opportunities.

The lack of interest among academic faculty was also cited as a major issue. The reward mechanism for doing and writing research, according to Taylor (2004), is one of the most effective determinants in faculty involvement. Their worldwide efforts, however, are not suitably rewarded, respected, or acknowledged. This finding is consistent with a large body of research that claims many higher education institutions do not recognise international activities in faculty compensation systems or prioritise faculty participation in international activities (Ellingboe, 1998; Khorsandi, 2014; Welch, 1997).

Furthermore, evidence from interviews suggests that competition with other universities is a big worry. Competitive countries' flexible policies, for example,

post study visas and the availability of jobs, have a substantial impact on national selection. These challenges were discovered to be interconnected in some ways, in general. These roadblocks add to the workload of both parties involved in the internationalisation process.

In conclusion, this chapter, with its focus on perception, rationale, strategies, implementation, risks, challenges, and obstacles faced by internationalisation, has provided the basis to critique Knight's model (1994), juxtaposed against de Wit (2004) and Perez-Encinas, (2018).

Anyone embarked upon a study of the relatively new topic of internationalisation in higher education will find that Knight's cyclical model provides a gateway to useful definitions, plausible concepts, and components that identify tangible benefits, as well as alerting us to the challenges that engagement with the international agenda presents to a wide range of universities.

Knight's cycle model, first published in the early 1990s and updated in 2012, is a valuable reference point and anchor from which to expand our understanding and then expand out into what for her model remains unidentified area. Research for this thesis has certainly identified points of convergence with all parts of her cyclical model through the responses to the interviews.

However, this thesis has revealed areas that would have remained hidden from view if there had been a sole reliance on Knight. Juxtaposing this thesis research

against the later models of de Wit in 2004 and Perez-Encinas in 2018, which themselves were critical of Knight's limitations, has provided embellishment and detail to help develop further an understanding of the cyclical internationalisation agenda, now and for the future.

Knight's model, discussed in chapter 2 and later in chapter 5, and presented in tabular form below, includes five components captured in a cycle, namely:

1. Awareness
2. Commitment,
3. Planning
4. Organisation
5. Review

Table 1 below identifies the points of convergence and divergence between Knight and the research findings in this thesis.

Table 5.1 – Points of convergence and divergence

Knight	Study Findings	Deviation
<p>Awareness: Need purpose.</p> <p>Benefits of internationalisation to students, staff, faculty, and societ</p>	<p>The study findings suggest the participants are aware of the need and purpose of internationalisation. Key points of emphasis on benefits included positive impact of a global presence as well as academic and economic benefits.</p> <p>Participants mentioned benefits like skills development, getting better jobs and ultimately producing new talented individuals for society. However, they also cited the financial benefits to the universities and the contribution in helping to achieve enhanced QS rankings. They also widely identified the benefits of internationalisation with partner institutions and consultants abroad.</p>	<p>No discernible deviation between this part of the model and the research could be traced here. It represents a common starting point for all subsequent models such as de Wit and Perez-Encinas profiled below.</p> <p>Knight is silent here on the tangible benefits later models and this research has uncovered, for the universities as a corporate body. Knight is also silent on the mutual benefits attained between universities and a growing diverse range of stakeholders in the academic community and beyond.</p>
<p>Commitment</p> <p>On the part of senior administrators, board of governors, faculty, staff, and students</p>	<p>The study findings align with the Knight's cycle as the participants mentioned the importance of staff, senior management, and students in the process of internationalisation. Participants focused upon designing strategies and policies by senior management, staff engagement in teaching and research.</p>	<p>Knight is largely silent on the concept of leadership which later models and this research has identified. A concept of leadership that is distinct from governance and day to day management or administration.</p> <p>Additionally, Knight is silent on the importance of gaining commitments on the</p>

	<p>The interview study opened examination of the support from leadership in the university. All the participants mentioned that without the leadership commitment internationalisation would not have been implemented.</p>	<p>part of external stakeholders and partners i.e., (TNES, study abroad agents/consultants)</p>
<p>Planning Identifying needs, resources. Purposes, objectives, priorities, and strategies</p>	<p>Participants agreed the critical importance of financial resources being underpinned by a robust infrastructure, usually an international department that understood the needs of the student.</p> <p>A typical robust infrastructure encountered during the research identified several international departments with sub divisional responsibilities. This included student recruitment, partnerships, marketing, immigration regulations.</p> <p>Strategic management of change in a global context was touched upon by some respondents</p>	<p>Knight's planning model overlooks the importance of measuring the impact of change and monitoring political and global events carefully. The research study for this thesis written at the time of COVID 19 and just after BREXIT provides telling case studies that will over the next decade be proven agents of change that planner are addressing now.</p> <p>Knight's model written in the nineties was somewhat sheltered from any strategic predictions about a pandemic or the relationship change between the UK and the EU as well as new alliances/immigration arrangements/trading agreements between the UK and non-EU countries, especially the Commonwealth.</p> <p>Knight's sheltered or insulated model precluded the possibility of bringing to life the integration concept discussed later in consideration of the de Wit and Adriana models.</p>

<p>Operationalise-Organise.</p> <p>Academic activities and services, organisational factors, use guiding principles in the mission and vision statement.</p>	<p>Participants certainly identified instances of academic work and factors which over time had become custom and practice for the effective organisation of the internationalisation agenda.</p>	<p>Knight's model is more restricted and somewhat inward looking. The research findings identified what is effectively a growth industry which has driven and sometimes reshaped the internationalisation agenda with tangible 'by-products' such as literature, publications, conferences, and seminars.</p> <p>Curriculum content and its integration with the internationalisation agenda is not even considered by Knight, illustrating again the limited use of her model for on and off campus activities.</p>
<p>Review</p> <p>Assess and enhance quality and impact initiatives and progress strategy</p>	<p>Respondents in the study identified a range of necessary review indicators covering curriculum content, equality outcomes, sustainability and the perception of other universities about the delivery of high service standards.</p>	<p>Knight's model did not identify the impact of robust external scrutiny and inspection requirements which stakeholders and partners nationally and globally have to demonstrate full compliance. Accordingly, stakeholders would expect that all their partners will be equally compliant.</p>

As previously discussed in chapter 2, chapter 4 and this chapter, other models have been carefully considered. Two of these, de Wit (2002) and Perez-Encinas, (2018), have been juxtaposed against these research findings.

De Wit Internationalisation Cycle (2004)

A pictorial representation of de Wit's cycle appears in Figure 2 below. It has eight components:

1. Analysis of Context
2. Awareness
3. Commitment
4. Planning
5. Operationalise
6. Implementation
7. Review
8. Reinforcement

Centre stage, feeding into all the foregoing eight components, can be found a ninth component which de Wit describes as the "Integration Effect", with its consequent impact upon teaching, research, and service functions.

According to de Wit's modified internationalisation cycle, all phases of the internationalisation process in a given institution combine distinct points of view. The de Wit cycle from 2002, which draws upon Knight's internationalisation cycle, considers several variables, while Knight's cycle, as tabulated above, relates more to awareness, commitment, planning, organisation, review and reinforcement variables (Knight,1994). These are detailed in chapter 2. de Wit's (2002), internal circle, denoted at 9, discusses the supportive culture that will facilitate the integration of internationalisation into all aspects of institutions. This

integrated or holistic approach can undoubtedly be reconciled with the findings of this thesis' research.

The research findings concur and can be reconciled with the impact of de Wit's integration effect, in that participants recognised the importance of reinforcement, brand recognition and rankings, as well as corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities, specifically:

- Reinforcement – Participants referred to the need for incentive recognitions and rewards for staff. Respondents indicated that if there were adequate remuneration and real career opportunities through promotions and working abroad, it would bring about positive reinforcement. Additionally, the prospect of dual reinforcement benefiting students and staff comes from the availability of bursaries and scholarship opportunities, coupled with access to other funding sources.
- Outreach activities – boosting community partnerships.

The research identified several examples of outreach activities sustained and held regularly with local and faith-based communities in the immediate precincts of campuses. These included open days, civic excursions to neighbouring towns and cities, affiliated links with local football clubs, and participation in local charitable events.

'Town and Gown' relationships between the academic and the civic world can be found in many localities, including those within the study.

- **Added Value 1** - The integration of the internationalisation agenda into all aspects of an institution's activities presents greater opportunities for joined-up thinking, diverse career paths, the spread and sharing of knowledge across internal boundaries, and the growing exchange of ideas, as well as positive social interaction between diverse cohorts of students from across the globe, undertaking studies in almost all disciplines.

Participants made the point that a robust International Department in the universities has the potential to be the vanguard in helping to steer the whole organisation into an ever-changing world with the ability to comply with complex multi-national regulations, political change, and able to access funding as well as employment opportunities on a wide scale for its students. For example, one of the participants identified how competence in and knowledge of distinct languages used within their area proved valuable in terms of credibility and access.

- **Added Value 2** – Participants identified some useful case studies around staff and student exchanges, pointing to the benefits of international social mobility. These included staff mobility to China, delivering language courses, students taking up fire engineering internships in Zambia, and twinning arrangements between specific departments in different countries covering the same academic modules.

The de Wit (2002), model and this research are at one in recognising that the internationalisation agenda is a live dynamic model that through its cyclical approach feeds and informs each component, keeping everything under high standards of review and quality assurance. More static models such as Knight (1994) and hierarchical models such as Söderqvist (2002) do not have this potential.

Perez-Encina Internationalisation Cycle (2018)

However, Perez-Encinas (2018), articulates a modified version of the de Wit model (2002), which retains the nine-point cycle but threads in and argues strongly for what she calls a collaborative approach. She contends that there is a missing component in the internationalisation cycle, namely the critical inclusion of all stakeholders in the decision-making process, which underpins an institution's supportive culture. This is her definition of a collaborative approach, and it is strongly compatible with the findings of this thesis' research.

Participants in the study expressed their hope, both directly and inferentially, that collaborations among formal and informal services, as well as all stakeholders, will help to improve the quality of education, research, and service.

As a result, the study attempts to demonstrate an incremental concept of how internationalisation is progressing toward becoming more inclusive and collaborative within higher education institutions' internal cultures. Perez-Encinas (2018), emphasises the importance of raising awareness about the need

for an educational system that connects various higher education institutions and internationalisation strategies, as well as staff members and students from various regions.

Figure:5.1 A Collaborative Approach to Internationalisation:

Source: Perez-Encinas (2018)

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This collaborative approach can be seen throughout the research study, for example, in its emphasis on strategic initiatives aimed at fostering community engagement and greater integration among students and staff members on campus. It was notable that a recurring viewpoint emerged, namely that internationalisation of a university is aimed not only at mobile or foreign students, but at all stakeholders involved in higher education.

Perez-Encinas (2018), argues that in order to follow and keep up-to-date with changing trends it is critical to sustain the participation of all stakeholders within and outside the campus. This takes us beyond Knight and de Wit, providing a model which, in a nutshell, reinforces the research findings here. Perez-Encinas (2018), sees “internationalisation as an approach which should be inherently collaborative between formal, informal services and all university constituents to enhance the quality of education, research and service function of the universities.”

As a result of this critique, the following table was created, which retains the nine points from de Wit (2002) and Perez-Encinas (2018) but adds at 11 the additional factor of 'Added Value,' which operates on the same level field as integration.

Added Value 3: sustaining outcomes which go beyond traditional ways of meeting objectives.

Figure: 5.2 Modified Model

Source: Modified by author

5.7 Summary

The key themes from this research are strongly informed by a wide range of definitions, perceptions and interpretations and underpinned by a variety of academic models authored from the 1990s to the early 2020s. These themes were developed against a five-point backcloth. The five themes included:

Perception of Internationalisation of Higher Education ranging from the short term immediate to longer term visionary outlooks.

Rationale for Internationalisation of Higher Education - academic, socio-economic, political, and cultural variables.

Strategies and Implementation of internationalisation - home and abroad.

Risks and Challenges of Internationalisation - financial, resources, geopolitical, economic, and cultural clash.

Obstacles to Implementing Internationalisation - lack of awareness, incentives, lack of interest, funding, no potential for career development.

In a comprehensive focus of one of these cyclical models Knight (1994), the opportunity was taken to juxtapose the central findings of this research against her model. Further analysis and the interpretation of the Knight model clearly indicated that the content of this research went some way beyond the Knight boundaries. Accordingly, a further two models with similarity to Knight but entering new territory were also explored. These two models were de Wit (2002) and Perez-Encinas (2018). The de Wit model, also based on a cyclical framework, went beyond Knight and is immediately reconcilable in large part with this research. This paradigm was particularly valuable because it highlighted new concepts of integration and stakeholder engagement from the outside. On this dimension, the Knight model was almost deafeningly quiet.

Additionally, the Perez-Encinas (2018), cyclical model developed a useful strand under the heading of collaboration, which effectively brought all the Knight and de Wit model concepts into a coherent whole. This holistic

approach was indicative of the findings gleaned from many participants in this research study. However, further examination of the data and participants' feedback identified a new dimension, namely 'Added Value'. Specifically, this added value arose from considerations of the potential for creating community outreach work, staff mobility, and student mobility in terms of attendance at a UK host institution or its counterpart abroad.

In considering all the documented research here, and the formulation of a new model of understanding, this research study will contribute to what is a relatively new concept, which is continually developing within a fast-changing political, educational, and cultural environment both here and abroad.

The next chapter will sum up the research by offering some concluding remarks and considering both the implications and the contribution of the study.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapter discussed data analysis and interpretation based on interviews conducted. This final chapter demonstrates how the thesis's aims and objectives, as stated in chapter 1, have been addressed throughout. It summarises the main points and findings of the empirical investigation and emphasises the study's significance and contribution to the body of knowledge. The chapter also discusses the research findings' implications, makes recommendations, and acknowledges the study's limitations. Future research directions are suggested.

6.2 Review of aim, objectives and research questions of the study

The overriding aim of the study was to identify the key issues and explore the concept of internationalisation with reference to UK universities. To help achieve this aim, the following three objectives were drawn up:

- To critically explore the concept of internationalisation in higher education.
- To critically assess the strategies used by the UK universities to advance internationalisation.
- To critically appraise the challenges faced by the universities in implementing strategies in internationalisation.

In order to address these research objectives, the study used inductive inquiry to investigate research participants' perspectives on various aspects of

internationalisation in higher education. The qualitative semi-structured interviews used for this study addressed each objective. Themes emerging from the data collected demonstrate that each objective was met, as shown below.

6.2.1 Review of objective one (Concepts)

The first objective of this study has been met. It has been determined based on key informant perceptions. According to the findings, three primary conceptual understandings of internationalisation exist among university participants. They are associated with three dominant approaches to the concept of internationalisation: the activity approach, the process approach, and the rationale approach.

The first school of thought considers internationalisation of higher education to be a broad set of policies and programmes that an institution must implement. These activities are specifically related to these institutions' core areas or functions, namely teaching, research, and services.

The second school of thought regards internationalisation as the process of an institution's international integration with the global education arena. In this perception, internationalisation is expressed as a common trend, recognising the critical role of connections and networks among various higher education institutions across the globe. Internationalisation is defined as higher education's overall response to the phenomenon of globalisation in order to ensure its continued existence, survival, and development.

Finally, the third school of thought was viewed by participants as contributing to the rationale of internationalisation, in the sense of assisting the institution in catching up with other universities. The conceptualisation of internationalisation is understood as incorporating international recognition, higher rankings in the league tables, and achieving international targets in terms of research, partnerships and collaborations.

In complementing and reinforcing each of the themes above, most participants appear to understand why universities need to pursue internationalisation, what should be included, and where more investment should be made to advance internationalisation. Regardless of the various interpretations of the concept, the importance of objectives and purposes is an essential part of internationalisation understandings.

6.2.2 Review of objective two (Strategies)

The second objective of this study has been accomplished. According to the research findings in this domain, academic motivations drive higher education internationalisation more than economic, cultural, societal, or political motivations. Internationalisation activities, according to participants' perspectives, are expected to positively improve quality in research, education, and curriculum, talent pool, graduate employability, and, most importantly, institutional recognition and recognition. Notably, this demonstrates that participants across disciplines have a high level of agreement on the rationale for

internationalisation. The most important strategic focus is one that emphasises the idea that internationalisation is primarily educational in nature.

According to the study's findings, most universities have been aiming for the long-term viability of their core business. Different universities' internationalisation programs and activities also show significant differences. This disparity is due to several factors, one of which is its academics' prior study abroad participation. According to the study's findings, there is a significant correlation between academics' and students' actual experiences studying and working abroad and the current level of internationalisation in practice. As a result, any educational policymaker seeking to develop, implement, and sustain a strategic approach to internationalisation must consider both the domestic and international dimensions of internationalisation.

The home dimension will obviously have to capture and address related components that embrace collaborative communication, internationalisation of the curriculum, research collaborations, recruitment and retention of foreign faculty staff, and extracurricular activities, as well as a robust quality assurance or review system.

The overseas dimension, if properly addressed, will have a positive impact on university rankings, curriculum content such as Joint Degree Programmes, collaborative research, and mutual engagement with and between students here and abroad.

6.2.3 Review of objective three (Risks and Challenges)

The third goal of this study has been attained. The findings of this study on the possible risks of internationalisation, however, do not always agree with the previous studies. The author specifically claims that there are significant risks associated with the international context of higher education. This frequently contradicts the findings of the research literature, which consistently rates the potential risk areas as low.

Participants are concerned about 'brain drain,' 'internal strife,' 'political threat,' and 'commercialisation,' among other things. Traditional values, education, and 'loss of cultural identity' were not identified to be serious problems at participating universities. These findings suggest that internationalisation of higher education is associated with more advantageous benefits than potential risks. These are major results that make a significant contribution understanding of the characteristics of internationalisation in the context of the United Kingdom.

When it comes to internationalisation, universities have faced a slew of challenges. Financial deficiencies, a lack of innovative infrastructure, a shortage of highly skilled teaching staff, administrative inertia or bureaucratic difficulties, sustainability, the pandemic, BREXIT, resources, cultural challenges, financial contracts, a lack of interest on the part of the staff, competition, and changing priorities are the most significant challenges impeding the advancement of the internationalisation process. Internationalisation is part of higher education's

efforts to fulfil its primary functions of teaching, research, ranking, mobility, and student service. According to published studies, this area has received little attention in academia. Identifying this vacuum, through the research outcomes described above, the aim of this thesis has been met, namely that this empirical study set out with its primary focus on investigating issues in the internationalisation of higher education in UK universities.

- The overarching goal was to contribute to the investigation of "What" in the field of higher education internationalisation in the United Kingdom. The research objectives were met by soliciting responses from participants to the following three questions: What is understood by the term 'internationalisation' in the context of higher education?

The study has revealed a diverse range of academic definitions with varying degrees of agreement. The findings also suggest some agreement and disagreement on the meaning by the participants.

- What strategies have institutions implemented to advance the internationalisation agenda?

This research identifies a range of strategies, focusing primarily not only on educational and academic output but also on political, socio-economic and cultural approaches and on the needs of the wider stakeholder community.

- What challenges have universities encountered in their drive to advance the internationalisation agenda?

The findings suggest a combination of external political and social issues prevailing at the time of study, coupled with internal threats and challenges associated with student and staff recruitment, retention, and mobility.

6.3 Implications and Recommendations

In this section the implications emerging from the findings of this research are presented and some recommendations resulting from these implications are offered for higher education, stakeholders, and the governance community, which includes inspection regimes externally and the requirements of government through legislation

6.3.1 Higher education implications

The research findings have repeatedly illustrated a real enthusiasm for internationalisation in higher education. The positive implications for higher education are considerable. Specifically, if the enthusiasm detected in this research is to be retained and developed in a substantive way, these positive implications can be realised. Considerable potential benefits will clearly arise from proper funding, strong organisational structures, strategic marketing, collaborative research and partnerships, and staff and student mobility, as well as

through the mainstreaming of internationalisation across all departments of a university.

Leadership and Senior Management in institutions will certainly have to ensure that their strategic corporate policies include all of the foregoing, and that existing related policies and procedures are assessed for impact against the internationalisation agenda.

To begin with, if internationalisation is to become a new institutional driver or fully integrated into an overall strategy, it requires both strong commitment and top-level support. The strategy should become a living document that encourages and supports active participation by all relevant stakeholders. It is not unreasonable for de Wit and Hunter (2015), to predict that the future of internationalisation appears bright, but its further development and impact will only occur if all relevant aspects of this ongoing process, such as rationales, means, or barriers, are openly discussed by all stakeholders. The university must create the right conditions for the implementation of appropriate structures, as well as have a well-defined set of goals and timetables.

Political will and support from higher bureaucratic levels are required for public HEIs in the UK to successfully engage in the internationalisation process. This assistance could take the form of increased budget allocation for higher education institutions, the provision of a legal framework to support broadening internationalisation programmes, or the reduction of the complex bureaucratic

process that stymies international initiatives. Public HEIs, for example, can maintain autonomy while still being held accountable for their performance and societal service. A balance of the three elements of politicisation, institutional autonomy, and accountability is the key to success for higher education development, particularly the expansion of international dimensions in HEIs.

Participants laid emphasis on the need to deter poor quality universities and education providers from blighting internationalisation. To meet this challenge, a national regulatory system is required. To keep up with the growing number of HEIs and the increasing complexity of their operations, the existing regulatory system must be improved. In other words, the system of higher education supervision should be capable of regulating both domestic and foreign education systems or programmes operating within national borders. At the institutional level, the development of a functional, comprehensive internationalisation plan and policy is critical for guiding, monitoring, and assessing the execution and progress of its internationalisation.

Setting explicit internationalisation goals, standards, and indicators, as well as providing systematic organisational support, are critical. To eliminate contradictions and inconsistencies and maximise the benefits of internationalisation, institutions should properly identify and address the challenges and risks associated with higher education internationalisation, as well

as aligning and harmonising internationalisation perceptions, procedures, and priorities.

A useful database system should be established at both the institutional and national levels to collect and update timely, reliable information relevant to the international dimensions of higher education, which can then be fed into various stages of the policy development process. More notably, the strategy should be associated to the government's economic diversification programme and address current human capital development issues such as skill gaps and misalignments between higher education provision and labour market needs.

A number of other factors, such as strong institutional leadership, the commitment of all appropriate institutional stakeholders, and institutional activeness in seeking collaboration, should be incorporated into the UK higher education system in general, as they are critical in enhancing internationalisation. Furthermore, improving institutional communication channels is required to keep institutional stakeholders informed and updated about opportunities to get involved in international programmes and activities, such as information about existing international agreements.

Faculty and staff must keep learning and growing by attending professional development workshops, international conferences, and seminars. Because conducting research is heavily reliant on funding sources, allocating a larger portion of the budget to these activities is critical for developing faculty and staff

research capacity and output. Furthermore, curriculum reform and innovative thinking are crucial to enhance the competitiveness of students and graduates in regional and international markets. International students and academics from other countries should be consulted and involved, encouraging participation in curriculum development.

6.3.2 Implications for other stakeholders

The research findings took the author through a number of academic models formulated from the 1990s to the present day. By way of incremental discussion and argument these models essentially identified the importance of stakeholders. Findings from the interviews concurred strongly with the importance of engaging with appropriate stakeholders, both here and abroad. A typical stakeholder map includes other universities, TNES, international student recruitment agencies, various inspection regimes, and local and national government departments, as well as the wider geographical communities where staff and students live and work. Both academics coming to this research for the first time and existing authors should find a more proactive stakeholder model a powerful reference point.

Stakeholder involvement was cited by some respondents as being something that was being overlooked; when it had been taken into account it greatly enhanced the internationalisation agenda. Projects such as joint working, research, staff exchanges, student internships and conferences and networking were regarded as

good in themselves, but such projects also made a contribution to greater cultural understanding and community harmony.

The following recommendations, under four themes, would greatly assist in realising the aspirations set out above:

Awareness and visibility programmes:

- As a first and continual duty the International Department must assume an ambassadorial function and place of “first contact” with all stakeholders, assisting with problem solving and creative solutions. This might also include the organisation of and/or participation in conferences, training courses and roadshows.

Collaborations

- Any research programme commissioned with an international dimension should include and expect the active participation of an International Department member.
- Any collaboration will demand a good working relationship between the international departments and overseas student recruitment agencies. It therefore follows that the department should have a permanent standing role in showcasing the institution, by, for example, attending fairs, seminars, and webinars.

- The benefits of working with a growing range of general and specialist international recruitment agencies, both here and abroad, must be subject to a rigorous cost benefit analysis.

New study and work opportunities

- The International Department working within the immigration laws of the United Kingdom and other international jurisdictions should play a leading role in securing sponsorships for economic migrants and international students, including employment opportunities, internships, and study placements. It will be expected that close liaison with other colleagues responsible for monitoring progress, adherence to regulations and progression will be sustained. Similar responsibilities will be undertaken with respect to staff secondments or shadow working schemes hosted abroad.

The governance community

- Compliance with laws and regulations and meeting the demands of external inspection regimes requires attention from senior managers of the institution. They will be expected to ensure that the international work of the institution can withstand robust scrutiny and emerge with credit from any inspection or inquiry.

Other Recommendations:

The following recommendations, under eight themes, would also greatly assist in realising the aspirations set out above:

Finance

- An International Department should receive proportionate and pro rata funding, using a model that matches the finances and resources allocated to a mainstream academic department chaired by a professor.
- Budget holders responsible for internationalisation in an institution should be encouraged each financial year not only to bid for a broad allocation but also to specifically be accountable for how each heading of expenditure is used, primarily for educational purposes but also for secondary benefits relating to organisational, economic and cultural achievements.

Organisational Structure

- A stand-alone International Department serving as a one stop shop for the initial recruitment and reception of students should be established with continual proactive links to those parts of an organisation concerned with staff and student progression, including retention policies.

Strategic Marketing

- The International Department should have a proactive on-going role in terms of raising internal and external awareness through marketing, inductions, training, conferences and other activities.

Student and staff recruitment, retention and mobility

- The International Department should be fully involved in the development and implementation of all student enrolment initiatives, staff recruitment and selection policies, and selection decisions, as appropriate.
- Additionally, the International Department should take ownership of all activities relating to alumni.

Collaborative research and partnerships

- Working in close liaison within in-house units of the institution dealing with procurement, ambassadorial activities and speaking engagements, the International Department should be involved in research proposals, bids for funding, and participating in events to showcase activities and achievements.

Mainstreaming

- International Departments should take the lead in identifying and implementing a “twinning arrangement” with comparable departments in

other institutions, so that examples of best practice can be exchanged and shared.

Leadership and senior management responsibility

- Those responsible for corporate governance should ensure they receive appropriate training and management updates on the prevailing internationalisation agenda being addressed in the institution.
- Senior management must ensure that they comply with the governance expectations, and that department heads are cascading appropriate updates to all the teams within their line management.

Culture

- In the United Kingdom, most universities are public bodies, and as such they are subject to the Public Sector Equality Duty (PSED) of the Equality Act 2010. The duty means the organisation must show how it has paid “due regard” to eliminating discrimination, advancing equality of opportunity and fostering good relationships. International specialists inside an institution should have the opportunity to participate in all appropriate equality and cultural impact assessments of employment and learning activities in terms of access to and content of curriculum activities to help to narrow achievement gaps and to secure equality of choice, process and outcome.

6.4 Contribution of the thesis

To some extent, the contribution of this study can already be seen in the fact that the findings have implications for universities, education, government, policymakers, research, and academic scholars. By definition, any thesis with ramifications and subsequent data-backed suggestions must contribute. The subsections that follow present this work's theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions.

The desire to make a potential contribution to the understanding and clarity of internationalisation in higher education research influenced the study design. As a result, this research provides a comprehensive review of the literature on higher education's understanding, implementation, and challenges in internationalisation. A variety of factors influence the implementation of internationalisation (Rumbley, Altbach, and Reisberg ,2012). According to de Wit (2013), most definitions are authored with a specific purpose in mind.

These studies, however, ignore aspects of internationalisation such as specific activities, as well as the state and purpose of internationalisation at the institutional level. Thus, by focusing on internationalisation of higher education at the local level, the study adds new dimensions to higher education research, providing a theoretical and practical contribution that will be useful to higher education internationalisation

Because decisions are made on a variety of grounds, the study revealed that the choice of the type and level of internationalisation is also influenced by factors other than those presented in the literature. As a result, because the process of internationalisation is about integrating and adapting to the international dimension, the integration is filtered and modified by institutional or national organisational realities. Several studies have found that historical, cultural, and academic influences all have an impact on the integration process. As a result, from this perspective, one should look into how decisions about whether or not to approve a specific integration are made.

Based on this comprehension, internationalisation necessitates a rational and scientific choice approach, as well as deliberate choice made by intentional stakeholders in order to achieve the best solution. The various levels of internationalisation are the result of various approaches and motivation among relevant parties. As a result, entering and exiting internationalisation is primarily determined by consequences and appropriateness rather than institutional rules and norms of internationalisation.

Understanding the context of internationalisation and the staff perspective adds to the body of knowledge about internationalisation. Because the concept of internationalisation is broad and previous studies have not exhausted the clarification of the concept, growing understanding of it, it was necessary to study internationalisation in the context of UK higher education. Although

internationalisation is widely used in higher education, there is no agreed-upon definition. Multiple definitions have impacted the concept, as has widespread acceptance of the failure to develop a common, shared definition.

After reviewing literature and interviewing with higher education leaders, the researcher concludes that the term fails to recognise the subjective nature of higher education's internationalisation. Despite the fact that internationalisation in higher education is multifaceted and many factors are considered, this decision was drawn. The study found that different definitions can exist within and between individuals, institutions, and institutions, as well as within and between nations. Definitions are being developed, updated, and improved as the number of stakeholders changes and internationalisation activities expand.

The study did not seek to develop a theory or a definition of internationalisation; rather, it sought to comprehend and clarify the concept in light of emerging attributes and characteristics of internationalisation, as well as the dynamics surrounding the term's definition. The study supports the general consensus that internationalisation has multiple definitions; however, the researcher does not agree with the assertion that internationalisation of higher education is difficult to define. There are conflicting views on what constitutes a definition and how to create one. As a result, the study proposes the use of concept analysis as a rigorous approach to uncovering the characteristics of internationalisation. The study recognises

internationalisation as a strategy based on its understanding of the definition of internationalisation and the characteristics of various attributes of internationalisation, both from literature and from interview data. As a result, internationalisation as a strategy is the sum of internationalisation activities carried out in order to run higher education, whereas purpose is the original intention. However, this does not imply that the sum of all activities contributes to the achievement of internationalisation as a strategy at different times and on different levels.

The project demonstrates creativity in developing and expanding on previous work. The internationalisation of higher education has piqued the interest of world-renowned academics. However, a review of existing research on internationalisation of higher education in the UK revealed that there are no publications on how university internationalisation is perceived and implemented by its key stakeholders, particularly academic staff. This study filled that void by providing information on the conceptualisation of internationalisation and its characteristics in the UK context. It is the first attempt to analyse and systematise a wide range of aspects of university internationalisation, including conceptualization, rationales, implementation, risks, and challenges in the UK context and from the perspective of staff. This study is regarded as an important step toward comprehensive and meaningful understanding of the internationalisation characteristics of UK universities. The new knowledge and insights gained from the internationalisation of

thirteen universities from across the United Kingdom are likely to be useful to other educational researchers interested in this contemporary global issue. The study's findings could help institutional leaders and policymakers determine the most effective methods for ensuring and improving internationalisation policies and practises in higher education institutions.

The thesis makes several significant contributions to the field of internationalisation of higher education. In terms of theoretical contributions, the thesis developed a systematic conceptualisation of internationalisation through the examination of meanings in use and the elevation of empirical data to a conceptual level. As a result, it defines the parameters within which the concept of internationalisation can progress and increases the analytical differentiation of the process in order to capture its various empirical forms. Furthermore, the reconceptualisation of internationalisation can be easily operationalised for research in various contexts and scales of analysis. As such, the thesis contributes to research on higher education internationalisation by transforming the process of internationalisation into a fact-finding category with which theories and models can be tested.

In terms of empirical contributions, the thesis contributes to higher education research in a variety of ways. For instance, it provides a census to UK higher education sector systems that pursue the process strategically at both the institutional and national levels. Furthermore, it provides an original and comprehensive database for UK higher education internationalisation

strategies that can be updated as new plans and strategies are developed, as well as strategies that can be extended to include institutional and supranational strategic documents. It provides a typology of national higher education internationalisation. The benefit of a heuristic device is that it comprehensively describes the universe of empirical data, making it easier to select and justify comparative analysis (Seawright and Gerring,2008). As such, it serves as a baseline for comparing various policy approaches, increasing the likelihood of generating cumulative knowledge. The typology can be adapted for other levels of analysis and combined with other characteristics described in the thesis, for example, two types of approaches (inward and outward) can be combined with primary goals of internationalisation (economic vs non-economic) to form a new body of knowledge. Thus, depending on the focus of future investigations, the typology can be easily redesigned to align with the research goal. This is significant because it implies that typology is not static but rather dynamic. As a result, it may serve as a guiding post for future research and improve the comparability of results.

In terms of practical contributions, the findings increase the transparency of the United Kingdom's internationalisation strategies and challenges for higher education, stakeholders, students, universities, government, business, and policymakers. Understanding the various motivations and aspects of internationalisation, as well as the diversity within the system, can aid in the formulation of strategies and competition. As a result, the study contributes by

increasing the transparency of the internationalisation process for both researchers and practitioners.

6.4.1 Methodological Contributions

This study's contribution can be viewed from a variety of perspectives.

By incorporating key themes emerging from the findings into the established body of knowledge, the study has contributed to the growth and development of the existing body of knowledge. The findings of the study are supported by the interpretivism theoretical framework. Interpretivism is important in assisting us in understanding and exploring their perspectives and expectations in relation to concepts, challenges, and strategies.

This is the first study in relation to UK higher education internationalisation that incorporates the perspectives of staff from all four countries in the United Kingdom.

This study contributes to the ongoing debate in the literature about various issues that arise during the internationalisation process in the UK context. Furthermore, this study examines various models and theories of internationalisation, going beyond Knight's cyclical model, and adds author perspectives based on the study's findings. Further to which a new perspective to the Knight's model is added and this model could be used by universities and researchers as it looks at internationalisation from the new perspective and fits with the new situations (BREXIT and Covid -19)

This is one of the few known studies that used a qualitative approach to investigate the issue of internationalisation in the UK, considering various universities throughout the country. The few studies that have covered this or related areas, such as those by Thomas (2012), Drake (2016), and a few others, have all used a quantitative approach, mixed methods, or are restricted to one case study.

According to Hodges (2017), studies of higher education institutions are frequently hampered by a variety of methodological challenges, such as individuals' reluctance to complete surveys, employees' limited time, and reluctance from institutions to allow researchers to conduct such studies. The researcher was able to use her academic contacts through social media and snowball sampling to conduct in-depth interviews and obtain an adequate sample size from a key group of universities.

Furthermore, this study fills a gap in the literature. In this respect the literature has only focus on studies which are primarily quantitative or qualitative in nature. This study takes a qualitative approach and draws perspectives of staff from the universities who are directly involved in the process of internationalisation. Finally, this study is unique in that it draws on a sample size of universities from each of the United Kingdom's four countries.

6.5 Limitations

6.5.1 General limitations

The study is limited to thirteen higher education institutions. To examine various degrees and stages of internationalisation, all of the cases were examined using similar criteria.

To investigate different degrees and stages of internationalisation, all cases were examined using similar criteria. However, as a reflection of the entire map of higher education internationalisation in the UK higher education context, the findings and theories generated by this research are still limited. Thus, future research could look into the internationalisation of higher education in a variety of HEIs, including public and private, new and old, research-based and teaching-based institutions.

Concerning the limited number of cases, the researcher contends that in the early stages of theory exploration, a low (or small) number of cases is advantageous in gaining a thorough understanding of internationalisation of higher education in a specific context. These provide more detailed and comprehensive information about higher education internationalisation.

A large sample would have been ideal for comparing and contrasting, but this was not possible due to logistical issues, time constraints, and issues of access and participation due to the global pandemic and university office closures.

6.5.2 Methodological limitations

In terms of data collection methods, it must be acknowledged that no matter what methods are used, we can never be certain whether the responses provided by participants represent their genuine viewpoint, especially when considering the context and diverse setting in which most of this research was conducted. Initially, the researcher considered conducting more interviews or focus groups with the staff and segmenting the sample into different geographical locations, further narrowing the sample to old, new, and Russell Group institutions. Due to time constraints, travel restrictions, and a lack of response to the participation invitations sent, semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted only with participants who responded positively.

6.6 Future research

According to the findings of this study, future studies of the internationalisation process in public HEIs in the United Kingdom should include the perspectives of Ministry-level stakeholders. Examining their perspectives may shed light on how decisions regarding the international dimensions of higher education are made, as well as what criteria and factors influence those decisions. Furthermore, future research in this field should consider the perspectives and concerns of business and industry sectors, as well as local communities, in order to bridge the gap between higher education provision and labour market needs.

This study did not consider the viewpoint of the students. Students are key players in internationalisation, and it will be critical to conduct a similar study that includes student perspectives. Their perspectives on issues such as fee structure and internationalisation of the curriculum, as well as international experience, can provide a unique perspective that is not currently available.

According to the findings of this study, there are both similarities and differences between participating universities in terms of internationalisation conceptualisation and practices. As a result, a comparison of this research with similar research conducted in other countries with similar political but different social contexts is suggested for ongoing research in this area. On the one hand, this would allow for additional validation of the study's findings, but more importantly, such broader comparative studies would aid in the development of a more robust theory of the impact of such differences.

The study found some interesting similarities and differences in funding for internationalisation. A separate study on funding in the United Kingdom would be interesting. This could yield some information on potential funding approaches, which could potentially help institutions and policymakers design funding mechanisms to improve higher education internationalisation.

This study examines the role of internationalisation in influencing the quality of higher education. As a result, a more in-depth research study on the impact of internationalisation on the overall quality of the UK higher education system is

required. A study like this will help shed light on the effectiveness of internationalisation strategies that universities can use.

The decolonisation of the curriculum has the potential to have an impact on the internationalisation of higher education in the United Kingdom. While institutions continue to grapple with curriculum internationalisation, curriculum decolonisation has emerged. As a result, it would be worthwhile to conduct a systematic investigation into the potential effects of this phenomenon on the internationalisation of higher education.

Future research could investigate what constitutes international academic standards in the eyes of higher education stakeholders, as well as how internationalisation procedures can help achieve this goal. Finally, future research could look into the impact of BREXIT, Covid, and other changes such as arrangements for online teaching, lecture theatre delivery, and/or a combination of these through hybrid arrangements.

6.7 Conclusion

This study took a long time to complete, but it resulted in an insightful evaluation of internationalisation in higher education, particularly in the context of the United Kingdom. The findings of this study meet the goal of filling a gap in academic research literature. More importantly, it broadens the understanding of internationalisation in higher education in the United Kingdom, and it marks a significant milestone in the theoretical and practical aspects of this field of study.

The point has been made, when discussing the limitations of the scope of this research, that it was being conducted against a fast-changing political and socio-economic backcloth. Specifically, the impact of BREXIT and the continuing devastation wreaked on all sectors, including education, by the ongoing pandemic, cannot be overexaggerated. This has certainly not only limited the research but has signposted areas of massive potential change within the internationalisation agenda, on which other research is likely to find rich data and information.

Finally, the three objectives underpinned by the research questions appeared during the early drafting process to be restricted and unlikely to generate fresh or innovative ideas. However, no less than seventeen recommendations have resulted from this study, with both an internal and external focus. This certainly supports the author's claim that future research and effort on the subject will alter the landscape much more than what has been presented in this study.

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Appendix 1 Ethics Approval

13/11/2019

Dear Pranita Rajendra Gosavi,

Your application 9001: Internationalisation Strategies in Higher Education in the UK, submission 7476, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Please note the student has inadvertently ticked the risk to investigator box in pre-screening. I can see no risk in interviewing university staff so this needs to be unchecked.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix 2 Communication email sent to the universities

Dear Sir / Madam

I am currently undertaking my doctoral research at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). My research involves exploring the concept of internationalisation in UK Universities. More specifically my research seeks answers to the following:

- What is understood by the term 'internationalisation' in the context of higher education?
- What strategies have institutions implemented to advance the internationalisation agenda?
- What challenges have universities encountered in their drive to advance the internationalisation agenda?

The research is essentially qualitative in nature and seeks to collect data from key informants within the University sector. To this end I would appreciate if you could consider taking part in this research or suggest who within your institution would be best placed to contribute the research aim and objectives. The research will comply with all necessary ethical requirements. A full ethics application will be submitted for approval.

It is envisaged that interviews will take approximately one hour. Any information given will remain totally confidential and anonymity will be ensured when reporting the findings.

I would appreciate if she could let me know if you or a colleague are willing to participate in the study and I will get back to you to arrange a convenient time.

Please note interviews will be conducted either in person, phone or skype.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Best wishes

Pranita Rajendra Gosavi

Appendix 3 [Participant Information Sheet](#)

Name of Department/School: School of Business and Enterprise

Researcher: Miss Pranita Gosavi

Title of Research:

Exploring Internationalisation Strategies in Higher Education: UK Universities [Click here to enter text.](#)

Dear participant,

I would like to invite you to take part in this research. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it involves. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Please feel free to ask questions if anything you read is not clear or you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you want to take part.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

There is evidence that universities are internationalising. This is because international students are valuable source for generation of economic, social and cultural advantage to the UK. Due to the major extension of the international student movement and rapid growing competition, the Universities are witnessing competition to attract students. However, there are divergent views about the way in which internationalisation is implemented. Therefore, although the notion of

internationalisation is popular, the current fundamental problem for universities, academic researchers, is how to deal with the complexity of internationalisation. The research seeks to understand the concept of internationalisation, rationales, challenges, and future priorities in the UK universities. This research in relation to the experience of the staff in the international department of the universities, represents a pertinent opportunity to explore the concept and challenges to internationalisation. It is envisaged that the results of the study will generate evidence base that contributes to fostering internationalisation strategies in the universities. Hence, as a Doctoral researcher at University of the West of Scotland, I am undertaking this study.

Do you have to take part?

Participation in this study is voluntary. I or my representative will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which will be given to you. I will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agree to take part. You are free to withdraw anytime without giving a reason.

What will you do in the project?

If you agree to participate in the research, you are required to attend an interview. This will be moderated by myself. During the interview you will be asked number of questions relevant to this research.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you represent a stakeholder whose contribution would be valuable in meeting the objectives of the research.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

During the research you will not be exposed to any physical, psychological, or legal risk or harm. Focus group themes have been structured in such a way as to protect your privacy and no pressure will be put on you to answer sensitive questions. All information provided will be anonymised and kept confidential.

What happens to the information in the project?

Every care will be taken to maintain confidentiality and anonymity. All information received will be stored securely and out with the reach of any third party.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the General Data Protection Regulation and the Data Protection Act 2018. All personal data on participants will be processed in accordance with the provisions of this legislation.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the research then please proceed to take part in the interview, which will be viewed as your agreed consent and sign the consent form. If you do not wish to be involved, then thank you very much for your time.

Research Ethics

This study was granted ethical approval by the UWS School of Business and Enterprise Ethics Committee.

If you have any questions or concerns, during or after the investigation please contact:

School of Business and Enterprise

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

High Street

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Researcher's contact details: Miss Pranita Gosavi

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 4 Participant consent form

Participant consent form

Name of Researchers: Miss Pranita Gosavi

Please initial/check box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above

study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at

any time, without giving any reason.

3. I agree to take part in the above study.

4. I agree to the interview being audio recorded.

Name of participant _____

Date

Signature

Researcher:

Date _____

Signature _____

Appendix 4

Appendix 5 Interview schedule

- In the context of higher education, what is your understanding of internationalisation?
- Does your institution have an internationalisation agenda?
- If yes, what is the rationale for pursuing this agenda?
- What are the principal drivers of internationalisation in your institution?
- What would you say are the key themes of your internationalisation agenda?
- How is the internationalisation agenda implemented i.e. what strategies or measures has your institution adopted to pursue internationalisation activities?

- Do you have a unit/division that is specifically responsible for internationalisation? If yes, do you believe it is sufficiently resourced to achieve the internationalisation agenda?
- What mechanisms are in place to promote internationalisation in your institution?
- How is the University leadership supporting internationalisation at the institution?
- What challenges have you encountered or perceive in attempting to implement your internationalisation agenda?
- How would you differentiate your institution's approach to internationalisation in relation to other institutions?

Appendix 6 Statistics and data on UK higher education sector (HESA)

TRENDS IN INTERNATIONAL STUDENT ENROLMENTS IN THE UK

438,010

international students studied
in the UK in 2015-16.

Figure 3: Number of EU and non-EU students in the UK, 2007-08 to 2015-16

Source: HESA Student Record (2007-08 to 2015-16)
Note: All figures for non-EU, EU and total non-UK enrolments are rounded to five.

INTERNATIONAL STUDENT ENROLMENTS IN THE UK

28%

increase in the number of international students in the UK since 2007-08.

Figure 4: Number of EU and non-EU students in the UK, by students' place of origin, 2007-08 to 2015-16

Source: HESA Student Record (2007-08 to 2015-16)

WHERE DO INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN THE UK COME FROM?

51%

of international students come from just 10 countries.

Figure 5: Top 20 countries of student origin 2015-16

Source: HESA Student Record (2015-16 and 2010-11)

WHAT DO INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN THE UK STUDY?

As much as
63%
of all students at
postgraduate level can
be international.

Figure 6: Number of international students by subject area, 2015-16

Figure 7: Proportion of non-UK students by subject area, 2015-16

Subject Area	Undergraduate	Postgraduate (Taught)	Postgraduate (Research)	Total
Business and Administrative Studies	26.8%	62.9%	59.0%	37.6%
Engineering and Technology	23.8%	60.0%	61.0%	32.5%
Social Studies	13.6%	36.5%	47.1%	19.3%
Subjects Allied to Medicine	5.6%	10.5%	35.4%	7.4%
Creative Arts and Design	12.7%	48.2%	30.8%	16.9%
Biological Sciences	8.2%	21.5%	31.7%	11.0%
Law	21.0%	44.4%	51.1%	26.4%
Computer Science	13.0%	50.4%	58.2%	19.9%
Languages	13.7%	45.0%	44.3%	17.9%
Physical Sciences	9.5%	41.4%	40.8%	16.0%
Education	1.8%	10.6%	31.1%	6.7%
Architecture, Building and Planning	20.4%	35.0%	54.7%	25.8%
Mass Communications and Documentation	15.5%	55.3%	41.0%	23.6%
Medicine and Dentistry	11.2%	24.1%	30.8%	16.1%
Historical and Philosophical Studies	6.6%	27.8%	36.0%	11.3%
Mathematical Sciences	15.9%	57.5%	54.0%	21.8%
Combined	6.5%	3.4%	40.0%	6.4%
Agriculture & Related Subjects	6.2%	33.7%	48.1%	11.8%
Veterinary Science	17.3%	10.7%	31.7%	16.8%
Total	13.6%	36.6%	43.2%	19.3%

Source: HESA Student Record (2015-16)

THE IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

78%
of undergraduate students believe
that studying alongside international
peers prepares them for working in
a global environment.

Figure 10: Home students views on studying alongside international students

Figure 11: Poll of British public on international students

Source: Left: HEPi (2015) Right: Conres (2017)

Note: Figure 10 is based on the responses of 1,009 students. Figure 11 is based on the responses of 4,043 British adults in March 2017.

THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

Figure 12: Export earnings generated by international students by UK region, 2014-15

£25.8bn

generated for the UK economy through on and off-campus spending by international students and their visitors.

In 2014-15:

£13.6bn

gross value added generated by international students on and off-campus spending

£10.8bn

worth of export earnings from international students

Supporting 206,600

full-time jobs

Sources: Universities UK (2017) The Economic Impact of International students; Universities Scotland (2013) Grow, Export, attract support; Universities Wales (2015) The Economic Impact of higher education in Wales; Universities UK (2017) The Economic Impact of Queen's University Belfast and Ulster University on the Northern Ireland Economy
 Note: The figures for Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland represent total export earnings and therefore include international income earned by HEIs from overseas businesses, charities, governments.

ACADEMIC MOBILITY

Between 2007-14

14,316

UK researchers and teachers received EU funding to spend time abroad for research, teaching or training.

Figure 16: UK engagement in researcher mobility through EU programmes, 2007-13

	UK Academics going overseas	Overseas Academics coming to the UK
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions: Fellowships	1,297	6,132
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions: International Research Staff Exchange Scheme (IRSES)	2,157	1,988
Erasmus+: Staff mobility (up to 2012)	10,862	13,464

Figure 17: Top 5 destinations under IRSES, 2007-14

Top 5 source countries for researchers coming to the UK	Rank	Top 5 destinations for UK researchers
China	1	China
Brazil	2	USA
Russia	3	Brazil
India	4	Russia
South Africa	5	India

Sources: European Commission, Erasmus+ UK National Agency

Note: International Research Staff Exchange Scheme (IRSES) was a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action within FP7 aimed at supporting staff exchange and networking with countries with which the EU has a science and technology agreement. Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action fellowships supported researcher mobility within and outside the EU, and the Erasmus+ programme provides educators the opportunity to teach or train abroad.

STUDENT MOBILITY

27,400+

UK students went abroad in 2015-16 to study, work or volunteer as part of their degree.

Figure 18: Where mobile UK students go, 2015-16 (2014-15)

Source: HESA student record (2015-16)

Note: 80 instances of outward mobility recorded by HESA were to an unrecorded destination.

STUDENT MOBILITY AND OUTCOMES

Mobile students are

24%

less likely to be unemployed six months after graduation than their non-mobile peers.

Figure 19: Among undergraduate students graduating in 2014-15, students who were mobile experienced the following six months after graduation:

Figure 20: Differences in the unemployment rates of mobile and non-mobile students are greatest among those from under-represented groups:

Source: ULKI Gone International 2017

*BME refers to black and minority ethnic

TRANSNATIONAL EDUCATION

701,010

students study for UK higher education qualifications outside of the UK.

Figure 23: Top 20 countries by UK HE TNE student numbers, 2015-16

Figure 24: Location of UK HE TNE students, 2015-16

Source: HESA Aggregate Offshore Record (2015-16)

Note: In 2015-16 45% of all TNE students were registered through Oxford Brookes University with an overseas partner on Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA) programmes.

TRANSNATIONAL EDUCATION

81%

increase in the number of UK HE TNE students since 2008-09.

Figure 26: Trends in UK HE TNE student numbers, 2008-09 to 2015-16

Figure 27: Changes in location of UK HE TNE students rankings

Rank	2010-11	2012-13	2015-16
Malaysia	1	1 ▶ 0	1 ▶ 0
China	3	3 ▶ 0	2 ▲ 1
Singapore	2	2 ▶ 0	3 ▼ -1
Pakistan	4	4 ▶ 0	4 ▶ 0
Nigeria	6	6 ▶ 0	5 ▲ 1
Hong Kong, China	5	5 ▶ 0	6 ▼ -1
Sri Lanka	21	13 ▲ 8	7 ▲ 6
Egypt	15	17 ▲ 2	8 ▲ 9
Oman	16	11 ▼ -5	9 ▲ 2
Ghana	7	7 ▶ 0	10 ▼ -3

Figure 28: Type of UK HE TNE provision, 2015-16

Source: HESA Aggregate Offshore Record (2015-16)

Note: In 2015-16 45% of all TNE students were registered through Oxford Brookes University with an overseas partner on Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA) programmes.

RESEARCH INCOME FROM INTERNATIONAL SOURCES

73%

increase in overseas investment in UK research and development in the last seven years.

Figure 30: Research income from international sources, 2009-10 to 2015-16

Figure 31: Percentage of GERD* funded from abroad, 2015 or latest data available

Source: Top: HESA Finance Record (2009-10 to 2015-16). Bottom: OECD (2016)

*Gross Domestic Expenditure on research and development (GERD) refers to the total intramural expenditure on R&D performed on the national territory by all sectors in a given period of time.

INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH COLLABORATION

50.7%

of the UK's research publications involve international collaboration.

Figure 32: Percentage of research collaborations involving an international co-author, 2013

Source: Elsevier Scopus 2000-2013

UK INNOVATION

3rd

The UK ranks in the top 3 in the world for its innovation capabilities.

Figure 37: Global Innovation Index ranking, 2011-16

Ranking	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
1	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland
2	Sweden	Sweden	Sweden	UK	UK	Sweden
3	Singapore	Singapore	UK	Sweden	Sweden	UK
4	Hong Kong	Finland	Netherlands	Finland	Netherlands	USA
5	Finland	UK	USA	Netherlands	USA	Finland
6	Denmark	Netherlands	Finland	USA	Finland	Singapore
7	USA	Denmark	Hong Kong	Singapore	Singapore	Ireland
8	Canada	Hong Kong	Singapore	Denmark	Ireland	Denmark
9	Netherlands	Ireland	Denmark	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	Netherlands
10	UK	USA	Ireland	Hong Kong	Denmark	Germany

Source: Global Innovation Index (2016)

Appendix 7 Findings Themes and coding – Question 1

In the context of higher education, what is your understanding of internationalisation?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	<p>Intercultural and global perspectives that we're trying to work through the universities, teaching research and business activity.</p> <p>Curriculum to mobility opportunities</p>	<p>There is a high degree of optimism in university's views about the curriculum making a global impact.</p> <p>The university has significant awareness about student mobility and is currently dealing with highest rate of student mobility.</p>	<p>research</p> <p>student mobility</p> <p>curriculum</p>
UNIVERSITY 2		<p>Awareness about the necessity of students with diverse nationalities is observed.</p> <p>Strong support for overseas students is emphasized by the senior management.</p> <p>The university is aware about the statistical distribution of overseas students.</p> <p>This is observed in one of their statements that claims that approximately 20% of the students come from overseas.</p> <p>Strong encouragement is provided to research partnerships with overseas institutions as also to that with global companies.</p>	<p>diversity</p> <p>research</p> <p>collaboration</p> <p>rankings</p>
UNIVERSITY 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Working with partnerships •international student recruitment •offering an international experience •curriculum also includes global perspectives •research exchanges •staff exchange •inward and outward student mobility •Internationalisation of the whole community 	<p>There is a strong support for activities like research, teaching, partnership taking internationalisation into consideration.</p> <p>There is an acknowledgement about the university's intent towards making a global impact.</p>	<p>research</p> <p>collaboration</p> <p>global impact</p>

UNIVERSITY 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global perspective • Having global Impact • Student and staff exchanges • Doing things for the community • Commercial activities • Research and teaching • Partnerships • Recruitments • Overseas agents 	<p>High degree of awareness about sustainability issues and climate change is observed.</p> <p>Significantly high diversity is observed in the student body from UK.</p> <p>The university is comparatively more inclined in favour of comprehensive internationalisation (through curriculum) as opposed to the transactional or commercial internationalisation.</p>	<p>sustainability</p> <p>climate change</p> <p>diversity</p>
UNIVERSITY 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operations • Partnerships • Student recruitment • Learning and teachings • Research collaborations • Work abroad placements • Content on curriculum 	<p>Presence of partnerships with students in learning, teaching and research was viewed.</p> <p>As per the university, internationalisation is associated with the ability of students to study or work abroad for placement periods.</p>	<p>research</p> <p>recruitment</p>
UNIVERSITY 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internationalisation culture • student body • faculty • research • educational programmes • support services • physical resources • stakeholder relation. 	<p>There is acknowledgement about partnerships with organizations and with overseas universities.</p> <p>Emphasis is given on opportunities in providing international experience to students.</p> <p>Inclusion of global perspectives in subject areas is stressed upon and essentially practised among students.</p> <p>The university acknowledges the opportunities it provides to the local students to spend their time overseas.</p>	<p>collaboration</p> <p>international experience</p> <p>contribution</p> <p>community</p> <p>recruitment</p>

		Significant degree of awareness about contributions made by the appointed academic staff in the areas of teaching and research.	
UNIVERSITY 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students moving between different countries • staff moving between different countries • research; collaborative research projects across borders 	Emphasis is given on student and staff exchange , research collaboration	collaboration international experience recruitment
UNIVERSITY 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student movement , stakeholder relation • boundaries are to disappear 	A positive approach towards student movement and cross border curriculum	staff and student exchange
UNIVERSITY 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing to international students and UK students • positive international community • teaching and learning methods 	A high degree of importance is given to student recruitment and internationalisation of curriculum	community impact Student recruitment internationalisation of curriculum
UNIVERSITY 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research links • diversity of nationalities on campus 	As per the university, internationalisation is associated with research and diversity	Diversity research collaborations
UNIVERSITY 11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • staff and students mobility • keep its position in the ranking. 	Global ranking and student mobility is the main internationalisation strategy	global ranking staff and student mobility
UNIVERSITY 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •environmental sustainability internationalisation culture • student body 	The university is positively inclined towards collaborating with students globally. There is acknowledgement about partnerships with organizations and with overseas universities.	collaboration globally collaboration
UNIVERSITY 13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Partnerships • Having global Impact 	As per the university, internationalisation is associated with the ability of students to study or work abroad for placement periods. The university is comparatively more inclined in favour of comprehensive	partnerships global impact

		internationalisation (through curriculum) as opposed to the transactional or commercial internationalisation.	
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Appendix 8 Findings Themes and coding – Question 2

Does your institution have an internationalisation agenda? If yes, what is the rationale for pursuing this agenda?

PARTICULARS

INITIAL FINDINGS

KEY FINDINGS

Themes

<p>UNIVERSITY 1</p>	<p>•Yes, we do. Our first internationalisation strategy at least ten years ago, and it was very successful in terms of increasing our outbound student mobility programmes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased our international numbers, particularly at undergraduate level, and we established to international strategic partnerships. • international student mobility • and building TNES • rationale is to improve our global rankings. • Global research • Global impact • attract more students to study with us, particularly from rankings conscious market, and it will improve our research profile • And most recently we've been rewriting our international strategy. And through it, we're going to focus on two main areas. One is growing international student numbers, and the second is developing TNE partnerships. 	<p>The university is well aware about the delay in taking initiatives on internationalization, however recently efforts were taken to make improvements and recruitments have been done to appoint individuals to handle specific responsibilities.</p> <p>Presence of commercial partnerships and research partnerships is acknowledged.</p> <p>Until now, there wasn't a separate team and/or individuals to handle responsibilities related to internationalisation.</p> <p>A considerable amount of time (18 months, as stated) was spent in developing the internationalisation strategy.</p> <p>A strong financial support has been provided as the university has invested a significantly high amount of money.</p> <p>Strong expectations of getting returns on financial investments has been observed in the university staff.</p>	<p>partnerships - commercial partnerships, research partnerships strategy recruitment relationships competition</p>
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UNIVERSITY 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Yes •attractiveness of our offerings to students •Research and enterprise •university to university collaboration internationally is becoming an increasing focus of international research. So research income 	<p>Innovation and research are regarded highly and greatly encouraged. It is observed that the university has received compliments from international research journals.</p> <p>There is a strong expectation to improve rankings in</p>	<p>research collaboration ranking reputation joint projects</p>
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<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>3</p>	<p>Global strategy sits alongside research, education and engagement</p> <p>dedicated global strategy as well</p> <p>got companies in Malaysia and Singapore</p> <p>key locations where we're actually delivering teaching</p> <p>Partnerships include universities in North America, Australia and China, India.</p> <p>quite a few relationships with other organizations as well in and across Asia, America and Europe</p>	<p>The university is well aware about the requirement of a dedicated global strategy, which it already has in place.</p> <p>A considerable significance has been given to global strategy which is being planned parallel with research, education and engagement.</p> <p>It is observed that the university is involved in multiple partnerships with other universities from regions like North America, Australia, China and India.</p> <p>There is a strong consensus on collaborations spanning across multiple nations. This is observed from their relationships with organizations in Asia, Europe, America, Malaysia and Singapore.</p>	<p>strategy</p> <p>research</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>relationships</p>
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<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>4</p>	<p>had our first internationalisation strategy at least ten years ago</p> <p>it was very successful in terms of increasing our outbound student mobility programs</p> <p>We increased our international numbers, particularly at undergraduate level</p> <p>Focus on 2 main areas - growing international student numbers, developing TNE partnerships</p>	<p>The university intends to develop a global outlook through the strategies it has undertaken.</p> <p>Steps are being taken to encourage diversity among students in the campus.</p> <p>A detailed and well planned strategy is observed. The university has identified four key sectors to invest in - medical Science, sustainability and low-carbon Technology Material Science, assistive technology, animation simulation and visualization.</p> <p>The university has identified 'International research Partnerships' as the area to emphasise on and has dedicated resources towards this objective.</p> <p>Strong support for new international collaborations in the identified sectors.</p>	<p>student mobility</p> <p>numbers</p> <p>strategy</p> <p>partnerships</p>
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<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>5</p>	<p>one of the actions that strategy has - to develop a global Outlook</p> <p>we still have actions around diversifying our student body on campus</p> <p>really focus on - International research Partnerships</p> <p>Four areas university is looking to invest in - Medical Science, sustainability and low-carbon Technology Material Science, assistive technology, animation simulation and visualization</p> <p>my role is now to really work with academic colleagues to try and drive new collaborations in these areas with institutions that have strength in these areas, you know internationally</p>	<p>The university has recently chalked out an internationalisation strategy and has incorporated learning and teaching in it.</p> <p>It is observed that the university holds talks on internationalisation.</p>	<p>strategy</p> <p>global outlook</p> <p>specialization</p> <p>recruitment</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>research</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>6</p>	<p>Innovation - research Enterprise - more about international research</p> <p>Emphasis to be higher up in the rankings</p>	<p>There is high degree of awareness about the requirement of international experience and global perspective in the curriculum. To provide for this, the university is working on developing a global strategy.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement about a need for creating and maintaining an international student community.</p> <p>The university intends to take the programs closer to a more global audience.</p>	<p>curriculum</p>

<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>7</p>	<p>•KPI for this one, we've got rankings so and and so rankings specific KPI strategic partnerships</p> <p>it was very successful in terms of increasing our outbound student mobility programs</p>	<p>Internationalisation strategy is viewed as very successful as it was developed ten years ago and it significantly increased outbound student mobility programs.</p> <p>High degree of awareness is observed among the staff in international students' distribution. The impact of global strategy is observed predominantly in undergraduate courses.</p> <p>A strong emphasis is given in growing international student numbers and in developing Jeanny partnerships.</p>	<p>research rankings KPI experience</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>8</p>	<p>working on including international experience for all students and global perspectives in the curriculum</p> <p>creating a sort of an international student community</p> <p>how we bring our programs closer to more of a global audience</p>	<p>A strong focus is on student experience and having global and diverse audience</p>	<p>curriculum, diversity</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY</p> <p>9</p>	<p>Rationales</p> <p>• international student mobility</p>	<p>Until now, there wasn't a separate team and/or individuals to handle responsibilities related to internationalisation.</p>	<p>recruitment</p>

UNIVERSITY 10	• building TNES and student and staff exchange	A considerable amount of time (18 months, as stated) was spent in developing the internationalisation strategy.	relationships
UNIVERSITY 11	• Global research, financial benefits	Strong expectations of getting returns on financial investments has been observed in the university staff.	Global research financial benefits
UNIVERSITY 12	•attractiveness of our offerings to students •Research and enterprise	More emphasis is given to research and attracting international students along with providing best experience	research collaboration diversity in population
UNIVERSITY 13	We increased our international numbers, particularly at undergraduate level Focus on 2 main areas - growing international student numbers, developing Jeanny partnerships	Strong support for new international collaborations in the identified sectors.	strategy partnerships

Appendix 9 Findings Themes and coding – Question 3

What are the principal drivers of internationalisation in your institution?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES

UNIVERSITY 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • student diversification. So a good range of students from different countries, different cultures. • There's income generation • the ability to network for research • global research network • the partnerships we develop allow that to happen 	<p>The university has an abundant number of overseas students. It is observed that the university is aware about the statistical distribution of overseas students.</p> <p>It is acknowledged that payments made by students are a significant income driver for the university.</p> <p>The university is well aware about its ability to attract international research funding.</p> <p>The university strongly supports in providing opportunities and is working under franchise agreements with local providers in countries like Nepal. In providing such opportunities, the university charges less but emphasis is given on providing employability.</p>	<p>apprenticeships</p> <p>competition</p> <p>institutions</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>costs</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>research</p> <p>opportunities</p> <p>international experience</p>
UNIVERSITY 2	<p>exposure of our own students to people from different cultures and backgrounds</p> <p>issues of social justice around the curricula</p> <p>decolonization agenda</p> <p>principal driver for internationalization - income and the mission</p>	<p>It is observed that the university associates internationalization strongly to the student experience.</p> <p>The university acknowledges to attract global students through their attractiveness of offerings.</p>	<p>student experience</p> <p>offerings</p>

UNIVERSITY 3	<p>research and student recruitment</p> <p>knowledge transfer of experience</p> <p>collaborations across the globe with different research</p> <p>maintaining the rank, profile, reputation and growth of the university</p> <p>student exchange for teaching and research collaboration</p>	<p>Significant emphasis is given to partnerships like exchange of students and exchange among the staff.</p> <p>The university states that knowledge transfer of experience gives the city a more global perspective and understanding.</p> <p>Multiple collaborations have been done across the globe. As per the university, this has resulted in their research to get stronger. Furthermore, this is also contributed to improving the rank, profile and reputation of the university thereby ensuring better growth for the university in the long run.</p> <p>It was acknowledged by the university that exchange for teaching and research collaboration is one of the objectives. Also, this activity is driven by the individuals together with the faculty that the international office.</p>	<p>perspective</p> <p>partnership</p> <p>recruitment</p> <p>research</p> <p>financial sustainability</p> <p>relationships</p>

UNIVERSITY 4	<p>growing international student numbers, developing TNE partnerships, to improve global rankings global research four pillars that support our current international strategy - global graduates, global partnerships, global research and global impact</p>	<p>The university intends for their work to make an impact on all levels - regionally, nationally and globally. To achieve this, different strategies are required.</p> <p>There is a strong expectation to have a diverse international campus.</p> <p>International research partnerships and co-authoring research papers with international authors is regarded highly.</p> <p>There is a strong consensus among the staff who work in mobility to have global outlook among the students. There is also an agreed certainty among the mobility staff that global outlook results is beneficial for employability.</p> <p>One of the initiatives of the university has been the 'global talent program' for the students to imbibe cross cultural awareness among them.</p>	<p>research diversity partnerships global outlook mobility sustainability</p>

UNIVERSITY 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial: need to recruit international students. • Change of Vice Chancellor into one who ‘believes in strategies’ • Follow the ‘fads and fashions’ of the HE sector. Be part of the club 	<p>There is a high degree of awareness about exposure of students to individuals from multiple cultures and backgrounds.</p> <p>A concern about issues of social justice around the curriculum is observed. Also, the university views decolonization agenda as an issue to be addressed.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of income and mission being the key drivers for internationalization is observed.</p>	<p>values</p> <p>cultures</p> <p>social justice</p> <p>curriculum</p>
UNIVERSITY 6	<p>student experience</p> <p>attractiveness of offerings to students</p>	<p>There is a high degree of awareness about the changing pace of technology and the integration it has brought as in the ease of getting a job overseas or the convenience to travel.</p>	<p>research</p> <p>contribution</p>

		As per the university, higher ranked universities can co-operate together to produce high quality research.	
UNIVERSITY 7	Main drivers are student recruitment and growing the research profile	The university has expressed a keen interest in attracting growing international student numbers. In order to achieve this purpose, they intend to participate in better international partnerships. A key area where university aims to grow significantly is the research profile.	rankings partnerships
UNIVERSITY 8	having global presence, partnerships and international students	The university has identified four pillars that support their international strategy - global graduates, global partnerships, global research and global impact.	research, student recruitment , partnerships
UNIVERSITY 9	• student diversification. So a good range of students from different countries, different cultures.	The university has an abundant number of overseas students. It is observed that the university is aware about the statistical distribution of overseas students.	student diversity
UNIVERSITY 10	Contribute to innovations and strategies	The university prioritises global challenges for contributions by students like contributions to innovations, strategies and UN goals.	global challenges

UNIVERSITY 11	maintaining the rank, profile, reputation and growth of the university	The university focuses on rankings and the growth of the university	reputation global ranking
UNIVERSITY 12	student exchange for teaching and research collaboration	Priority is given to research collaboration	research collaboration
UNIVERSITY 13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • global research network • the partnerships we develop allow that to happen 	emphasis on partnerships and networking	research opportunities international experience

Appendix 10 Findings Themes and coding – Question 4

What would you say are the key themes of your internationalisation agenda?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	<p>More international students of partners</p> <p>Research funding</p> <p>Exchange programs</p> <p>Visiting scholars and their work on research projects</p> <p>Doctoral students</p>	<p>Higher number of international students from partners, more research funding and more students coming to exchange programs are among the key intentions of the university.</p> <p>The university intends an increase in the quantity of visiting scholars for their works on multiple research projects.</p> <p>It is observed that increase in quantity is desired in multiple areas by the university however those are not quantified.</p>	<p>growth</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>research</p>
UNIVERSITY 2		<p>It is observed that high significance is given to brand awareness and international collaborations.</p> <p>The university intends to improve its research performance in terms of recognition and income.</p> <p>Awareness about collaborations is observed and is given due importance.</p>	<p>institutions</p> <p>collaboration</p> <p>research</p>

UNIVERSITY 3	co-operative research for global impact connections with global alumni	It is observed that there is emphasis on co-operative research and connections with global alumni. There is a high degree of optimism about the support and contributions from alumni. There are expectations from alumni to generate engagement and help in fundraising.	research alumni recruitment
UNIVERSITY 4	graduate international students, both inward and outward students global partnerships, Tinney partnerships, pixelation partnerships and the exchange partnerships global research student diversification staff mobility programs	The university is involved in partnerships like TNE partnerships, pixelation partnerships and exchange partnerships. The university acknowledges that it expects student diversification and thereby aims for income generation. Presence of a global research network is regarded highly and partnerships are encouraged. There is a very good support for staff mobility programs and strategy partnerships. Strategic partnerships are distributed across multiple regions like South east Asia, Middle east, Europe, Central America and Latin America.	international students partnerships global research mobility - mobility programs and staff mobility

UNIVERSITY 6	<p>university collaboration</p> <p>International research</p> <p>Working on collaborative activities</p>	<p>It is expected that students do not remain only to their sub-groups but rather mingle with individuals of different nationalities and cultures.</p> <p>The university is of the view that involvement in work offerings will result in development of the global citizens.</p> <p>Significance is given to diversity and it is intended that this will result in students learning from each other and developing their network.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement about work being done on strategic level, however it is yet to be implemented.</p>	<p>placements</p> <p>curriculum</p> <p>opportunities</p> <p>diversity</p>
UNIVERSITY 7	<p>study abroad, work abroad</p> <p>global education</p> <p>recruiting students from different countries worldwide</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>internationalization strategy</p>	<p>The university is involved in partnerships like TNE partnerships, pixelation partnerships and exchange partnerships.</p> <p>The university acknowledges that it expects student diversification and thereby aims for income generation.</p> <p>Presence of a global research network is regarded highly, and partnerships are encouraged.</p> <p>There is a very good support for staff mobility programs and strategy partnerships. Strategic partnerships are distributed</p>	<p>international</p> <p>students</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>global research</p> <p>mobility - mobility</p> <p>programs and staff</p> <p>mobility</p>

		across multiple regions like Southeast Asia, Middle east, Europe, Central America and Latin America.	
UNIVERSITY 8	Connections with alumni and global partners	The university focuses on partnering with alumni and other institutions worldwide	Relationships with alumni and partnerships
UNIVERSITY 9	providing community the best skills and talents	The university is of the view that involvement in work offerings will result in development of the global citizens.	global citizens
UNIVERSITY 10	research programmes and staff exchange	The university intends an increase in the quantity of visiting scholars for their works on multiple research projects.	partnerships
UNIVERSITY 11	graduates and research collaborations and more PhD Students	The university also expects more doctoral students to complete their education.	research and graduate outcomes
UNIVERSITY 12	global research and having students from various parts of the world staff mobility programs	More emphasis is given on research impact and student staff exchange	global research Student Diversification Self-mobility programs

UNIVERSITY 13	Diversity of student population	Significance is given to diversity and it is intended that this will result in students learning from each other and developing their network.	diversity learning outcomes
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Appendix 11 Findings Themes and coding – Question 5

Ø How is the internationalisation agenda implemented i.e. what strategies or measures has your institution adopted to pursue internationalisation activities?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> international student growth- projects particular project that's running at the moment called International Step Change, and that's got ten work packages associated with it, and that is the implementation strategy for that particular strand of the international localisation strategy. So we've been given funding by the university to develop to reach the targets over a five year period to the global graduate. also driving the global rankings improvement as well 	<p>It is observed that multiple new individuals have been recruited and assigned to specific positions.</p> <p>A huge financial support has been provided which includes the budget to increase to tenfold.</p> <p>The university acknowledges about lack of reach and network and hence has hired third party organizations for international partnerships and recruitments.</p> <p>Personal relationships are held in a high regard and are used to benefit in the day-to-day tasks like getting leads for international partnerships.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> partnership recruitment budget strategy taxation investment -

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementing the research, global research. We have a separate research strategy which aligns with the university's strategic plan. • And the global research element is embedded in that. And we just incorporate the global bit of extra internationalisation strategy. • And then in terms of mobility, we work with. Are learning and teaching committee to make sure that our mobility programmes are embedded in the curriculum and the quality audited and controlled, and the same would be for our TNE development as well. 	<p>Awareness of legalities like taxation laws is observed.</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p>	
<p>UNIVERSITY 2</p>	<p>there's requirements on programs in the way approval to address the issue of decolonization</p> <p>elements of partnerships and placement operations</p> <p>we have a partnerships unit that manages our international franchise operation</p> <p>we have a policy that will practice around the development</p>	<p>Changes in Brexit and visa regulations are given significant consideration in order to offer opportunities.</p> <p>Awareness about placement opportunities and joint PhDs is observed.</p>	<p>strategy</p> <p>opportunities</p> <p>markets</p>

	<p>of international corporations</p> <p>we have a number of franchise partnerships</p>		
UNIVERSITY 3	<p>Recruitment numbers</p> <p>objective to grow our international student numbers for both undergraduate and graduate by five percent, by seven percent over the next five years</p> <p>a similar kind of an objective within the research arena, in the partnership arena as well</p>	<p>Well defined goals are observed like growth in international student numbers by 5-7%.</p> <p>Objectives have been setup for research and partnerships too. This signifies a significant interest in research and partnerships and high degree of awareness these fields.</p>	<p>Research partnership growth key areas</p>
UNIVERSITY 4	<p>For international student growth - International Step Change</p> <p>we've been given funding by the university to develop to reach the targets over a five-year period to the global graduate</p>	<p>Unstructured data is maintained about alumni and their careers.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement about presence of an alumni team that has frequent interactions with the students.</p>	<p>alumni</p>

	We have a separate research strategy which aligns with the university's strategic plan	Data about abilities and social experiences has been collected and analysed with a view to aim towards a strategy. Since 2014, emphasis has been provided to strategic investment towards internationalisation.	
UNIVERSITY 5	it's more important to have like a alumni backup alumni team has regular interactions with students since 2014 is all we really had a big push for internationalisation - Strategic sort of real pushing investment	Presence of a designated partnership unit to manage international franchise operation is observed. Strong support for international partnerships and recruitment. Also, there exists a policy in place based on the development of international corporations, research and postgraduate programs. High awareness about partnerships, also involvement in multiple franchise partnerships.	partnership placement study work
UNIVERSITY 6	looking at the changes with Brexit and with Visa regulations in terms of what opportunities that affords to the institution	Changes in Brexit and visa regulations are given significant consideration in order to offer opportunities. Awareness about placement opportunities and joint PhDs is observed.	strategy placements

UNIVERSITY 7		<p>Presence of a dedicated project - 'International Step Change' for international students' growth indicates a keen interest in internationalization by the university.</p> <p>Fund allocation to meet well defined targets signifies a well directed approach by the university.</p> <p>It is observed that a separate research strategy is in place that aligns with the university's plan.</p> <p>Presence of a learning and teaching committee to ensure cohesion of mobility programs with curriculum along with maintaining their quality and control.</p>	<p>growth strategy global research mobility</p>
UNIVERSITY 8	we have a policy that will practice around the development of international corporations	setting up various policies and developing international partners	policies and partnerships
UNIVERSITY 9	we have a number of franchise partnerships	strategies based on various external stakeholders	stakeholder relations
UNIVERSITY 10	Our learning and teaching committee to make sure that our mobility programmes are embedded in the curriculum and the quality audited and controlled, and the same would be for our TNE development as well	Focus on mobility programmes with inclusion of curriculum and partnerships	<p>mobility quality</p> <p>TNE development</p> <p>curriculum</p> <p>internationalisation</p>

UNIVERSITY 11	We need more students coming to us on exchange programs	Strong emphasis on student recruitment and exchange programs	Student recruitment exchange programs
UNIVERSITY 12	is branding and positioning, which is the whole marketing plan.	main agenda is creating a brand image	brand image
UNIVERSITY 13	Building partnerships and developing relations with various external stakeholders	High awareness about partnerships, also involvement in multiple franchise partnerships.	building partnerships

Appendix 12 Findings Themes and coding – Question 6

Ø Do you have a unit/division that is specifically responsible for internationalisation If yes, do you believe it is sufficiently resourced to achieve the internationalisation agenda?			
PARTICULARS	INTIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES

<p>UNIVERSITY 1</p>	<p>we now have within that what's called a global opportunities office and that is me and my team involved in and Partnerships and the international recruitment team</p>	<p>Global opportunities are given high significance. This is indicated by the presence of global opportunities office. Also, multiple initiatives have been undertaken like recruitment of a director, plans of a dedicated international department.</p> <p>Whilst there is acknowledgement about drastic changes, lack of stability and a history of small budget allocation, some rectification steps have been taken like the expansion of budget.</p> <p>As a result of rectifications steps, there is a high degree of optimism about positive results.</p>	<p>partnership recruitment control willingness for change</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY 2</p>	<p>we don't have a special department. We have three bits of the university that did the work on this</p>	<p>There is acknowledgement about presence of a hierarchy in the management designations.</p> <p>Responsibilities have been allotted to specific individuals and it is the dean who is responsible for resource management.</p> <p>Significant support is observed for internationalisation as indicated by the presence of an international agenda.</p>	<p>strategy resource management implementation</p>

		Also, presence of a dedicated office (international office) is observed.	
UNIVERSITY 3	<p>for many years, no we've had probably the resources probably grow by 25 to 30 to 40 percent, to be honest.</p> <p>really in the last three or four years that the universities taken this seriously.</p> <p>we're doing more recruitment activities, more fairs, more up to then more online activity, more online communications, more advertising, all kinds of activities be tripled, if not more, in the last few years compared to where we were</p>	<p>Significant growth in resources is observed. Range of growth has been claimed to be between 25 to 40%. This indicates adequate attention is being provided for resource management.</p> <p>Strong support for internationalization agenda since last three to four years. Support has been found to be in areas like recruitment and promotional activities.</p> <p>It is found that university expects international students, exchanges and partnerships and intends a growth in income through these.</p> <p>The university intends a growth in student numbers and thereby growth in diversity.</p> <p>A return on investment is desired and the university is willing to invest money in return for global presence.</p>	<p>resource</p> <p>recruitment</p> <p>partnership</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>sustainability</p> <p>travel</p> <p>investment</p>

<p>UNIVERSITY 4</p>	<p>we have an international development office which manages student recruitment and student mobility</p> <p>we have a separate academic partnerships office which manages the Tierney partnerships and the strategic partnerships.</p> <p>We also have a separate admissions department which works alongside them and digital marketing</p> <p>at the moment I think we're quite well resourced</p> <p>we are exploring a restructuring process</p>	<p>A dedicated department called - 'global engagement hub' is assigned to take care of internationalization strategy.</p> <p>Although the university falls short in adequacy of resources, delegation of authority into smaller teams and their cohesion has proved effective for managing their daily responsibility.</p> <p>A high confidence is observed among the colleagues and they have a high degree of awareness of each other's responsibilities.</p> <p>To attain a global outlook is one of they key intentions of the university.</p>	<p>resource</p> <p>strategy</p> <p>management</p> <p>partnership</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY 5</p>	<p>yes, we do</p> <p>called the global engagement Hub</p> <p>We've slightly reduced in size mainly because a few people have left</p> <p>we do we have a core team that there's 10 of us in the team</p> <p>probably we could do with a bit more resource</p>	<p>Absence of a specific department is handled but multiple teams that work in an agile fashion.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement about the need for increase in dedicated resources.</p> <p>The university is aware about partnerships in placements and study abroad and work abroad activities.</p>	<p>partnership</p> <p>study</p> <p>work</p>

UNIVERSITY 6	we have seven schools in the University those some schools so Dean manages resources within the school but oversees the courses and research and the provision within the schools	we have seven schools in the University those some schools , so Dean manages resources within the school but oversees the courses and research and the provision within the schools	research
UNIVERSITY 7	We have separate departments and different teams responsible for the same as we are undergoing restructuring	Dedicated offices to manage student recruitment and partnerships and presence of a separate admissions department indicates that responsibilities have been assigned to specific units. Currently the teams are undergoing a restructuring process. This points to a change in strategy. Strong support for resource management is observed. It is observed that the teams work in cohesion and awareness of recent trends like digital marketing is present.	development recruitment mobility delegation of authority
UNIVERSITY 8	Yes, we do and we are currently expanding	new strategies would be implemented	expansion

UNIVERSITY 9	our senior leadership looks after the international department and is working well	Leadership plays an important role	leadership support
UNIVERSITY 10	A dedicated international office with three directors who are responsible for international activities	Strong support to the international team is observed	leadership support
UNIVERSITY 11	Along with international department the academics are also involved in various activities	Collaborations of different departments to advance internationalisation is observed.	involvement of staff and other departments
UNIVERSITY 12	We don't have a department and they carry out all the international activities	All the activities are carried out by international department	management
UNIVERSITY 13	we have a dedicated department and further sub departments to carry out the activities	Dedicated offices to manage student recruitment and partnerships and presence of a separate admissions department indicates that responsibilities have been assigned to specific units.	different units

Appendix 13 Findings Themes and coding – Question 7

Ø What mechanisms are in place to promote internationalisation in your institution?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	<p>we do not have the fundamental academic resource in place</p> <p>we're also in the process of reviewing our processes</p> <p>we have recruited someone within the business school as a senior lecturer who has responsibility for international students</p> <p>what we've got to do is support those who do come to us write it.</p> <p>we have a couple of Staff in India who work for us. So they will be doing those briefings we constantly research our students. Monitor them at the end of their first semester</p>	<p>University acknowledges that they lack the fundamental academic resources for internationalization. Therefore, they fall short of having dedicated staff.</p> <p>It is observed that the currently a process review is in progress in the university.</p> <p>Significant awareness about the availability of opportunities but process and being under-resourced are key hurdles.</p> <p>A high degree of diversity is expected in the students' distribution. As per the university, bigger clusters of students from similar backgrounds is challenge.</p> <p>Emphasis is given on mental health along with physical health for the students.</p> <p>Track is kept of the students' health on a continuous basis.</p>	<p>workload</p> <p>management</p> <p>resource</p> <p>management</p> <p>process review</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>culture</p> <p>finances</p>

		The university possesses a high degree of awareness about the financial conditions of their international students and the ways they use to manage their finances.	
UNIVERSITY 2	<p>we're also in the process of reviewing our processes</p> <p>we have recruited someone within the business school as a senior lecturer who has responsibility for international students</p> <p>what we've got to do is support those who do come to us write it.</p> <p>we have a couple of Staff</p>	<p>Emphasis is on planning every year and on resource management.</p> <p>The institution is cautious on investments and intends to invest in case returns are expected.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement from the university about the number of international students being significantly low.</p>	<p>KPIs</p> <p>responsibilities</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>resource</p> <p>management</p> <p>budget</p> <p>allocation</p> <p>return on</p> <p>investment</p> <p>prioritization</p>

UNIVERSITY 3	<p>agenda is promoted through our vision and strategy document</p> <p>there is a global strategy and work on student recruitment</p> <p>we've got kind of like mass awareness, digital online advertising going on as well as on the ground and recruitment.</p> <p>So we have a research and impact campaign that we want basically to show off what we've done in the research area.</p> <p>much of our recruiting is through agents in Asia and not much in the in North America. Asia and Africa are very much driven.</p> <p>Singapore, we've actually got offices and we have staff that work for us in country in those offices</p> <p>And we've just recruited a similar number of staff in Nigeria as well</p>	<p>A high degree of clarity is observed in strategy and objectives as this institution promotes its agenda through a vision and strategy document.</p> <p>Multiple steps have been taken to ensure detailed planning and effective implementation of the global strategy.</p> <p>It is observed that university has undertaken multiple campaigns both physically and through digital media. Significant interest is displayed in advertising to establish presence and for mass awareness.</p> <p>Emphasis is given on research, collaborations, and partnerships.</p> <p>Also, a research and impact campaign are held to present accomplishments in research.</p> <p>Recruitments are predominantly done in Asia and Africa and the university has offices in India, China and Singapore.</p>	<p>culture</p> <p>advertising</p> <p>campaigns</p> <p>digital media</p> <p>demographic</p> <p>variations</p>
UNIVERSITY 4	<p>Go Global team will run a profile-raising event across our campuses</p> <p>social media campaigns</p> <p>several surveys of students to find out what students want, what type of programs, where in the world they want to have them</p>	<p>High degree of importance is given to various activities. Focus on student and staff development is observed.</p>	<p>opportunities</p> <p>surveys</p> <p>network</p> <p>partnerships</p>

	<p>work with the academic staff to develop programs</p> <p>also have the articulation partnerships that act as a pathway</p> <p>also have a private pathway provider who recruit students</p> <p>direct advertising on digital platforms</p>		
UNIVERSITY 5	<p>Various different programs to communicate with the student body.</p> <p>International partnerships and programmes are encouraged</p>	<p>The university attempts to initiate communication with the prospective students through their open day talks which includes introductory institutional welcome.</p> <p>International partnerships is encouraged and regarded highly and the university assists students in their attempts to find potential partners.</p> <p>It is observed that students are linked with the programs and the university exercises caution in order to ensure that students face minimum curriculum challenges.</p>	<p>student interaction study induction partnerships challenges</p>
UNIVERSITY 6	<p>stay connected with our global alumni as well. And that network can bring a whole different type of variety of different benefits to both of them in nine countries that they're from it to attract international students, attract international staff.</p>	<p>There is a resounding agreement about the alumni playing a key role in attracting the students, discussing about experiences and assisting with presentations.</p> <p>The university has a high degree of optimism about prospective students and guardians associating with alumni and their cultural</p>	<p>recruitment alumni</p>

		experiences. This enhances the alumni involvement in the process.	
UNIVERSITY 7	<p>alumni have had quite a significant role to play</p> <p>Alumni can talk about their experiences</p> <p>can help free departure</p> <p>can help with doing presentations</p>	<p>Presence of a dedicated team, 'Go global team' that runs profile raising events across the campus.</p> <p>A high degree of support from management is observed due to multiple initiatives like campaigns, surveys, recruitments and advertising.</p> <p>Surveys are organised to identify and analyse expectations of students and the feedback of surveys is taken into consideration for program development.</p> <p>There is an acknowledgement about utilising the global network of agents for inward student recruitment. The university is also associated with a private pathway provider that is involved with student recruitment.</p>	<p>opportunities</p> <p>surveys</p> <p>network</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>-</p>
UNIVERSITY 8	<p>We conduct various student and staff surveys and further work on the feedback</p>	<p>Surveys are organised to identify and analyse expectations of students and the feedback of surveys is taken into consideration for program development.</p>	<p>surveys and</p> <p>student</p> <p>feedback</p>

UNIVERSITY 9	to outreach our activities we use various digital platforms and social media	To enhance outreach, direct advertising is done on digital platforms.	digital platforms
UNIVERSITY 10	external partners and alumni play a major role	greater emphasis is on external partners and alumni	alumni external stakeholders
UNIVERSITY 11	research and ranking and community service	The university focuses on research collaborations and being higher up on the league table and serving the community	research collaborations league table serving the community
UNIVERSITY 12	research collaboration plays an important part along with overseas agents	University focuses on research and partnering with overseas agents	research collaborations and relations with overseas agents
UNIVERSITY 13	Advertisements and international fairs are mainly the mechanism used. Also, recommendations	Strong emphasis on advertisements and overseas fairs are focused	adverts fairs word of mouth

Appendix 14 Findings Themes and coding – Question 8

Ø How is the University leadership supporting internationalisation at the institution?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	Chancellor - is very supportive sponsor scholarships well connected and influential	A strong support is observed from the senior leadership, specifically, the chancellor. Authorities in the top management like the pro vice chancellor have a significant global exposure. Authorities like the pro vice chancellor and the chancellor are approachable and involve themselves among their interactions with the students and the staff. There is awareness about the senior management having a good network and being influential.	Authority implementation senior management support

<p>UNIVERSITY 2</p>	<p>Board of Governors - seeking us to present to them a new internationalization strategy</p> <p>leadership makes it clear that the resources are available</p> <p>gets the necessary support at the highest level</p>	<p>Presence of dedicated staff on specific positions is observed, for example having a separate events officer.</p> <p>High degree of presence of multiple student societies which are regarded as successful due to frequent events they organize and an adequate participation in such events.</p> <p>There is acknowledgement about overseas trips which have resulted in new partnerships and have contributed to teaching and learning.</p>	<p>student engagement</p> <p>delegation of authority</p> <p>partnerships</p> <p>research</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY 3</p>	<p>is actively seeking opportunities</p> <p>also from a research perspective and a partnership perspective</p>	<p>is actively seeking opportunities</p> <p>also from a research perspective and a partnership perspective</p> <p>It is noted that the university has made appointments at key responsible positions who can lead in strategy and can co-ordinate with top management positions like the vice chancellor.</p> <p>A significant growth in student numbers is intended.</p> <p>Significance is given to research perspective and partnerships.</p> <p>The institution is aware about the challenges met by students coming from backgrounds of non-English languages. As</p>	<p>Acclimatization</p> <p>leadership role</p> <p>challenges</p>

		observed, it causes hinderances to the teachers in their teaching experience as well.	
UNIVERSITY 4	looking to appoint a PVC international very shortly International Step Change Board, which is responsible for driving the international student growth heads of colleges are all supportive of the project	Awareness among the staff is observed about their steps taken and their corresponding large-scale impact. Emphasis is given on the activities related to business and on external engagements on a regional, national and international level. There is acknowledgement that strong support is provided by the top management and that the top teams are accessible by the teams working on ground level. The university is aware about the significance of strategy while working on internationalization.	Vision diversity multiple level engagement resource management focus areas senior management support
UNIVERSITY 5	focusing on all the work we do regionally with Businesses we do get very good level top-level support.	A lack of clarity observed in the staff about the understanding of the requirements from board of governors.	Strategy partnerships resource availability

		A strong support from the leadership is observed. This can be found in the investments university has made and the ready availability of resources.	leadership's direction
UNIVERSITY 6	there's visibility and sort of interaction with our students we have overseas trips promoting the university over cities when we set up new Partnerships overseas research for all teaching and learning	As per the university, there has been an ad-hoc appointment of a non-academic staff who is currently handling the day-to-day tasks relevant to internationalization. There are plans in place to appoint a university executive who will be undertaking this role in future.	Hierarchy management structure accountability
UNIVERSITY 7	we do have a a sovereign member of the university executive who will be undertaking that role in future	Effective use of top leadership in the university. Plans of recruiting dedicated personnel and appointing them on specific positions relevant to internationalization. Strong support by top management has driven confidence in among the staff in the lower divisions of management hierarchy.	Accountability leadership role higher management support
UNIVERSITY 8	We do have good support from to leaders and they do attend various activities and student forum	An effective and collaborative leadership support is observed	effective and collaborative

UNIVERSITY 9	overseas trips promoting the university overseas e set up, new partnerships overseas research for or teaching and learning. The senior staff broadly, engaged	Emphasis is given on partnerships and teaching and learning experience	Staff engagement Teaching and learning
UNIVERSITY 10	leadership makes it clear that the resources are available gets the necessary support at the highest level	There is strong support from senior management and leadership to promote internationalisation	Strong leadership support
UNIVERSITY 11	All the departments are well connected and receive a strong support from the senior leaders. They actively participate in various events	The university receives a strong support from the leadership who have active involvement in various activities	Participation and support in various activities
UNIVERSITY 12	Currently we are recruiting two international directors to support international process	A strong support from the leadership is observed. This can be found in the investments university has made and the ready availability of resources	Leadership Resources
UNIVERSITY 13	In various activities PVC and various senior staff from departments get involved. We are currently expanding the team	University is focusing on expanding the team and also has strong support from senior staff.	Expansion Involvement in activities

Ø What challenges have you encountered or perceive in attempting to implement your internationalisation agenda?

PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES
UNIVERSITY 1	Resource human resource we have a declining resource and the faculty our faculties have just gone through a redundancy process demoralized staff	Resource management, especially on the personnel front has been a concern for the university and there is awareness among the staff about it. This has impacted the work culture as the staff is quoted to be "demoralized". Sufficient financial support has been provided by the institution. The university acknowledges that the processes are time consuming and may take four to five months to bring in new students for work and/or education. However, the students have not been willing to wait for such longer periods and therefore move to a different university or workplace	resource management work culture among staff work process
UNIVERSITY 2	the issue is some staff who don't really get the agenda properly. we haven't got sufficient funds to support them completely	The university acknowledges that there have been multiple cases of clubs promising not to	Provisioning demand

		<p>mention joint campuses, etc. This has been a challenge.</p> <p>It is observed that the institution regards sponsor relationships highly and there has been an increase in sponsorships.</p> <p>There is an agreement to realise the need of impact analysis. For example, some institutions seek to make games without assessing the potential future implications and this can cause problems later.</p> <p>Understanding of international isolation agenda is identified to be a key challenge.</p> <p>Student societies are regarded very highly and are found to have high quality standards. These make significant contribution in international student connections.</p> <p>It is noted that the university encourages diversity and is aware about the significance of having international staff. The university also</p>	<p>risk analysis</p> <p>competition</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>understanding of the</p> <p>international</p> <p>isolation agenda</p> <p>engagement</p> <p>student societies</p> <p>implications</p>
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		encourages the staff to take the students to global institutions and acknowledges that this happens on a regular basis.	
UNIVERSITY 3	<p>we want to increase student numbers, but that requires a great deal of travel and carbon footprint</p> <p>we want to have a diverse group of students</p> <p>market is very much China driven.</p> <p>We have English language difficulties some time</p> <p>Europe and Brexit often combine Europe and the UK together as one kind of entity</p> <p>we will probably see a downturn in our interactions and collaborations and student numbers from Europe</p> <p>research partnerships may also stand for Brexit</p> <p>Other challenges, competitors</p> <p>very competitive market for everything that we want to achieve</p>	<p>It is observed that the institution is driven to increase student numbers. However, the challenges it faces is that higher student numbers are related to a higher volume of travel and greater amount of carbon footprint.</p> <p>The university intends for diversity among its student body.</p> <p>The market is regarded is very China driven and the university expresses that getting quality students and potentially successful ones is a challenge due to heavy reliance on China.</p> <p>It is noted that the institution has managed to meet the objectives of its sustainability agenda.</p> <p>The university identifies budget management and resource management as challenges during the promotions.</p>	<p>Travel</p> <p>sustainability</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>advertising and promotions</p> <p>resource management</p> <p>budget management</p> <p>competition</p>

		<p>The university also predicts that Brexit may result in reducing interactions and collaborations as the costs may rise after Brexit. As per university, Brexit may cause research partnerships to fall in volume.</p> <p>The university also identifies rising competition as a challenge to face and expresses that the market has been very competitive.</p>	
UNIVERSITY 4	<p>managing expectations in terms of the speed of growth</p> <p>it's so competitive in the world</p>	<p>High significance is given to legalities as the university takes into consideration the terms of the agreement with its partners.</p> <p>Cultural difference, communication, governance and understanding of the partners are identified as the key challenges faced by the university.</p> <p>University acknowledges that they have watched their partners work very hard.</p> <p>Preference of communication mediums is regarded as a hinderance while collaborating among partners. For example, the first partner</p>	<p>Partnerships</p> <p>negotiations</p> <p>legalities</p> <p>culture</p> <p>communication</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>funding</p> <p>strategy</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>relationships</p> <p>awareness</p>

		<p>may prefer using emails and a second may either call on a phone or visit directly for a physical meeting.</p> <p>The university is optimistic about students finding funds for themselves, either through crowdfunding or by applying.</p> <p>It is observed that the institution has attempted to convince students and their families about the importance of going abroad but found that a challenge.</p> <p>The university views that early funding results in more opportunities for students.</p> <p>A higher degree of positivity is detected among the students in terms of awareness and interest and the university considers this to be in the right direction.</p> <p>The university has found that there is a lesser degree of awareness of opportunities among the</p>	<p>recruitment</p> <p>staff ability</p> <p>demographic differences</p>
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		people and this stops them from reaping the potential benefits.	
UNIVERSITY 5	<p>legal issues about the agreement</p> <p>cultural difference</p> <p>Watching the partners also work very hard</p> <p>using email or using which sort of form of communication</p> <p>governance</p> <p>trying to encourage the students to find funding themselves</p> <p>challenge of convincing students of the importance of going abroad</p> <p>that challenge of just of convincing the students and the families of</p> <p>all the importance of either internationalisation</p> <p>often people just aren't aware</p>	<p>The emphasis of university is predominantly on resources as compared to on staff.</p> <p>There is an agreement about some staff not having clarity about the agenda.</p> <p>As per the university, a key challenge identified is financial stability of the students who don't come from wealthy backgrounds. The university express inability to completely support them although makes attempts to do so.</p>	<p>resource</p> <p>management</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>budget allocation</p>
UNIVERSITY 6	<p>still a general reticence against it for very good reasons you know</p> <p>there's been a lot of problematic cases of Club to provision</p> <p>promising</p> <p>joint campuses</p> <p>it's becoming much more competitive</p> <p>understanding of the international isolation agenda</p>	<p>The university acknowledges that they were, in the past working on a strategy. However, along with this, it is observed that integration is seen as a challenge.</p> <p>The university notes that presence of high diversity may result in loss of direct control.</p>	<p>Strategy</p> <p>integration</p> <p>lack of direct control</p> <p>-</p>

		A significant degree of awareness about course structure is observed. -	
UNIVERSITY 7	<p>“Responding to opportunity”</p> <p>Follow the university’s competitors who already have a strategy.</p>	<p>managing expectations in terms of the speed of growth</p> <p>it's so competitive in the world</p> <p>There is a resounding agreement about managing expectations to be the biggest challenge that university faces.</p> <p>A second key challenge that university faces is competition. However, the university expresses confidence in promotions.</p> <p>The university identifies persuasion of students and convincing them about a higher quality of academic and living experience.</p>	<p>managing expectations</p> <p>growth</p> <p>competition</p> <p>student persuasion</p>
UNIVERSITY 8	<p>Changing context: the national policy, the pursuit of privatisation, the collaborative agreements made, the obvious financial need to recruit overseas students and generate external research</p>	<p>The university faces challenges in terms of recruiting overseas students due to various government policies</p>	<p>Collaboration</p> <p>finance</p>

UNIVERSITY 9	Commitment to internationalisation is a major issue faced. We want to be a global player. However, we need finance and support from the management.	Challenges faced due to commitment and support from the management is majorly highlighted.	Global competition Management support
UNIVERSITY 10	Being an internationalised community is a challenge due to various cultural differences also due to competition it is difficult to maintain the numbers of international students. Need to be visible internationally.	Cultural differences are the major challenges mentioned by the university	multi culture competition
UNIVERSITY 11	Government pressure to increase international students' numbers. Pressure of competition is mainly what the current situation is	High degree of challenge faced is due to the pressure to recruit students and sustain in the competition.	Government pressure competition
UNIVERSITY 12	very competitive market for everything that we want to achieve. It is difficult to balance the expectations	Universities finds balancing expectations and maintaining and sustaining in the market	Balance between expectation
UNIVERSITY 13	Managing expectations of the staff, students, stakeholders is great challenge we face at the point. Also, availability of resources	The emphasis of university is predominantly on resources as compared to on staff. Further	Managing expectations resources

		challenge highlighted is managing the expectations of staff ,students and stakeholders.	
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Appendix 16 Findings Themes and coding – Question 10

Ø How would you differentiate your institution’s approach to internationalisation in relation to other institutions?			
PARTICULARS	INITIAL FINDINGS	KEY FINDINGS	THEMES

UNIVERSITY 1	<p>I think we are very flexible.</p> <p>we would take very managed risk</p> <p>might consider things that other universities would not so I think that's probably how We differentiate ourselves</p> <p>So we need to work within the boundaries of things</p> <p>We do still have a great reputation.</p>	<p>The university mainly focuses on reputation and managing work life balance</p>	<p>Flexibility</p> <p>reputation</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>competition</p> <p>opportunities</p> <p>challenges</p> <p>research</p>
UNIVERSITY 2	<p>it's not a Catholic university, but it's a Catholic Faith Foundation university.</p> <p>We have a very strong emphasis on employability</p> <p>tends to choose partners overseas who work in the same way.</p> <p>they've done a lot of stuff developing the stuff around how they will how they can change their curriculum to reflect an international perspective rather than just a UK based perspective.</p>	<p>The universities has built partnerships overseas which creates a brand image and also focus on collaborative curriculum</p>	<p>collaborative approach</p> <p>interactions</p> <p>diversity</p> <p>opportunities</p> <p>employability</p> <p>interest</p>
UNIVERSITY 3	<p>recruitment is the way that we differentiate</p> <p>much of the tape, our location, our campuses, our research strengths, which differentiate us very much, our recent strength being we've got five key research</p>		<p>Recruitment</p> <p>research strengths</p> <p>employability support</p>

	<p>strengths</p> <p>I think we can differentiate on going forward, is our career path and our employability support to the help that we give students internships, work experience, CV, career fairs, interview techniques</p> <p>we've ranked really highly in quite a lot of tables for our careers part</p> <p>we've got campuses in Singapore, Malaysia.</p>	<p>University advertises on the location.</p> <p>Focuses on research and employability support.</p> <p>They also have a great emphasis on rankings and having campuses on various locations</p>	<p>global presence</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY 4</p>	<p>wonderful location by the sea</p> <p>we used up a lot of student experience</p> <p>we do a lot of location-based marketing</p> <p>we have a very good work life balance</p>	<p>University prioritises on work life balance.</p> <p>They mainly advertise on the location – location-based marketing</p>	<p>Authority</p> <p>growth</p> <p>research</p> <p>delegations</p> <p>institutional presence</p> <p>investments</p> <p>profile building</p> <p>partnership</p>

UNIVERSITY 5	<p>as a university we don't we don't offer any form of authority</p> <p>we don't offer any of our programs overseas</p> <p>used sort of the growth of new sort of fields of expertise.</p> <p>We are looking much more also at the research</p> <p>institutional intervention and investment</p> <p>been the only ones do football training for years in a row</p>	<p>They focus on growth and building</p> <p>partnerships. They are more focused on</p> <p>development</p>	<p>Employability</p> <p>curriculum</p> <p>perspective</p> <p>development</p>
UNIVERSITY 6	<p>collaborative approach</p> <p>we're looking for long-term Partnerships</p> <p>among top 10 in the UK for diversity and employability</p> <p>we add a lot of value</p> <p>we focus on the individual Learners</p> <p>we focus on adding parts to an offering so it's not just about an individual transaction. It's about an overall working relationship.</p>	<p>Emphasis is given on collaboration and</p> <p>diversity</p>	<p>Recruiting</p> <p>approach</p> <p>collaboration</p> <p>diversity</p>
UNIVERSITY 7	<p>focused on international and internationalization for 10 years, though, it has</p> <p>been at the forefront.</p> <p>approach to internationalisation, it's a comprehensive approach and compares</p>	<p>The main focus is on student experience</p> <p>and creating a healthy environment with</p> <p>work life balance</p>	<p>Location</p> <p>student experience</p> <p>work life balance</p> <p>marketing</p>

	well, I think with whether the whether the universities in the U.K. Its more about student experience and having a work life balance		
UNIVERSITY 8	We differentiate ourselves because of the work we do in our research and the reputation we have gained	There is strong importance given to research, reputation and having a global presence.	Research Reputation Global presence
UNIVERSITY 9	We have strong partnerships and also have campuses at various locations. This builds on our reputation.	The universities focuses on partnerships and creating a brand reputation also having various campuses across the globe.	Partnerships Rankings Campuses at various locations Reputation
UNIVERSITY 10	We provide placement opportunities which improves the student experience.	Emphasis is on improving student experience	Placement opportunities Student experience Career opportunities
UNIVERSITY 11	We mainly capitalise on having higher up on the league table. Further we have different collaborations with various partners.	Importance is given to building partnerships with overseas universities and climbing up the league table	Partnerships Rankings
UNIVERSITY 12	We mostly focus on providing world class service to our students. We are in centre so it's easy for students to commute	University focuses on building on the location aspect and focuses on student experience .	Location Placement opportunities Student experience

UNIVERSITY 13	Our differentiation strategy comes from the research projects and activities we conduct. This helps to improve our global presence.	Focus on building partnerships and research is observed	Partnerships Research Reputation and global presence
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